

Zero Emission Network to facilitate CCUS uptake in industrial clusters
(HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02-12)

D3.1 CCUS value chains for the two CCUS ZEN regions selected for further development in WP4

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This document requires the following approvals:

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No industry has committed at this stage to implement the scenarios presented in the deliverable D3.1. The scenarios presented here, while based on an industrial reality on the ground, are forward-looking scenarios that explore the potential of CCUS in each of these regions

Executive summary

The main objective of this deliverable is to prepare a detailed integrated technical and nontechnical characterisation of CCUS value chains for the two CCUS ZEN regions selected for further development of business cases in WP4. These CCUS value chains in the Baltic and Mediterranean regions were selected from 8 projects proposed in D1.2 which were selected by WP1 from 15 value chains proposed in two regions by project partners.

Among technical parameters detailed metrics for CO₂ emission points, CO₂ transport pipelines and ships, CO₂ storage sites, CO₂ use options and CO₂ injection, and monitoring are collected, developed and estimated using technical data collected by WP1 and technical modelling made in WP3. Possibilities to reuse available infrastructure are carefully assessed versus planning and construction of new one as an option for saving time and resources.

Among nontechnical parameters, national strategies, regulatory, social, political parameters and financial support to CCUS projects as well as MRV readiness parameters are collected for the countries and considered. CCS national and international regulations, gaps and challenges are assessed for the developed value chains.

The Baltic-2 CCUS project includes nine clusters of 33 emitters divided in two development phases from three countries (Denmark, Sweden and Germany) with an annual CO₂ emissions volume of 22.7 Mt and respective captured CO₂ volume of 20.1 Mt, from which up to 6.1 Mt will be directed for utilisation (CCU). The project is planned for 30 years of CO₂ storage in six DSA (deep saline aquifers), and for 20 years of CO₂ storage in two DOGFs. All CO₂ captured in the Bremen cluster will be utilised in a CCU sub-value chain. Emissions captured in the Gothenburg cluster which are not utilised, are sent to offshore geological storage sites in Denmark (Inez and Lisa sites). From Esbjerg, a ship with CO₂ from the remaining German industrial clusters and the Fredericia and Esbjerg clusters is sent to Greensand and Inez sites. All CO₂ that cannot be shipped from these clusters or that is captured from the remaining clusters is sent to a pipeline network. Using pipeline network, the CO₂ not used in a CCU installation in Aalborg is distributed to the geological storage sites Bifrost, Jammerbugt, Gassum, Voldum and Thorning.

The Mediterranean-2 CCUS scenario is a transboundary project from France to Spain planned for 20 years. It includes three clusters with 32 CO₂ emitters from two countries and one storage site offshore Spain in DSA. The included industrial clusters are the Tarragona and the Barcelona clusters in Spain, and the Fos-Marseille cluster in France, annually producing 23.82 Mt CO₂. The geological storage site Castellón is located offshore Tarragona in the Ebro Basin. The captured 9.77 Mt CO₂ will be collected in the three clusters hubs, partly used depending on the viability of the CO₂ use options and the remaining CO₂ will be transported and stored in Castellón site. In the reference case, an onshore gathering hub at Tarragona port will collect the CO₂ from the three clusters: CO₂ from local Tarragona emitters, CO₂ from Barcelona cluster sent by an offshore dense phase pipeline and CO₂ from Fos-Marseille cluster transported by ships. From the onshore gathering hub at Tarragona, a single dense phase offshore pipeline will send the collected CO₂ to the subsea system including subsea injection wells around 60 km away.

CO₂ flow rates to be captured, transported and stored are limited in Mediterranean-2 project by the recently reported storage capacity of one Castellon site offshore Spain (200 Mt), while there are no such limitations in Baltic-2, using 8 storage sites onshore and offshore North Sea with total mean capacity above 1 Gt CO₂.

Deliverable 3.1. CCUS value chains for two regions

Considering planned infrastructure, the Mediterranean-2 project is less heavy and will make less environmental impact, planning less injection and monitoring wells, and less pipelines per one ton of CO₂ injected compared to Baltic-2. However, the Baltic-2 can get higher revenues from the higher annual and total bio-CO₂ used.

Regulatory bases are more ready in Denmark, than in Spain, and Denmark already awarded permits for CO₂ storage demonstration, with first injections made already in offshore Greensand field in Denmark with cross-border transported CO₂.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND UNITS

Abbreviations

CCS – CO₂ Capture and Storage

CCU – Carbon Capture and Utilisation

CCUS – CO₂ Capture, Utilization and Storage

CO₂ – Carbon Dioxide

CM – cooling medium

CP – Cement Plant

DEA – Danish Energy Agency

D1.2 – Deliverable 1.2 of CCUS ZEN project WP1

DH – district heating

DOGF – Depleted Oil & Gas field

DWSIM – an open-source CAPE-OPEN-compliant chemical process simulation software

DSA – Deep saline aquifer

EoS – Equation of State

EU – European Union

IPCEI – Important Project of Common European Interest

IS – International Standard

ISIF – Intermediate storage injection facilities

ISO – International Standard Organisation

FSIU – Floating Storage and Injection Unit

GHG – Greenhouse Gas

GIS – Geographic Information System

QGIS – is an open-source geographic information system

LCO₂ – liquid CO₂

LMTD – logarithmic mean temperature difference

LP – Low Pressure

MIn – Million

MAIP - Maximum Allowable Incidental Pressure

MAOP - Maximum Allowable Operating Pressure

MP – Medium Pressure

MRV – Monitoring, Reporting and Verification

M_w – moment magnitude, magnitude scale in logarithmic scale for ranking earthquakes by size, similar to the local magnitude/Richter scale (M_L). In M_w, „w“ stands for work (energy)

NECP – National Energy and Climate Plans

NCT – National Carbon Tax

NRTL – National Recognised Testing Laboratories

PP – Power Plant

PFD – Process Flow Diagram

SPA –Special Protection Area)

SCI – Sites of Community Importance

T&S – Transport and Storage

U-value – heat transfer coefficient

WP3 – Work Package 3

WTE – Waste-to-energy

WFS – Web Feature Service

WMS – Web Map Service

Units

cP – Centipoise, unit of fluid viscosity

in. – inches

m – metre

Gcal/hr – Giga calories per hour

g/l – gram per litre

kg – kilogram

kg/m³ – kilograms per cubic metre

kg/s – kilograms per second

km – kilometer

km² – square kilometre

kt – kiloton

kt/y – kiloton per year

kW – kilowatt

kW/h – kilowatt per hour

l – litre

MJ/km – megajoule per kilometre

MPa – mega Pascal

Mt – million tonnes

Mt/y – million tonnes per year

MW – megawatt

MWh – megawatt hours

m – metre

m/s – metres per second

mD – milli Darci

t – tonne

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t/hr – tonne per hour

T, °C – temperature by Celsius

TJ – Terajoule

W – watt

W/m² K – watts per square meter per kelvin, SI unit for heat transfer coefficient

1 Introduction

The main objective of this deliverable is to prepare a detailed integrated technical and nontechnical characterisation of CCUS value chains for the two CCUS ZEN regions selected for further development of business cases in WP4. These CCUS value chains in the Baltic and Mediterranean regions were selected from 8 projects proposed in D1.2 which were selected by WP1 from 15 value chains proposed in two regions by project partners.

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Among non-technical parameters, national strategies, regulatory, social, and political parameters, and financial support to CCUS projects, as well as MRV readiness parameters, are collected for the countries and considered. CCS national and international regulations, gaps and challenges are assessed for the developed value chains.

General technical arrangements and methodologies applied, which could be common, or different for the CCUS value chains in two regions are also reported.

Section 2 starts by outlining the technical arrangements involved in CCUS value chains. Section 3 introduces the Baltic Region case of the Baltic-2 CCUS project including the assumptions and methodology of the analysis, and the specific techniques involved as well as a description of the emissions sources in the involved countries Germany, Sweden and Denmark. It also outlines the storage sites and utilization options involved and the transport infrastructures. The subsection 3.9 dives into the non-technical issues in the three countries and 9.10. outlines how technical and non-technical issues intersect.

Section 4 introduces the Mediterranean case of the Mediterranean-2 CCUS project, including CO₂ emitters from France and Spain captured and transported to CO₂ storage site offshore Spain. Section 5 offers short summary of both projects, their comparison and conclusions.

2 CCUS value chain technical arrangements

2.1 CO₂ emissions capture and purification

The CCUS ZEN project has collected recent emission data (2021) to identify relevant clusters of CO₂ emitters. The emission data are processed in QGIS and used for analysis.

To calculate amount of CO₂ captured and transported the following assumptions will be taken:

- CO₂ will be captured at the plants using one of the capture technologies listed in D1.1 (Ringstad et al, 2023).
- It is assumed that high-purity CO₂ has been collected from the plants and compressed to a maximum of 15 MPa for introduction to the pipeline and transport and this compression is included into the capture costs reported by technology vendors and capture projects.
- However, when these costs will be needed for estimation of CO₂ use costs, or CO₂ supply price, the ready values will be taken from available reports and publications.

CO₂ captured is lower than CO₂ produced at the capture plant, while CO₂ avoided is lower than CO₂ captured (Figure 2-1). CO₂ used ex-situ for mineral carbonation or any other CO₂

utilization pathways should be calculated and excluded from CO₂ flow transported and injected.

Figure 2-1 CO₂ emissions avoided versus CO₂ produced (red), captured (blue), used and stored (green) (Shogenova& Shogenov, 2020)

2.2 Conditioning and compression

2.2.1 Compression

Recompression using booster pumps will be needed to keep CO₂ in a dense phase when the pressure drops below 8 MPa. The technical parameters of booster pumps depend on CO₂ flow rate, and recompression duty depends on discharge pressure, varying for different CO₂ flow rates. The booster pump duty determines the energy required for their operation. Energy for booster pumps could be supplied either from the electricity grid or a purpose-built generator (Figure 2-2, EPRI, 2015). Energy costs in remote areas and offshore could be significantly higher than onshore near the electric grids. CO₂ emissions produced during this operation should be considered for the calculation of CO₂ emissions avoided (Shogenova & Shogenov, 2020).

Figure 2-2 Recompression duty for transported CO₂ versus discharge pressure for various CO₂ flowrates (EPRI, 2015, Fig. 107)

2.3 Transportation

2.3.1 Pipelines

For CO₂ pipelines design and specifications, the International Standard ISO 27913 “Carbon dioxide capture, transportation and geological storage. Pipeline transportation Systems” published in 2016 should be applied. The first edition of this standard was developed in 2016 by the Technical Committee of the ISO/TC 265 (Carbon dioxide capture, transportation, and geological storage). The second edition of this standard ISO/FDIS 27913 is under preparation now, as IS should be updated every five years.

In the Mediterranean scenario, the pipelines could be designed using X70 steel and 1500 lb flange rating (designed to 25.5 MPa upper working pressure). They allow a maximum working pressure of 15 MPa. The pipeline diameter should be determined depending on two calculated for this scenario parameters - the transport distance and CO₂ flow-rate (Figure 2-3, Table 2-1, EPRI, 2015). Number of boosters needed for CO₂ recompression is shown at Fig.2-2.

Figure 2-3 CO₂ pipeline diameter versus transport distance for various CO₂ flowrates (EPRI, 2015, Fig. 102)

Table 2-1 Data and equation coefficient for pipeline diameter as a function of distance and CO₂ flow-rate for steel grade X70 and flange-class CL1500, shown in Figure 2-3 (EPRI, 2015, Table 100)

Nominal diameter (mm)	CO ₂ flow-rate (Mt/y)										
	1	3	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	
Pipeline length (km)	17	150	250	300	400	450	500	550	600	650	700
	50	200	300	400	500	550	650	700	750	800	850
	100	200	350	450	550	650	750	800	850	900	950
	200	250	400	500	650	750	850	900	1,000	1,050	1,100
	400	300	450	550	750	850	950	1,050	1,100	1,200	1,250
	600	300	500	600	800	900	1,050	1,150	1,200	1,300	1,350
	800	350	550	650	850	1,000	1,100	1,200	1,300	1,350	1,450
	1,000	350	550	650	850	1,000	1,150	1,250	1,350	1,400	1,500
	1,200	400	550	700	900	1,050	1,200	1,300	1,400	1,450	n/a
	1,400	400	600	700	950	1,100	1,200	1,350	1,450	1,500	n/a
a	79.3	141	187	233	255	296	315	344	380	406	
b	0.2194	0.197	0.184	0.192	0.201	0.197	0.200	0.198	0.190	0.189	
R ²	0.976	0.994	0.990	0.996	0.997	0.996	0.999	0.998	0.999	0.999	

Note: The data in this table have been correlated as a power-law equation of the form $D = aL^b$ where D is the nominal diameter in mm and L is the pipeline length in km.

Transportation of CO₂ through pipelines is feasible in both gas and dense phase. Gas phase transportation is often carried at pressures below 3 MPa, to limit the possibility of CO₂ condensation due to low ambient temperatures. Gaseous CO₂ transportation is often required in densely populated areas, where the construction of high-pressure pipelines is not allowed. Normally, dense-phase transportation is preferred since, for a given pipeline internal diameter, a larger volume of CO₂ can be transferred. Given the ambient temperature constraints, to avoid any CO₂ vaporization in dense phase pipelines, the CO₂ is usually transported at pressure above 8 MPa. On the other hand, the maximum operating pressure is limited to around 15 MPa, a value constrained by the costs originating from the pipeline thickness. Moreover, depending on the location of the pipeline, the pressure of the CO₂ may vary. Offshore pipelines typically allow higher pressures than onshore pipelines. For onshore pipelines, to overcome pressure losses, booster stations may be usually located approximately every 100 km. Although the conditioning required for pipeline transportation eventually depends on the “history” of the CO₂ and its conditions before entering the pipeline, compression is usually required to increase the pressure of the CO₂ from the pressure level at the outlet of the capture facility. Since a high amount of heat is generated during compression, energy integration with district heating, when relevant, is also a possibility. In this way, some of the costs associated with compression can be offset with a revenue stream from heat sales.

Often, to benefit from economies of scale, emitters would group into clusters and share the most expensive infrastructure. In this way, each emitter would have to compress the CO₂ up to the pressure level of a gaseous pipeline leading towards a central compression facility. At this facility, the incoming CO₂ from several emitters is then compressed from the arrival pressure up to the 12–13 MPa required for dense phase transportation. Once compressed, the CO₂ is then further transferred through a dense-phase pipeline. Depending on the dense-phase pipeline length, pressure boosters can be located every 100 km to ensure single-(dense) phase CO₂ transportation.

2.3.2 Ships

Depending on the amount and the distance, CO₂ ship transportation may be more attractive than pipeline transportation. When the source points are scattered along the coast, have low CO₂ emissions, and the CO₂ is to be delivered to an offshore sink, ships may be more economically feasible compared to long offshore pipelines. Moreover, ship transportation may also be more suitable during early project phases due to its flexibility in accommodating the integration of different emitters and CO₂ storage sites over time. Although at a much lower scale, the transportation of CO₂ by ships, driven by the food and beverage industry, has been taking place for 30 years. CO₂ carriers are currently being designed for low (≈ 0.7 MPa), medium (≈ 1.5 MPa) and high-pressure (≈ 4 MPa) transportation. Lower design pressures entail cooling of the CO₂ to lower temperatures ($\approx -47^\circ\text{C}$ at 0.7 MPa), to ensure liquid conditions. Yet, due to weight constraints, the upper capacity of medium and higher-pressure ships is usually lower compared to that of low-pressure ships. Medium-pressure ships, with capacities of up to 12500 m³ are among the most preferred shipping option. A conceptual design of a CO₂ carrier is shown in Figure 2-4.

Before shipping, the CO₂ needs to be conditioned (liquefied) at the required pressure and temperature for ship transport. For ship transportation, the CO₂ can be liquefied at multiple conditions provided these (conditions) fall between the triple and critical point. As these conditions approach either the triple or critical point, higher refrigeration or compression loads, respectively, are required. Three different liquefaction pressures are usually considered, i.e., 0.7, 1.5, and 4 MPa, consistent with low, medium, and high-pressure shipping. The liquefaction of the CO₂ may be achieved following different process alternatives. The most common ways of liquefying the CO₂ are either by relying on a closed (external) refrigeration cycle (e.g., ammonia) or via an open refrigeration cycle, consisting of multiple consecutive

compression & expansion stages. The latter one is also known as the Linde-Hampson system. Ammonia-based refrigeration is often referred as the most cost-optimum. Yet, at the lowest liquefaction pressure considered here (e.g., 0.7 MPa), given the low temperature needed for the CO₂ stream, the ammonia evaporator should operate at vacuum conditions. Moreover, liquefaction via ammonia may also involve additional challenges from an environmental-permitting point of view. Thus, the final configuration of the liquefaction cycle will eventually be project specific.

Figure 2-4 Conceptual design of a CO₂ carrier (Element Energy, 2018)

The minimum storage capacity should provide enough volume to shelter any incoming CO₂ to account for the times that there is no ship at the harbour; this will depend on the shipping frequency. At the interface between the liquefaction facility and ship transportation, an intermediate storage is required as a buffer in case, for whatever reasons (e.g., bad weather conditions), the shipping of CO₂ is not feasible. The capacity of this intermediate storage shall be enough to accommodate the volume equivalent to several days' incoming CO₂ flowrates; the number of days may vary from a couple of days up to even a week, depending on how often and how long events that may impede ship transportation are envisioned to occur. At the intermediate storage, the CO₂ may be stored in either horizontal or vertical tanks. The design conditions of the storage tanks shall be consistent with the liquefaction pressure & temperature.

Ship transportation requires also that harbour facilities (e.g., berth or quay structure) are in place. The berth or quay structure shall include all the items needed for the safe ship pass and mooring (e.g., breasting and mooring dolphin, platforms, fender system, berthing aid system, etc). In some cases, re-using an existing berth may be possible. Yet, in the latter case, earthworks and demolition may still be needed to re-purpose the existing berths for receiving CO₂ ships (e.g., removal of existing pipes or adapting platform for CO₂ shipping). Moreover, each berth shall include pipelines and loading arms required for ship loading.

2.4 Assumptions and methodology

Figure 2-5 Representation of a CO₂ value chain process considering pipeline transportation

This section is designed to establish a framework and foundational assumptions, along with outlining the value chain process that underpins the development of the Baltic-2 and Mediterranean-2 projects. Figure 2-5 and Figure 2-6 exemplify key components within a CO₂ transportation network, each of which has been incorporated into different sections, geographies and scenarios of the Baltic-2 value chain structure.

Each mode of transportation in the value chain scenario requires distinct equipment, spatial allocation, and energy usage. Table 2-2 enumerates the specific characteristics and assumptions associated with each building block integrating the transportation network within the project's framework.

Figure 2-6 Representation of a CO₂ value chain process considering mixed, i.e., ship and pipeline, transportation

Compression and liquefaction services may also generate heat that can be recovered and used for district heating purposes. This report also assessed the heat and material balances according to section 3.2.1. The flowrates used for the heat and material balance were estimated assuming the Carbon Capture Units are operational 8000 hours per year. More specific assumptions are stated in the following sections.

Table 2-2 Building blocks and assumptions

Transportation block		Description	Technical assumptions
	Emitter	The emitters are listed in Section Error! Reference source not found. for Baltic case and 4.4 for Mediterranean case. It is assumed that each emitter delivers CO ₂ at final purity. The compositional variability resulting from different CO ₂ sources is not considered.	
	Cluster	A geographic concentration of interconnected businesses, suppliers, and associated institutions in a particular field, e.g., emission-intensive facilities located in tight geographical clusters. It is assumed that the cluster encompasses all the transportation blocks from the emitter and before high-pressure pipeline or long-distance shipping.	
	CO ₂ capture (incl. dehydration and purification)	CO ₂ dehydration, conditioning and treatment is considered to take place in the emitters site. CO ₂ will be captured at the plants using one the following capture technologies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post-Combustion Carbon Capture • Pre-Combustion Carbon Capture • Oxyfuel Processes 	Assumed CO ₂ Capture Recovery of 95%
	Compressor (gas phase)	The compressor (gas phase) performs an essential stage in the transportation value chain within the cluster for the CO ₂ to achieve the necessary pressure.	Drying and pressurization of CO ₂ downstream the emitter up to 3 MPa for gathering pipelines or further conditioning for transportation.
	CO ₂ gathering pipeline	The gathering pipeline operates within a cluster, at 3 MPa to transport gaseous CO ₂ from multiple emitters to common facilities such as a high-pressure compressor station, liquefaction, or intermediate hub.	Operation at 3 MPa

Deliverable 3.1. CCUS value chains for two regions

Transportation block		Description	Technical assumptions
	Liquefaction	For intermediate storage and transportation of CO ₂ using trucks or ships (or any batch transportation method), liquefaction is required. At medium pressure, i.e., 1.5 MPa, the CO ₂ is cooled to temperatures close to -30°C. Emitters within a cluster may share the liquefaction facilities to benefit from economies of scale.	MP: around 1.5 MPa and -30°C LP: around 0.7 MPa and -50°C
	Temporary (Buffer) storage (Liquified CO ₂)	The buffer storage is required at the emitter site for batch transportation options such as trucks or ships. The storage buffer was sized for three days of production plus one batch of transported CO ₂ . The temporary storage facility allows the liquefaction facility to continue operating without interruption, and the excess CO ₂ produced can be stored until it can be exported in case of ship unavailability.	Approx. 3 days of LCO ₂ production buffer storage
	Truck / lorry	In the Baltic-2 value chain, lorries may perform short range transportation of CO ₂ within a cluster from local emitters to a common storage hub. It is assumed that each lorry can carry 25 m ³ of CO ₂ at 1.5–2 MPa.	
	Barge	Similar to trucks, barges perform short range transportation of CO ₂ by sea or river within a cluster from local emitters to a common storage hub.	Each barge can carry 150 m ³ of CO ₂ at 1.5-2 MPa
	Intermediate storage hub	The intermediate storage hub is defined as a group of storage tanks which serve as buffer for export or import. It can serve an entire cluster of emitters as an export hub, or multiple clusters as a receiving hub. It is dimensioned as five days of flow plus one batch of CO ₂ transported from or to it.	
	Compressor / pump (dense and supercritical phases)	The compressor/pump arrangement pressurises CO ₂ to dense or supercritical phase at 12 MPa for long distance pipeline transportation. It can serve a single emitter, multiple, or a defined cluster.	Up to 12 MPa
	Export pipeline (Dense Phase Pipeline)	The export pipeline transports CO ₂ continuously through long distances at supercritical or dense phase. It is designed to operate at 12 MPa.	Operation between 12–15 MPa

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Transportation block		Description	Technical assumptions
	Ship	The ships can serve emitters or clusters for long distance transportation to import storage hubs or offshore storage sites. Low and middle pressure is assumed (0.7 and 1.5 MPa, respectively).	
	Fixed Injection Platform	A fixed offshore platform for CO ₂ injection is a structure that is permanently installed on the seabed to inject carbon dioxide into geological formations beneath the ocean floor. It can also host injection wells.	Not considered for Mediterranean Scenario
	Floating Storage and Injection Unit (FSUI)	A floating storage and injection unit (FSIU) for offshore CO ₂ injection is a vessel that is used to store and inject carbon dioxide into geological formations beneath the ocean floor. Unlike fixed offshore platforms, FSUIs are floating facilities moored on the seabed, but they are designed to be flexible and adaptable, allowing them to be moved to different locations as needed.	Considered in the alternative case of the Mediterranean Scenario
	CO₂ Subsea Injection System	Subsea injection systems are installed on the seabed, making them another alternative for offshore CO ₂ injection. The subsea injection system typically consists of a series of injection wells drilled into the geological formation, connected to a pipeline system that transports the CO ₂ from landfall to the injection wells. The CO ₂ is then injected into the formation at high pressure, where it is stored permanently.	Considered for both cases in Mediterranean Scenario

2.4.1 High-pressure compression (dense phase)

To design and size the main facilities required for conditioning the CO₂ for dense-phase pipeline transportation, a maximum operating pressure of 12 MPa was considered. Depending on the topology of the CO₂ network, several pressurization options may be required for conditioning and are therefore considered for further technical development:

1. Compression from 2 MPa to the required dense-phase pipeline pressure. This scenario corresponds to purified CO₂ arrival via a gaseous phase pipeline to a central compression station.
2. Compression from 3 MPa to the required dense-phase pipeline pressure. This corresponds to compression at an emitter site (decentralized compression) just after the initial compression & drying.
3. Pumping and heating of the liquefied CO₂ up to the required dense-phase pipeline pressure. This scenario is relevant when the CO₂ is shipped to a central CO₂ hub and then transferred by pipeline to a storage site.

A simplified process flow diagram (PFD) for a two-stage compression process with intercooling and heat integration with district heating is shown in Figure 2-7. The CO₂ enters the first compression stage at either 2 or 3 MPa, depending on the case. In the first compression stage, the CO₂ is compressed up to an intermediate pressure. The intermediate pressure is defined such that the pressure ratio ($P_{\text{outlet}}/P_{\text{inlet}}$) for each compression stage is equivalent. At the inlet of each compression stage, the CO₂ passes first through a compressor scrubber (V.01/2) to ensure that any liquid or solid particles are knocked out before entering the compressor. After each compression stage (C01-stage 1/stage 2), the CO₂ is cooled down via a closed loop cooling medium (CM) in the intercoolers (E.01/E.02). At the outlet of these two heat exchangers, the “hot” cooling medium transfers its heat to district heating (DH) water in the CM-DH heat exchangers (E.03/4). Air coolers (E.05/6) shall also be integrated to reject any excess heat from the CM in case the demand for district heating is low or non-existent.

Figure 2-7 Simplified PFD for two-stage CO₂ compression and waste heat recovery

2.4.2 Liquefaction

To design and size the main facilities required for conditioning the CO₂ for shipping, barge or truck transportation, low and medium-pressure liquefaction at 0.7 and 1.5 MPa, respectively, was considered. Under these pressure conditions, the CO₂ needs to be cooled down to temperatures close to -47°C (at 0.7 MPa) and -30°C (at 1.5 MPa). Considering the additional safety requirements when handling large amounts of refrigerants, the Linde-Hampson process is considered here for liquefying the CO₂ at the required pressure conditions. The CO₂ is assumed to be arriving at the liquefaction facility either at 2 or 10 MPa, corresponding to gaseous and liquid phase transportation, respectively. A simplified process flow diagram for CO₂ arrival at 2 MPa and liquefaction at 1.5 MPa (with no district heating integration) is shown in Figure 2-8. The CO₂ arriving from a gaseous phase pipeline enters a compression train (C.01–stage 2), where the CO₂ is compressed up to an intermediate pressure of 4 MPa. At the outlet of this compression stage, the CO₂ is cooled in the intercooler (E.01) up to 35°C before entering the next compression stage (C.01–stage 3) up to 9 MPa. A compressor scrubber for knocking out any solids or liquid particles is considered at the inlet of each compression stage.

After the second compression stage, the CO₂ is again cooled down to 35°C in the aftercooler (E.02). The stream leaving the aftercooler is then expanded up to the intermediate

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compression pressure of 4 MPa, generating a liquid-vapor mixture. The liquid and vapour fractions are then separated in a gas-liquid separator (V.03). The top stream (vapour) from the separator is recycled towards the inlet to the second compression stage (C.01–stage 2), whereas the bottom stream (liquid) is expanded again up to the final required liquefaction pressure of 1.5 MPa, causing a flash. The vapour and liquid fractions are again separated in a gas-liquid separator (V.04). The vapour stream is compressed up to 2 MPa in the first compression stage (C.01–stage 1) and recirculated to the inlet where it enters the compression train with the “freshly” arrived CO₂. The liquid stream leaving the V.04 separator is the final liquefied stream being sent to the intermediate storage. Note that analogous to the compression block, the liquefaction can also be integrated with district heating.

Figure 2-8 Simplified PFD for liquefaction – CO₂ arrival at 2 MPa and liquefaction at 1.5 MPa

A summary of the liquefaction cases considered is provided in Figure 2-9.

Figure 2-9 Liquefaction scenarios considered in the CO₂ network

2.5 Geological Storage and injection infrastructure

2.5.1 Criteria for project duration and sustainability

The project duration D is calculated by formula:

$$D = MCO_2 / CO_{2total_inj}$$

Where:

MCO₂ – average storage capacity of the structure, Mt

CO_{2total_inj}– CO₂ emission flow total to be injected during the project duration, Mt.

The project could be considered sustainable if it can cover the full lifetime of the emission sources (usually 20–30 years) and if the storage capacity is enough for emissions produced during this project duration. The shorter project duration will cause increase of the costs per one ton of CO₂ avoided (Shogenova & Shogenov, 2020).

2.5.2 Injection infrastructure

Injection infrastructure includes wells, storage site facilities and monitoring equipment. Reusing of old wells (if any are available), new wells drilling, geophysical well logging and well-head pressure and temperature monitoring, CO₂ injection and monitoring of the storage site should be considered. Storage site monitoring includes baseline monitoring, operational monitoring and post-closure monitoring. The number of injection wells depends on the CO₂ flow-rate, and storage reservoir properties such as thickness, total injection depth, permeability and injectivity (EPRI, 2015).

If new wells will be drilled, then wells logging and coring should be added. In case of using old abandoned wells, the costs of their reopening should be applied instead of the drilling costs (Shogenova & Shogenov, 2020).

Requirements for injection and storage facilities is described in international standard ISO/TR 27923:2022 Carbon dioxide capture, transportation and geological storage — Injection operations, infrastructure and monitoring.

2.5.3 Storage facilities

Onshore storage facilities need a simple distribution network to take the CO₂ from the pipeline out to one or more injection wells. The main technical parameters are number of wells and CO₂ flow rate.

Offshore storage facilities could include the offshore platform with a simple distribution network. The cost of the platform depends on the number of wells and is usually limited by five well slots per platform, however, the higher number of wells per platform (up to 20) is also reported (EPRI, 2015).

At present, the captured CO₂ is injected offshore from the repurposed oil and gas platforms. Such case was recently demonstrated by Project Greensand in Denmark where the Nini platform operated by INEOS was repurposed for CO₂ injection in the Danish North Sea (Offshore, 2023).

The modern concepts under development for offshore CO₂ injection include 1) Direct CO₂ Injection from the ship and 2) Intermediate storage injection facilities (ISIF) including CO₂ hose to transfer CO₂ to the storage unit with two options - either floating or at the seabed; 3) offshore

injection unit which is a floating or fixed structure with CO₂ conditioning and injection systems, The unit could have buffer storage, or could be connected to additional ships with the aim of continuous CO₂ injection (DNV, 2024).

2.5.4 Monitoring and verification

Monitoring plan should be designed by the operator according to the article 13 of EU CCS Directive and Annex I and II of the Directive. The plan should be designed considering the best available practice and have to be updated every 5 years. The operator reports the results of the monitoring to Competent Authority every year. The state of the art and requirements for monitoring methods is given in (Rütters et al., 2013, Niemi et al., 2017). Considering the requirement of EU CCS Directive (EC, 2009), the monitoring plan must include measurements of CO₂ fugitive emissions at the injection facility; CO₂ volumetric flow, temperature and pressure at injection wellheads; chemical analysis of injected material; and reservoir temperature and pressure. The technologies for monitoring shall be chosen based on best practice. Typically, seismic exploration (baseline, operational and post-closure) can permit to monitor CO₂ plume behaviour.

Table 2-3 EU and National Requirements for CO₂ Storage Site Monitoring

	During Storage			Post-closure period			Operator obligations
	Operator	Competent authority	Routine inspections	Routine inspections by competent authority		Operator obligations	
	Reporting to competent authority	Monitoring plan updating	Routine inspections	3 years after closure	Until transfer of responsibility (minimum 20 years)	After transfer of responsibility	
						Routine inspections	Financial contribution to monitoring costs
EU CCS Directive	At least once a year	Every 5 years	At least once a year	At least once a year	Every 5 years	May be reduced or intensified in case of problem	30 years
Denmark, CCS regulations	At least once a year	Every 5 years	At least once a year	At least once a year	Every 5 years	May be reduced or intensified in case of problem	30 years
Spain, CCS regulations	At least once a year	Every 5 years	At least once a year	At least once a year	Every 5 years	May be reduced or intensified in case of problem	30 years

The coring and logging costs should be included in the budget of the well drilling and logging operating costs should be added to the overall monitoring cost of the project. Equipment of the injection well(s) shall enable monitoring of pressure and temperature at wellhead and in the reservoir.

The number of monitoring wells should be estimated, depending on storage area, number of injection wells and methodological needs. Additional logging equipment located in the well outside or inside casing should be designed. Equipment for integrated monitoring well can include U-tube fluid sampling, pressure-temperature gauges and integrated fibre-optic bundles

for temperature, seismic and heat-pulse monitoring, etc. (Niemi et al., 2017). The costs of such equipment for integrated monitoring of well-designed specifically for CO₂ monitoring projects should be asked from the international geophysical companies like Schlumberger Carbon or others.

The monitoring of the onshore CO₂ storage sites could require soil gas monitoring to detect possible CO₂ leakage pathways using shallow wells (if available) often used for hydrogeological monitoring.

Monitoring of the offshore storage site should include monitoring of the possible leakage from the old, abandoned wells. For this purpose, gas-detecting sensors should be planned at the seabed close to the location of the old wells.

2.6 Utilization

Figure 2-10 CO₂ use options through conversion or direct use (IEA, 2019).

Carbon Capture and Utilisation represents an array of diverse technologies that can capture carbon from industrial installations or directly from the air and use it as feedstock to produce marketable products like fuels, chemicals and materials. Depending on the pathway selected, the origin of the captured carbon and the inputs in the process, the impact of CCU on GHG emissions can vary from emissions reductions compared to conventional fossil-derived products, net zero emissions or CO₂ removals. CO₂ options are summarized in Figure 2-10 below and further discussed in section 3.6 and 4.11, which include examples of CO₂ utilization among conversion into chemicals, building materials or fuels. Objective is to highlight the potential benefits of CO₂ utilization in the CCUS value chains.

3 Baltic Region: Baltic-2 CCUS Project

3.1 Introduction

Figure 3-1 Schematic representation of the Baltic-2 CCUS network potential scenarios (Germany, Denmark and Sweden). Emitters are represented in circles and connected to storage sites through shipping lines (orange lines) and pipelines (remaining multiple colour lines)

The Baltic-2 project, sketched in Figure 3-1, presents a tri-nation venture involving Germany, Denmark, and Sweden to establish a CCUS network encompassing emitters, transportation infrastructure, and options for carbon storage and utilisation. Although the CCUS ZEN project's Baltic Sea region includes eight countries (Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Germany, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland) and the Baltic Sea itself, Baltic-2 narrows its focus to the three selected countries.

Originally, as reported in Deliverable 1.2 (Gravaud et al., 2024), the Baltic-2 project comprised eight clusters with 37 emitters across the three nations, contributing to an annual CO₂ emission of roughly 42.6 Mt. However, this report sees the project evolve with refined or added sources derived from nuanced technical and commercial analysis. The result is nine clusters of 20 to 33 emitters with an annual maximum CO₂ emission of 22.7 Mt and respective capture nearing 20.1 Mt. Two CO₂ utilisation options (near emitters or near intermediate hubs) within this region are explored, potentially converting the CO₂ into methanol or synthetic jet fuel. While utilisation options were identified within the cluster regions, the most promising storage locations were found in Danish territories, including eight onshore, nearshore and offshore sites.

This report encompasses the technical and non-technical framework of the Baltic-2 CCUS project. On a technical level, it delineates the criteria for emitter selection (3.3), storage (3.4) and utilisation potential (3.6), transportation infrastructure (3.5), a risk and safety assessment (3.7) and monitoring infrastructure (3.8). The non-technical aspect assesses the individual national strategies of Germany, Denmark, and Sweden (3.9). Further, it probes the status and applicability of international regulations concerning potential CCUS pursuits within these nations. Complementing these analyses, a methodology section provides the strategic backbone guiding the execution of the study and providing important definitions and assumptions.

3.2 Specific methodology for Baltic-2

3.2.1 Heat and material balance

Process simulations have been carried out in DWSIM 8.6, an open-source CAPE-OPEN-compliant chemical process simulation software to carry out the heat and material balance for both the compression and liquefaction facilities. Considering the different emitters and uncertainties in terms of the impurities contained in the different CO₂ streams, pure CO₂ has been considered in all simulations. The CO₂ behaviour is described using the Peng-Robinson EoS. For the cooling medium (e.g., aqueous glycol mixture, seawater, etc.) the NRTL activity coefficient property package is chosen.

The dimensioning of the pipelines has also been carried out in DWSIM, with pressure loss being the main sizing criteria.

3.2.2 Equipment sizing

Equipment sizes for the transportation blocks described in Table 2-2 are calculated with a Ramboll “in-house” developed tool. For each equipment type, the size is estimated mainly by:

- Regression of equipment dimensions and weight from vendor information, from access to information on equipment installed on offshore installations (North Sea) as well as onshore equipment, from vendor quotes or similar.
- Legacy sizing relations for flow, pressure, etc.
- Fundamental physical principles.

The driver power, heat duty, logarithmic mean temperature difference (LMTD), pressure difference, overall heat transfer coefficient (U-value), operating & design pressure are some of the parameters used for the equipment sizing. Most of these parameters were taken from the heat and material balance calculated with DWSIM. U-values of 500 W/m² K have been assumed for shell and tube heat exchangers (high-pressure gas/liquid service) and air coolers, whereas values of 2000 W/m² K have been considered for plate heat exchangers in water service (low-pressure service).

3.3 CO₂ emission sources

The Baltic-2 value chain aims to build a cross-border network for large CO₂ volume storage. The goal of such selection is to create a CCUS system able to capture and store significant quantities of CO₂ to effectively limit the CO₂ emissions into the atmosphere. This requires the involvement of multiple entities, with emitters playing an essential role.

In its preliminary form, as detailed in Deliverable 1.2 (Gravaud et al., 2024), the Baltic-2 project consisted of eight different clusters, including 37 emitters from the three participating

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countries, which collectively emit approximately 42.6 Mt of CO₂ annually. The current report, however, charts the project's progression, with sources undergoing refinement or expansion thanks to additional technical and commercial examinations. Furthermore, the current assessment tackles the possibility of alternative scenarios based on a higher or lower probability of adherence of emitters to CCUS solutions. The analysis was performed individually for each of the countries considered and is described in sections 3.3.1, 3.3.2 and 3.3.3, and summarised below.

Nine emission clusters (Table 3-1, Figure 3-2) were identified with up to 33 individual emission sources in total, resulting in 22.7 Mt annual maximum emissions and captured amount nearing 20.1 Mt. The results are showed in ranges in Table 3-1 to represent the assumption that some of the emitters are in the “front line” for adopting a CCUS solution (Phase 1) while others will take the “follower” role (Phase 2).

Table 3-1 Emissions from selected clusters in the Baltic-2 project. This table considers that some of the emitters in the Power sector may retrofit to biofuels (as communicated by the respective plants)

Country	Cluster	CO ₂ emissions [Mt/yr]	CO ₂ captured [Mt/yr]	Captured biogenic CO ₂ [Mt/yr]	Number of emitters
Germany	Bremen Cluster	2.78–3.43	2.64–3.26	2.64	2–3
	Hannover Cluster	3.12–3.99	2.96–3.79	1.73–1.81	4–5
	Hamburg Cluster	1.05–3.80	1.00–3.61	0.00–1.14	1–4
Sweden	Gothenburg Cluster	3.12–4.12	2.96–3.92	0.34–0.65	5–9
Denmark	Aalborg Cluster	2.48–2.48	2.36–2.36	0.13	2–2
	Aarhus Cluster	0.82–2.72	0.78–1.16	0.25–0.55	2–3
	West Midtjylland Cluster	0.00–0.62	0.00–0.59	0.00–0.34	0–2
	Fredericia Cluster	0.85–1.28	0.81–1.21	0.67	3–4
	Esbjerg Emitter	0.22	0.21	0.12	1
Total		14.44–22.66	13.71–20.10	5.90–8.05	20–33

The approach for the selection of the emitters starts with the initial screening performed in Deliverables 1.1 (Ringstad et al., 2023) and 1.2 (Gravaud et al., 2024). To analyse CO₂ emitters, we chose to focus on the selected geographical range due to practical constraints regarding the scope of the project resources. While it is realistic to consider a broader geographic scope for the Danish storage capacity, the present report will focus on the geography limited to Germany (Bremen, Hannover and Hamburg areas), Denmark (Jutland area) and Sweden (Gothenburg area).

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The analysis of emitters was also limited to the largest ones, with a cut-off of 100 kt of emitted CO₂ yearly. From the selected emitters identified in Deliverable 1.2, and few recovered emitters which were reassessed, adding value to the Baltic-2 project, all emitters were evaluated in terms of CO₂ volume captured and a qualitative parameter named as “feasibility of capture”. The latter is defined by multiple sub-parameters which are presented in sections 3.3.1, 3.3.2 and 3.3.3, mainly dependent on existing decarbonisation plans for each emitter. This was adapted into a “value-effort” matrix, represented in to Figure 3-3 support the decision process of the selection of emitters for further assessment within the Baltic-2 project. The emitters were placed in the graph after appropriate assessments and two diagonal lines filter the emitters with most potential for capture, creating two scenarios. This provides the range of applicable emitters for the study.

It is important to note that the analysis can be complemented with additional information, which could be useful for assessing the relevance of CCUS in such a large network for each emitter, e.g., comparison of multiple decarbonisation strategies per emitter, commercial plans and ambitions, etc. The division of emitters in two scenarios (Phases 1 and 2) may be also used to present a chronological adherence of emitters to CCUS solutions.

Figure 3-2 Emissions clusters identified as part of the Baltic-2 project

Figure 3-3 presents the distribution of captured emissions within the Baltic-2 project per current industry sector. The expected emissions come predominantly from the Power and Cement sectors, with an important contribution as well from the Energy from Waste and Refineries sectors.

The selected emitters' CO₂ from the Power sector originate predominantly from fossil fuel sources. Many of which have communicated plans to decarbonise using alternative fuels such as biomass or natural gas or using CCUS solutions. The impact of retrofitting plants to alternative fuels on the volume of annually emitted CO₂ is considered minimal. While Figure 3-4 presents the emissions per sector in the present time, Table 3-1 provides already the CO₂ type (biogenic) after the retrofit of power plants to biofuels.

Although the Baltic-2 project considers more point sources from Denmark, their dimension is generally smaller compared to the Swedish and German emitters considered. Therefore, as presented in Figure 3-5, German emitters represent nearly half of the captured CO₂ of the value chain, while emitters from the Gothenburg cluster and Denmark take approximately 30% and 20%, respectively.

Figure 3-3 Methodology for assessment of potential for capture for each emitter (blue circles) and selection of Phase 1 (emitters to the right of the orange line) and Phase 2 (emitters to the right of the green line)

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Figure 3-4 Captured CO₂ emissions per present industrial sources in Mt/y for the Baltic-2 project, with a total of 20.1 Mt/y

Figure 3-5 Captured emissions per country for the Phase 1 (inner circle) and Phase 2 (outer circle)

3.3.1 Germany emitters

Figure 3-6 Analysed German emitters

In the present analysis, the emitters reported in Deliverable 1.2 (Gravaud et al., 2024) were reassessed based on plant and fuel type and public information released regarding the emitters' plans for decarbonisation, retrofitting, and respective timelines.

The selected emitters in Germany, within the Bremen, Hannover, and Hamburg clusters are presented in Table 3-2. The captured CO₂ was defined as 95% of the emitted volumes for both total and biogenic sources. Table 3-2 presents the emitters analysed. Figure 3-6 shows their partitioning in Phase 1 and 2. This assessment was based on the captured CO₂ volumes or publicly informed CCUS and plant retrofitting plans. While Phase 1 emitters may have communicated potential interest in CCUS solutions, Phase 2 emitters have mostly communicated an interest in decarbonisation solutions. Other emitters that have not been analysed could also be influenced by emitters which invest in CCUS and are geographically close. In this case, they would join an already-built infrastructure to access its benefits.

Table 3-2 Selected emitters in Germany*.

* Emissions assumed to be converted to biogenic after retrofit to biofuels

Emitter ID	Facility name	Cluster	Industry sector	Total captured CO ₂ [Mt/y]	Captured biogenic CO ₂ [Mt/y]	Phase
S_DE_38	Onyx Kraftwerk Wilhelmshaven Gmbh & Co. Kg	Bremen	Power	1.82	1.82*	1
S_DE_83	Onyx Kraftwerk Farge Gmbh & Co. Kgaa	Bremen	Power	0.82	0.82*	1

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Emitter ID	Facility name	Cluster	Industry sector	Total captured CO ₂ [Mt/y]	Captured biogenic CO ₂ [Mt/y]	Phase
S_DE_115	Swb Erzeugung Ag & Co. Kg / Heizkraftwerk Hastedt	Bremen	Power	0.61	-	2
S_DE_27	Arcelormittal Bremen Gmbh / Kraftwerk Mittelsbüren / Block 4	Bremen	Power	N/A	N/A	N/A
S_DE_29	Arcelormittal Bremen Gmbh	Bremen	Iron & Steel	N/A	N/A	N/A
S_DE_102	Empg - Eaa Großenkneten Erdgas-Aufbereitungsanlage	Bremen	Chemicals (other)	N/A	N/A	N/A
S_DE_131	Arcelormittal Bremen Gmbh / Brema Walzwerk Gmbh	Bremen	Iron & Steel	N/A	N/A	N/A
S_DE_53	Gkh - Gemeinschaftskraftwerk Hannover Gmbh	Hannover	Power	1.29	1.29*	1
S_DE_82	Kraftwerk Mehrum Gmbh	Hannover	Power	0.83	-	2
S_DE_116	Heidelbergcement Ag Zementwerke Hannover	Hannover	Cement	0.61	0.05	1
S_DE_124	Holcim (Deutschland) Gmbh Werk Höver	Hannover	Cement	0.55	0.05	1
S_DE_130	Enertec Hameln Gmbh	Hannover	Waste-to-energy (WTE)	0.52	0.35	1
S_DE_30	Volkswagen Ag Werk Wolfsburg	Hannover	Power	N/A	N/A	N/A
S_DE_62	Wärme Hamburg Gmbh Heizkraftwerk Tiefstack	Hamburg	Power	1.06	1.06*	2
S_DE_70	Zementwerk Lägerdorf	Hamburg	Cement	1.00	-	1
S_DE_72	HKW (CHP) Wede	Hamburg	Power	1.00	0.00	2
S_DE_123	Dow Deutschland Anlagenges. Mbh Werk Stade	Hamburg	Hydrogen	0.56	0.07	2
S_DE_77	Raffinerie Heide Gmbh	Hamburg	Refineries	N/A	N/A	N/A
S_DE_98	Holborn Europa Raffinerie Gmbh	Hamburg	Refineries	N/A	N/A	N/A
S_DE_107	Yara Brunsbüttel Gmbh	Hamburg	Ammonia	N/A	N/A	N/A
Total				10.66	5.59	-

3.3.2 Sweden emitters

In addition to the emitters reported in Deliverable 1.2 (Gravaud et al., 2024), other emitters distant from the Gothenburg cluster were also found as potential interested parties for a CCUS solution. Due to the distance from the common infrastructure of the Baltic-2 project, they were not considered, nonetheless, this shows that the Baltic-2 has the opportunity for expansion to a wider geography. Emitters were assessed based on plant and fuel type and public information released regarding the emitters' plans for decarbonisation, retrofitting and respective timelines. The respective annual sustainability reports of the companies owning the emission facilities may provide a good description of the decarbonisation solutions being analysed.

The selected emitters in Sweden, within the Gothenburg cluster are presented in Table 3-3. The captured CO₂ was defined as 95% of the emitted volumes for both total and biogenic sources. Table 3-3 also defines the emitters which are expected to be on the first and second line (Phases 1 and 2) for CCUS decarbonisation. Using a similar assessment method to the German case, in Figure 3-7, these emitters are qualified as players starting from either Phase 1 or Phase 2.

Table 3-3 Selected emitters in Sweden*.

* Emissions assumed to be converted to biogenic after retrofit to biofuels

Emitter ID	Facility name	Cluster	Industry sector	Total captured CO ₂ [Mt/y]	Captured biogenic CO ₂ [Mt/y]	Phase
S_SE_9	Preemraff, Lysekil	Gothenburg	Refineries	1.31	-	1
S_SE_29	Borealis Krackeranl.	Gothenburg	Chemicals (other)	0.60	-	2
S_SE_31	Sävenäs	Gothenburg	WTE	0.54	0.34	1
S_SE_33	Preem Ab Preemraff Göteborg	Gothenburg	Refineries	0.50	-	1
S_SE_34	St1 Refinery Ab	Gothenburg	Refineries	0.48	-	1
S_SE_79	Perstorp Oxo Ab, Stenungsund	Gothenburg	Chemicals (other)	0.12	-	1
S_SE_73	Rya Gaskraftvärmeverk	Gothenburg	Power	0.13	0.13*	2
S_SE_82	Ryaverket	Gothenburg	Power	0.12	0.07	2
S_SE_89	Sävenäs Kraftvärmeverk	Gothenburg	Power	0.10	0.10	2
S_SE_54	Hylte Paper	Gothenburg	Paper and pulp	N/A	N/A	N/A
S_SE_59	Lidköpings Värmeverk, Filen	Gothenburg	WTE	N/A	N/A	N/A
S_SE_62	Munksjö Paper AB Billingsfors	Gothenburg	Paper and pulp	N/A	N/A	N/A

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Emitter ID	Facility name	Cluster	Industry sector	Total captured CO ₂ [Mt/y]	Captured biogenic CO ₂ [Mt/y]	Phase
S_SE_68	Vargön Alloys AB	Gothenburg	Non-iron metals	N/A	N/A	N/A
S_SE_74	Riskullaverket	Gothenburg	Power	N/A	N/A	N/A
S_SE_75	Lillesjö Avfallskraftvärmeverk	Gothenburg	WTE	N/A	N/A	N/A
Total				3.92	0.65	-

Figure 3-7 Analysed Swedish emitters

3.3.3 Denmark emitters

Compared to Deliverable 1.2 (Gravaud et al., 2024), additional emitters, not present in the initial listing, were also found as potential interested parties for a CCUS solution; some of these emitters were selected for further analysis. Emitters were assessed based on plant and fuel type and public information released regarding the emitters' plans for decarbonisation, retrofitting and respective timelines. Additionally, data provided by the Danish Energy Agency (DEA, 2024) was also used to review the emissions data. Since only the disclosure of fossil CO₂ emissions is mandatory and most of the emitters produce biogenic CO₂, this reference provides a meticulous description of the fuel consumption (used for the energy sector). The Danish Energy Agency presents, as well, standard emission factors for individual fuels to estimate annual CO₂ emissions (DEA, 2024).

The selected emitters in Denmark, within the Aalborg, Aarhus, West Midtjylland, Fredericia and Esbjerg clusters are presented in Table 3-4. The captured CO₂ was defined as 95% of the emitted volumes for both total and biogenic sources, except for emitter S_DK_4 (20% was considered), currently using wood pellet-fired units which may be out-phased in 2030, leaving the potential for a minor carbon capture plant. Table 3-4 also defines the emitters which are

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expected to be on the first and second line (Phases 1 and 2) for CCUS decarbonisation as presented in Figure 3-8, using a similar assessment method to the German case.

Table 3-4 Selected emitters in Denmark

Emitter ID	Facility name	Cluster	Industry sector	Total captured CO ₂ [Mt/y]	Captured biogenic CO ₂ [Mt/y]	Phase
S_DK_1	Aalborg Portland A/S	Aalborg	Cement	2.14	-	1
S_DK_13	I/S Reno-Nord, Energianlægget Aalborg	Aalborg	WTE	0.22	0.13	1
S_DK_2	Nordjyllandsværket	Aalborg	Power	N/A	N/A	N/A
S_DK_58	Kredsløb	Aarhus	Biomass CHP / EFW	0.52	0.25	1
S_DK_4	Studstrupværket	Aarhus	Power	0.38	0.30	2
S_DK_57	Verdo Krafvarmeværk	Aarhus	Power	0.26	-	1
S_DK_23	LECA - Randers	Aarhus	Other	N/A	N/A	N/A
S_DK_56	Herningværket	West Midtjylland	Biomass CHP	0.34	0.34	2
S_DK_18	Maabjerg Energy Center – BioHeat & Power A/S	West Midtjylland	WTE	0.25	-	2
S_DK_54	Skærbækværket	Fredericia	Biomass CHP	0.54	0.54	1
S_DK_9	Crossbridge refinery	Fredericia	Refineries	0.41	-	2
S_DK_15	Energist Kolding	Fredericia	WTE	0.17	0.08	1
S_DK_25	Fjernvarme Horsens A/S Affaldsværket	Fredericia	WTE	0.10	0.05	1
S_DK_14	Energist Esbjerg	Esbjerg	WTE	0.21	0.12	1
S_DK_3	Esbjergværket	Esbjerg	Power	N/A	N/A	N/A
Total				5.53	1.82	-

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Figure 3-8 Analysed Danish emitters

3.4 CO₂ storage sites

Table 3-5 Selected Baltic-2 storage sites and some of the basic information to be used in the cluster analysis

CLUSTER ID	COUN-TRY	SITE ID	SITE NAME	STORAGE TYPE	COORDINATE Longitude	COORDINATE Latitude
Baltic-2	DK	S_DK1	Gassum	Deep Saline Aquifer (DSA)	56°33'50.421"N	9°58'6.243"E
Baltic-2	DK	S_DK10	Voldum	DSA	56°22'26.183"N	10°15'28.638"E
Baltic-2	DK	--	Jammerbugt	DSA	57°26'49.002"N	8°57'39.929"E
Baltic-2	DK	--	Inez	DSA	57°03'32.875"N	6°43'55.378"E
Baltic-2	DK	--	Bifrost	DOGF	56°20'38.915"N	4°16'18.911"E
Baltic-2	DK	--	Greensand	DOGF	56°38' 26.90"N	5°16' 19.04"E
Baltic-2	DK	--	Lisa	DSA	57°33'52.978"N	8°05'28.019"E
Baltic-2	DK	S_DK7	Thorning	DSA	56°16'43.262"N	9°16'16.107"E

The list of the selected Baltic-2 cluster storage sites is a mix of onshore, nearshore and offshore projects, but all of them are in clastic sandstone reservoirs (Table 3-5). Only three of the sites were included in the original database (Gassum, Voldum, Thorning) and the additional 5 have been added because they are relevant for the cluster analysis. The available

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information for these added sites is limited and the estimated properties have been derived from unpublished sources and by comparing to analogue sites. The two commercial projects (Bifrost and Greensand) have very limited published information but include predicted injection rates when in operation, although the conservative numbers have been preferred for the cluster analysis.

The information in the tables is extracted from the work in WP-1 with supplementary information and modifications as explained, and all this is summarised for use in the cluster analysis. The most important modification in comparison with the previous deliverable D1.1 is related to the calculation of static capacity since the storage efficiency factor has been reduced and therefore leads to reduced capacities for the structures to be included in the cluster analysis.

Table 3-6 Selected Baltic-2 storage sites and some of the basic information to be used in the cluster analysis

Baltic-2 SITE NAME	TYPE	LITHOLOGY	PERMEABILITY*, mD	CAPACITY MEAN*, Mt	SRL LEVEL	WELLS existing
Gassum	DSA	Sandstone	461	146	2	1
Voldum	DSA	Sandstone	464	213	2	1
Jammerbugt	DSA	Sandstone	400	100	2	N
Inez	DSA	Sandstone	400	178	2	1
Bifrost	DOGF	Sandstone	200	min. 60	6	5
Greensand	DOGF	Sandstone	600	min. 128	6	10
Lisa	DSA	Sandstone	400	29	2	N
Thorning	DSA	Sandstone	109	74	2	N
			TOTAL	Min. 928	2-6	18
*Several are permeability estimates				*Please observe the modifications in capacities compared to WP1		

The storage capacity of Gassum, Voldum and Thorning storage sites has been analysed and reported (Hjelm et al., 2020), whereas the capacity for Jammerbugt, Inez and Lisa has been estimated from preliminary work not yet published. Additionally, for all sites the storage efficiency factor has been modified to 10%, deviating from the previously 40% applied.

Generally, the estimation of static capacity for storage sites has uncertainty caused by several factors including the database for mapping spill points and the storage efficiency factor applied to the specific type of reservoir. Recent work has shown that static capacity estimations might

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use an efficiency factor of 10% instead of the previously applied 40% (Gregersen et al., 2023). This is of course a significant reduction, but further clarification will need more work on site-specific dynamic estimates based on filling scenarios and flow simulation. In addition, some site-specific conditions linked to the pressure buildup might further restrict the capacity.

Details about the Gassum, Voldum and Thorning sites can be found in Hjelm et al. (2020) where capacity analysis is performed based on structural maps derived from existing seismic interpretations. All three are 4-way anticlines above salt pillows. New seismic 2D data has been acquired during 2023 and will be used for new structural interpretation and more detailed outline of structure and possible faults. The seismic data for Gassum, Jammerbugt, and Thorning structures will be available for download at GEUS website (GEUS, 2024).

The storage capacity for the two commercial projects Bifrost and Greensand can be estimated as a minimum capacity assuming a 20-year operation period and the predicted injection rates published from these projects. This capacity estimate is therefore highly dependent on which type of dynamic analysis the commercial projects have included. The evaluation has most probably included a relevant number of wells, reservoir flow analysis, capacity of the planned transport system, and additional business parameters, all of which are not accessible.

Estimation of the injection rate for the remaining storage sites which are all at a screening stage, is very uncertain, as it depends on assumptions about a number of wells, effective permeability, aquifer response and pressure propagation. An indication for ranking can be taken from the reported permeability, where the Thorning site is assumed to have lower permeability than the other comparable sites.

For Bifrost and Greensand, the permeabilities are estimated as conservative numbers based on the limited data, while estimated minimum Storage Capacities are based on the published numbers for annual injection rates and the assumption of a 20-year operation period.

Table 3-7 Selected Baltic-2 storage sites and the evaluations to be used in the cluster analysis

Site name	Onshore/offshore	Permeability, mD	Annual Injectivity per well, Mt/y	Storage site area, km ²	Annual CO ₂ injection volume, Mt/y	Project Duration, years	No of injection wells	No of monit. wells	No of monit. Reporting to Legal Authority
Gassum	onshore	461	0.5	233	3.0	30	7	4	38
Voldum	onshore	464	0.5	560	3.0	30	7	4	38
Jammerbugt	offshore	400	0.5	140	3.0	30	7	0	38
Inez	offshore	400	0.5	250	3.0	30	7	0	38
Bifrost	offshore	200	0.25	16	0.8	20	4	0	28
Greensand	offshore	600	0.5	16	1.5	20	4	0	28
Lisa	offshore	400	0.5	70	0.5	30	2	0	38
Thorning	onshore	109	0.12	210	0.3	30	3	2	38

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Site name	Onshore/offshore	Permeability, mD	Annual Injectivity per well, Mt/y	Storage site area, km ²	Annual CO ₂ injection volume, Mt/y	Project Duration, years	No of injection wells	No of monit. wells	No of monit. Reporting to Legal Authority
Average		379.5				30			28-38(35.5)
Total			3.37	1495	15.1		41	10	

Well-injectivity is assumed to be linked to permeability. A 400 mD formation is assumed to take 0.5 Mtpa pr well as is assumed in publication on Danish CCS (DEA, 2024).

Storage site area for Gassum, Voldum and Thorning sites was calculated during the capacity evaluation, the rest is estimated from the published maps of structural contours. This area measure is defined by the last closing contour, whereas the area relevant for monitoring assessment should reach further, at least also covering any spill point areas.

The total annual CO₂ injection volume is linked to the number of wells and their injectivity. All estimates include one extra surplus well accounting for maintenance periods. For Greensand it is assumed for the first 5 years of operation that 4 wells inject in total 1.5 Mtpa. The future development plans are not included in this analysis which has decided to use conservative numbers for very uncertain scenarios. For Bifrost, it is assumed for the first 5 years of operation that 4 wells inject 0.8 Mtpa. For the remaining sites, the well count is based on evaluating permeability and area.

The data summary in Table 3-7 is also used in the monitoring assessment in a later chapter, but some of the derived results are reported in this table for completeness. Monitoring wells are only advised for onshore sites. Numbers are advised in the publication on Danish CCS (DEA, 2024).

The number of monitoring campaigns by operator can be calculated (based on the regulations table). It is calculated as follows: baseline monitoring (1) + annually during storage (projects duration) + (3) three years annually after storage site closure + (4) every 5 years before transfer responsibility (minimum 20 years). Financial contribution to Competent authority for 30 years after the transfer of responsibility could be calculated as 6 monitoring campaigns (30 years - we propose every 5 years).

Table 3-8 Summary of strong and weak parameters for the sites in the Baltic-2 cluster

SITE NAME	Strong parameters	Number of strong parameters (+)	Weak parameters	Number of weak parameters (-)	Total per Project	References
Gassum	Porosity, permeability, CO ₂ density, good and thick caprocks. One well.	5	No test, no baseline	2	3	Capacity analysed (Hjelm et al., 2020)
Voldum	Porosity, permeability, CO ₂ density, good and	5	No test, no baseline	2	3	Capacity analysed (Hjelm et al., 2020)

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	thick caprocks. One well.					
Jammerbugt	Porosity, permeability, CO ₂ density, good and thick caprocks.	4	No well, no test, no baseline	3	1	Capacity not analysed, estimation
Inez	Porosity, permeability, CO ₂ density, good and thick caprocks. One well.	5	No test, no baseline	2	3	Capacity not analysed, estimation
Bifrost	3 Mt/y					Commercial project, limited information, capacity minimum from rate and 20 years period
Greensand	1.5 to 8 Mt/y (2025 to 2030)					Commercial project, limited information, capacity minimum from rate and 20 years period
Lisa	Porosity, permeability, CO ₂ density, good and thick caprocks.	4	No well, no test, no baseline	3	1	Capacity not analysed, estimation
Thorning	Porosity, permeability, CO ₂ density, good and thick caprocks.	4	No well, no test, no baseline	3	1	Capacity analysed (Hjelm et al., 2020)

Given that we operate with this heterogeneous dataset for storage sites and associated uncertainties, it is important to remember that the cluster analysis has to be performed at a high level and should focus on describing the methodology for a decision scheme and not necessarily worry as much about accuracy and realism.

3.5 CO₂ transport infrastructure

The CO₂ captured in Germany and Sweden is imported to Denmark through pipelines, ships, or both. The imported CO₂ together with the amount captured in Denmark is sent to both Danish offshore and onshore storage sites as previously shown in [Figure 3-1](#). This section gives an overview of the overall CO₂ network and the governing technical parameters.

3.5.1 Routes

The route selection for underground pipelines requires careful deliberation over numerous factors, such as:

- Handling the intricate interplay between safety and construction complexities associated with dense population centres.
- Navigating around the existing maze of underground infrastructure, including utilities like power lines, telecommunication cables, water, and sewage lines, among others.

- Minimizing intersections with roads and railways to preserve structural integrity and prevent disruptions.
- Abiding by safety distances and navigating around restricted areas to ensure public safety and regulatory compliance.
- Respecting areas designated for natural protection to uphold environmental preservation efforts.
- Complying with municipal local plans, particularly those outlining predetermined housing and infrastructure development, to ensure alignment with local zoning regulations and expectations.

Routing scenarios prioritisation is typically defined as follows:

- Operational and execution safety takes precedence. This can be accounted, for example, allowing for safety distances to existing infrastructure or populated areas. Safety distances were not considered in the routing exercise presented in this report.
- The alignment with existing infrastructure like roads or metro systems follows next.
- Environmental factors, including the preservation of protected natural areas and cultural heritage sites, are also significant.
- The plan also considers crossings like bridges, railways, and water bodies.

Access to this information is sometimes denied for the public if sensitive regarding business and security concerns. However, the geo-data infrastructure largely differs in each country or regions within a country. Such challenges must be accounted for in routing projects, since underground mapped information can deeply affect the results, particularly in populated areas.

The ultimate objective is to strike a balance between utility, safety, respect for nature areas, and regulatory compliance. Since at this stage, the data available is limited and region-dependent, the routing exercise was divided per country, using respective and appropriate databases presented in the following subsections.

3.5.1.1 *Germany*

For the pipeline routing in Germany, we utilised data from the federal states of Schleswig-Holstein and Niedersachsen. These included details of natural and bird protection zones, primarily sourced from the respective state survey agencies.

While comprehensive parcel data was available for Schleswig-Holstein, providing intricate details on plot boundaries, land ownership, usage, and more, this dataset was not examined due to its greater relevance to more advanced stages of project planning.

We encountered a lack of accessible data concerning underground infrastructures such as high-voltage power lines and existing pipelines within these states. Accessibility to such data has been restricted, a change put in place due to the conflict in Ukraine. Geological information was also not considered.

Figure 3-9: Pipeline routes in the pipeline export scenario for Germany emitted CO₂. Gathering pipelines are shown by blue lines, while export pipelines are shown by yellow-green lines. Emitters are shown by circles

It is also noteworthy that the geo-data infrastructure's standard and availability vary widely among the German states. For example, Schleswig-Holstein boasts a diverse range of data that can be accessed through web services like WFS (Web Feature Service) and WMS (Web Map Service). The latter, however, presents challenges for automated analysis as it delivers data in the form of tiled image maps that do not permit direct geometry access. In contrast, Niedersachsen's approach to geo-data availability is to provide it mainly via WMS services. Moreover, the acquisition process in Niedersachsen often requires navigating through a lengthy procedure to obtain a legitimate user agreement with the state's survey office.

The results of the routing exercise in Germany are provided for three different scenarios to be studied forward in the project:

- 1) Pipeline export scenario: all German clusters send the captured CO₂ through onshore pipelines to Denmark. The routing is performed for the gathering pipelines at gaseous phase and backbone pipeline in supercritical/dense phase to which they connect. Figure 3-9 represents the pipeline routes for this scenario. The CO₂ within each cluster gathering pipelines (blue lines) is injected into the export pipelines (yellow-green lines).
- 2) Shipping export scenario: the pipelines transport CO₂ to the Wilhelmshaven harbour for shipping export (Figure 3-10).
- 3) Combined shipping and pipeline export scenario: the Bremen cluster sends its CO₂ by pipeline to be exported by ship in the Wilhelmshaven harbour or used to produce CO₂ derived products. The remaining German clusters use an onshore pipeline for export of CO₂ to Denmark (Figure 3-11).

Figure 3-10 Pipelines routes supporting shipping export scenario for Germany emitted CO₂. Emitters represented by circles

Figure 3-11 Pipelines routes supporting the combined shipping and pipelines export scenario for Germany emitted CO₂. Emitters are represented by circles

Since all the studied scenarios are valid and competitive regarding a potential business case or can well represent different stages of the evolution of the German CO₂ export infrastructure, all three scenarios are selected further analyses in the following sections.

3.5.1.2 Sweden

The emitters in the Gothenburg cluster are assumed to send their captured CO₂ to the Gothenburg port for export to Denmark either by pipeline or ship. Multiple scenarios for CO₂ transport within the Gothenburg cluster were studied:

- 1) Transportation from all emitters to the Gothenburg port is made by Pipeline.
- 2) Transportation from distant emitters is performed by truck to the Gothenburg port. The emitters located at the Gothenburg port send their respective CO₂ by pipeline.
- 3) Transportation from distant emitters is performed by barges when possible, or trucks to the Gothenburg port. The emitters located at the Gothenburg port also send their respective CO₂ by pipeline.

The first scenario encompasses sections of the latter two and it is described forward. The pipeline routing in Sweden intersects two Swedish counties, Hallands County and Västra Götalands County. The analysis is based on the same data for both counties, which include:

- Animal and plant protected areas, access banned areas, Natura 2000 SPA (Special Protection Area) and SCI (Sites of Community Importance), nature reserves, areas of national interest for nature conservation, culture reserves, and landscape image protected areas from the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency.
- Protected biotopes from the Swedish Forest Agency.
- Areas of national interest for outdoor activities, areas of national interest for fishery, national interest for sea-planned areas and areas of importance on land from the Swedish County Administration.
- Areas of cultural environmental importance from the Swedish National Heritage Board.

To simplify the scope, information related to geodata for geology, infrastructure, breeding areas for fishes and bathymetry was not considered. This must be accounted for on a further iteration of the routes. There is also information that varies from municipalities regarding local plans, which were not considered, and it is not free of cost.

The area for the routing of distant emitters to Gothenburg is a large archipelago consisting mostly of rock outcrops and bays/fjords which in some places reach far into the mainland. This, in combination with a large amount of onshore protected areas, is the reason why we chose to place the suggested routing mainly at sea. In some places, we have had to cross protected areas but have tried to avoid them as much as possible. Eel grass beds are rare, but it is the only geodata avoided completely at sea in this analysis. In city areas, we chose to follow present infrastructure such as pipelines, roads, and railroads visible on orthophotos with remote sensing, but the routing in Gothenburg will most likely be challenging due to the Göta river crossing, dense infrastructure, and several emitters within the city boundaries.

For these reasons, we expect that barge or truck transportation for distant emitters may ensure higher feasibility. Therefore, only scenarios 2 and 3 will be considered forward, while scenario 1 will be dismissed in future works.

3.5.1.3 Denmark

In developing pipeline route suggestions for Denmark, the most current public data has been examined. The primary focus during this analysis included steering clear of the following high-priority considerations:

- Infrastructure:
 - Buildings
 - Some existing pipelines
- BNBO zones (water drillings)
- Natural resource areas
- Plans:
 - Adopted local plans
 - Adopted municipality plans
 - Low-lying areas
- Protected nature:
 - Paragraph 3 nature
 - NATURA 2000
 - Lakes
 - Protected streams
 - Protected forest

Figure 3-12 Pipelines route scenarios to be studied in Denmark. Emitters are represented by circles. Storage sites represented by pink shapes

Given the abundance of data available in Denmark, our approach required streamlining the scope to focus on the most crucial areas to avoid during this phase. Consequently, a substantial volume of data has been excluded.

Examples include:

- Contaminated soils
- Archaeology:
 - Preserved historic sites
 - Preserved historic sites protected zones
 - Memorial lines
 - Cultural heritage areas
- Nature:
 - Forest protection lines
 - Stream protection lines
 - Lake protection lines
 - Nonprotected nature
- Landscape:
 - Valley landscape
 - Transitional landscape
 - Coastal landscape
- Soil conditions

Certain infrastructure data, particularly those below ground level such as oil pipes and high voltage cables, were not incorporated due to their non-public availability or the need for specific surveys. To access these details, ordering through LER (Danish Register of Underground Cable Owners) would be required, which is not feasible for the entire Jutland area.

Jutland poses a considerable challenge due to its extensive coverage of protected nature, making complete avoidance impossible. However, the approach involves minimizing the impact on the top-prioritized data. In instances where avoidance is impractical, crossings are designed to be at the thinnest possible points. Additionally, when dealing with roads and protected streams, crossings are executed at a 90-degree angle to minimize any adverse effects.

Multiple scenarios were constructed, as represented in Figure 3-12, to be studied forward in the following sections.

3.5.2 CO₂ conditioning facilities

3.5.2.1 Compression facilities

Compression facilities in each cluster pressurise the CO₂ before supercritical/dense phase transportation. The power consumption and cooling duty of the centralized compression facilities were calculated for different flow rates using DWSIM. The relationship between the power and cooling duty requirements for different flow rates is given in Figure 3-13, panels (a) and (b), respectively. About 80% of the compression cooling duty can be recovered for district heating purposes when integration with the district heating network is possible.

Figure 3-13 (a) Compression power and (b) cooling duty requirements vs CO₂ flowrates

3.5.2.2 Booster stations

CO₂ boosters may be required within very long (>100 km) onshore supercritical/dense phase pipelines. Shorter pipelines will not require boosting. The power consumption of the booster stations was estimated with DWSIM and increases linearly with the flow rate according to Figure 3-14.

Figure 3-14 Relation between the compression power and the incoming flowrate at the booster stations

The power consumption and cooling duty of the liquefaction facilities were calculated for the relevant flow rates using DWSIM. The relationship between the power and cooling duty requirements with increasing CO₂ flow rates is shown for two different CO₂ arrival pressures at liquefaction pressures of 0.7 MPa and 1.5 MPa in Figure 3-15 and Figure 3-16, respectively. About 80% of the cooling duty can be recovered for district heating purposes when integration with the district heating network is possible.

As an example, considering the two emission scenarios (Phase 1 and Phase 2) and the different transportation cases for Germany, i.e., pipeline, shipping & pipeline, and shipping, the power and cooling duty requirements for the conditioning facilities within the CO₂ German network are summarized in Figure 3-17.

3.5.2.3 Liquefaction facilities

2 MPa arrival pressure

10 MPa arrival pressure

Figure 3-15 Compression power and cooling duty requirements for liquefaction at 0.7 MPa considering CO₂ arrival pressures of 2 and 10 MPa

2 MPa arrival pressure

10 MPa arrival pressure

Figure 3-16 Compression power and cooling duty requirements for liquefaction at 1.5 MPa considering CO₂ arrival pressures of 2 and 10 MPa

Figure 3-17 Compression power and cooling duty requirements for the different transportation cases and scenarios in Germany

3.5.3 Pipelines

The CO₂ backbone across Germany, Sweden, and Denmark is represented in section 3.5.1 for the Phase 1 and 2 emission scenarios. In both phases, gaseous and dense state CO₂ pipelines with maximum operating pressures of 3 and 12 MPa, respectively, have been considered for connecting the CO₂ sources and sinks. Emitters within a cluster transfer the captured CO₂ through gaseous pipelines to a central location where the CO₂ is compressed; hereafter the CO₂ is transferred through dense-phase pipelines. Generally, the Phase 2 scenario leads to more gaseous pipelines than the Phase 1 alternative since it connects more emitters within a cluster. Moreover, since three different possibilities (i.e., pipelines, pipelines & ship, shipping) have been considered for importing the CO₂ from Germany, the pipeline routing for this country is eventually constrained by the different transport options.

Considering all the scenarios studied, the pipelines (low and high pressure) were sized between 6" to 30" and totalling approximately 1720 km.

3.5.4 Ports and CO₂ ships

The ports considered in the Baltic-2 region are listed in Table 3-9, including the main port restrictions.

The capacity of the medium-pressure ships developed specifically for CCS applications is about 10,000 m³ CO₂. Much larger capacities, up to 50,000 m³ are expected to be achieved for low-pressure variants. Yet, the capacity of the ships considered for CO₂ transport will eventually be constrained by the port characteristics.

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Table 3-9 Ports considered in the Baltic-2 Region. Data from (Shipnext, 2024). LOA (Length Overall) and DWT (Deadweight Tonnage) stand for length overall and deadweight tonnage, respectively.

Port	Max draft [m]	Max beam [m]	Max LOA ⁽¹⁾ [m]	Max DWT ⁽¹⁾ [t]
Aalborg	9.4	40	250	102,000
Esbjerg	10.3	71	250	76,640
Hirtshals	9	-	150	-
Fredericia	14	-	300	-
Wilhelmshaven	20	52	430	260,000
Gothenburg	19	-	350	225,000

For a certain amount of CO₂ to be transported annually, the number of ships needed will eventually depend on the ship size, its availability (i.e., operating hours) and its cycle time. The cycle time, i.e., hours required to complete a back-and-forth journey between the port and a storage site, is a function of the ship speed, distance, loading/unloading time onshore/offshore and ship connection to the offshore facilities. Figure 3-18 shows the variation of the cycle time as a function of the distance for two different ship speeds, considering typical loading/unloading and connection times. As an example, the cycle time between three different ports and storage sites is also included.

Figure 3-18 Ship cycle time as a function of distance and ship speed

As the ship capacity increases, the number of ships required for transporting the CO₂ decreases. Yet, an increase in the capacity leads also to higher fuel consumption. The relationship between the ship capacity and the fuel consumption is given in Figure 3-19. Moreover, a greater ship capacity also leads to greater volume required for the intermediate storage.

Figure 3-19 Fuel consumption vs ship capacity

3.5.5 Trucks

In Sweden, for smaller and scattered emitters, the option of CO₂ truck transportation has also been considered. Truck transportation may be appealing during the initial development of the CO₂ network, due to its flexibility. Yet, truck transportation has been shown to only be economically competitive with other transportation methods when a short period is considered and when the volumes to be transported are low.

Figure 3-20 Main parameters considered for CO₂ truck transportation

The conditioning of the CO₂ for truck transportation is analogous to medium-pressure shipping. Thus, before being loaded into the trucks, the CO₂ needs to be liquefied at around 1.5 MPa (≈-30°C saturation temperature). Compared to pipelines, truck transportation requires also additional infrastructure, e.g., intermediate storage and loading bays. This additional infrastructure is required at both the emitter and delivery site. The intermediate storage should

have enough capacity to shelter the captured CO₂ for about 2.5 days in case transportation at weekends is not envisioned or to account for unusual circumstances (e.g., bad weather, strikes, etc.). Truck transportation relies on significant energy consumption, i.e., about 18 MJ/km, contributing further to the overall emissions associated [Figure 3-20](#).

For a certain amount of CO₂ to be transported annually, the number of trucks needed will eventually depend on the truck size, its availability (i.e., operating hours), and its cycle time. The cycle time, i.e., hours required to complete a back-and-forth journey between the emitter and the destination, is a function of the truck speed, distance, and loading/unloading time [Figure 3-21](#) shows the variation of the cycle time as a function of the distance for two different truck speeds, considering typical loading/unloading and connection times. As an example, the cycle time between two different emitters and the Gothenburg harbour is also included.

Figure 3-21 Truck cycle time as a function of distance and average speed

3.5.6 Barges

CO₂ transportation via barges is an alternative to truck transportation within the Gothenburg cluster. This option also maintains the flexibility offered by trucks, while increasing the transported capacity per trip. This may result in reduced costs compared to trucks. Nonetheless, as trucks, barge transportation is economically competitive with other transportation methods only when a short period is considered and when the volumes to be transported are also low.

The conditioning of the CO₂ before barge transportation is the same as for medium-pressure shipping. Therefore, the CO₂ must be liquefied at around 1.5 MPa (≈-30°C saturation temperature). Besides the intermediate storage and loading stations needed for trucks, barge transportation may also require a harbouring infrastructure, e.g., a jetty. Some of the emitters may already have this kind of infrastructure.

The intermediate storage should also have enough capacity to shelter the captured CO₂ for about 2.5 days in case transportation at weekends is not envisioned and an additional contingency for the round-trip time and external events (weather, strikes, etc.).

The propulsion power is assumed to be 2 x 200 hp, with an average fuel consumption of 60 litres per hour.

The main parameters for barge transportation are summarized in [Figure 3-22](#).

Figure 3-22 Main parameters considered for CO₂ barge transportation

For a certain amount of CO₂ to be transported annually, the number of barges needed will eventually depend on the barge size, its availability (i.e., operating hours), and its cycle time. The cycle time, i.e., hours required to complete a back-and-forth journey between the emitter and the destination, is a function of the barge speed, distance, and loading/unloading time. Figure 3-23 shows the variation of the cycle time as a function of the distance for two different barge speeds, considering typical loading/unloading and connection times. As an example, the cycle time between two emitter sites to the Gothenburg harbour is also included.

Figure 3-23 Barge cycle time as a function of distance and average speed

The capacity of the intermediate storage should be at least equivalent to the capacity of the ship transporting the CO₂. In practice, the capacity of the intermediate storage must be enough to accommodate the incoming CO₂ from the liquefaction facility for several days in case of bad weather events when ship transportation may not be feasible. To achieve the required intermediate storage capacity at harbours, cylindrical tanks with a nominal capacity of 2500 m³ and hemispherical heads are considered. Smaller tanks, i.e., 1000 m³ nominal capacity, are considered for the intermediate storage required for truck transportation at an emitter site.

3.5.7 Intermediate storage

Figure 3-24 Dimensions of the storage tanks considered for the intermediate storage for ship and truck & barge transportation

The effective capacity of the tanks is assumed to be 90% of that of the nominal value. The design conditions of the tanks should be compatible with the pressure the liquefaction is carried out at. Due to the lower operating temperatures, for the low-pressure liquefaction pressure, stainless steel is considered. Low-temperature carbon steel shall be used for medium-pressure storage tanks. An overview of the tank dimensions and operating conditions is provided in Figure 3-24.

3.5.8 Selected infrastructure for WP4

The selection of infrastructure for WP4 was defined based on the distribution of the captured CO₂ (considering Phase 2) to the geological storage sites or utilisation infrastructures. Table 3-10,

Table 3-11 and Table 3-12 present the captured CO₂, stored and utilised per year according to the previous sections.

Table 3-10 Emissions captured in Phase 2.

Cluster	Phase 2 – CO ₂ captured [Mt/y]
Bremen Cluster	3.26
Hannover Cluster	3.79
Hamburg Cluster	3.61
Gothenburg Cluster	3.92
Aalborg Cluster	2.36
Aarhus Cluster	1.16

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Cluster	Phase 2 – CO ₂ captured [Mt/y]
West Midtjylland Cluster	0.59
Fredericia Cluster	1.21
Esbjerg Emitter	0.21
Total	20.1

Table 3-11 Storage maximum injectivity.

Geological storage	CO ₂ stored [Mt/y]
Gassum	3.0
Voldum	3.0
Jammerbugt	3.0
Inez	3.0
Bifrost	0.8
Greensand	1.5
Lisa	0.5
Thorning	0.3
Total	15.1

Based on the information presented, the transport infrastructure scenario selected for further development in WP4 is presented in Figure 3-25. It considers that all CO₂ captured in the Bremen cluster is utilised in a CCU sub-value chain. Emissions captured in the Gothenburg cluster which are not utilised in a local CCU infrastructure, are sent to offshore geological storage sites in Denmark (Inez and Lisa). From Esbjerg, a ship with CO₂ from Germany, Fredericia and Esbjerg is sent to Greensand and Inez. All CO₂ that cannot be shipped from these clusters or that is captured from the remaining clusters is sent to a pipeline network. Within the pipeline network, the CO₂ not used in a CCU installation in Aalborg is distributed to the geological storage sites Bifrost, Jammerbugt, Gassum, Voldum and Thorning.

The supply to CCU projects is met by 100%, according to the defined demand. The supply for CCS reaches approximately 93% of the estimated geological storage annual capacity.

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Figure 3-25 Selected transportation scenario for WP4

Table 3-12 Utilisation maximum consumption

Utilisation project		CO ₂ used [Mt/y]
Germany – Bremen		3.20
Denmark – Aalborg		1.66
Sweden – Gothenburg		1.19
Total		6.1

The pipelines defined in Table 3-13, with pipeline diameters ranging from 6 to 30 inches and a total network length of approximately 1720 km.

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Table 3-13 Pipeline list for the selected scenario

Pipe #	From	To	Cluster	Country	Phase	State	Flow-rate [t/h]	Length [km]	Size [inches]
P1	S_DE_115	S_DE_83	Bremen Cluster	Germany	2	gas	77	44	16
P2	S_DE_83	S_DE_38	Bremen Cluster	Germany	1	gas	179	74	24
P3	S_DE_130	Intersection S_DE_82/130	Hannover Cluster	Germany	1	gas	65	48	16
P4	S_DE_82	Intersection S_DE_82/130	Hannover Cluster	Germany	2	gas	104	15	18
P5	Intersection S_DE_82/130	S_DE_124	Hannover Cluster	Germany	1	gas	170	17	24
P6	S_DE_124	S_DE_116	Hannover Cluster	Germany	1	gas	238	2	24
P7	S_DE_116	Intersection S_DE_116/53	Hannover Cluster	Germany	1	gas	314	10	24
P8	S_DE_53	Intersection S_DE_116/53	Hannover Cluster	Germany	1	gas	161	17	16
P9	Intersection S_DE_116/53	S_DE_62	Hannover Cluster	Germany	1	dense	474	138	20
P10	S_DE_62	Intersection S_DE_62/70	Shared Infrastructure	Germany	1	dense	607	75	20
P11	S_DE_72	Intersection S_DE_72/123	Hamburg Cluster	Germany	2	gas	124	11	18
P12	S_DE_123	Intersection S_DE_72/123	Hamburg Cluster	Germany	2	gas	70	12	14
P13	Intersection S_DE_72/123	S_DE_70	Hamburg Cluster	Germany	2	gas	194	38	20
P14	S_DE_70	Intersection S_DE_62/70	Hamburg Cluster	Germany	1	dense	319	26	12
P15	Intersection S_DE_62/70	Intersection Germany-Denmark	Shared Infrastructure	Germany / Denmark	1	dense	926	205	24
P16	Intersection Germany-Denmark	Intersection Esbjerg	Shared Infrastructure	Denmark	1	dense	1077	39	30
P17	Intersection Esbjerg	S_DK_14	Shared Infrastructure	Denmark	1	dense	258	27	12
P18	Intersection Esbjerg	Bifrost	Shared Infrastructure	Denmark	1	dense	100	256	14

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Pipe #	From	To	Cluster	Country	Phase	State	Flow-rate [t/h]	Length [km]	Size [inches]
P19	Intersection Esbjerg	S_DK_56	Shared Infrastructure	Denmark	1	dense	719	82	24
P20	S_DK_56	Intersection close to S_DK_18	Shared Infrastructure	Denmark	1	dense	719	39	24
P21	S_DK_56	Thorning	West Midtjylland Cluster	Denmark	2	dense	42	31	6
P22	S_DK_18	Intersection close to S_DK_18	West Midtjylland Cluster	Denmark	2	dense	31	16	6
P23	Intersection close to S_DK_18	Intersection west Gassum	Shared Infrastructure	Denmark	1	dense	751	81	24
P24	Intersection west Gassum	Gassum	Shared Infrastructure	Denmark	1	dense	463	37	18
P25	Gassum	S_DK_57	Shared Infrastructure	Denmark	1	dense	88	10	8
P26	S_DK_57	Voldum / Intersection S_DK_4/58	Shared Infrastructure	Denmark	1	dense	120	29	8
P27	S_DK_4	Voldum / Intersection S_DK_4/58	Aarhus Cluster	Denmark	2	dense	48	10	6
P28	S_DK_58	Voldum / Intersection S_DK_4/58	Aarhus Cluster	Denmark	1	dense	65	10	6
P29	Intersection west Gassum	Intersection Jammerbugt and Aalborg	Shared Infrastructure	Denmark	1	dense	288	74	16
P30	S_DK_13	S_DK_1	Aalborg Cluster	Denmark	1	gas	28	7	6
P31	S_DK_1	Intersection Jammerbugt and Aalborg	Aalborg Cluster	Denmark	1	dense	87	10	6
P32	Intersection Jammerbugt and Aalborg	Jammerbugt	Shared Infrastructure	Denmark	1	dense	375	62	16
P33	S_DK_25	Intersection Fredericia	Fredericia Cluster	Denmark	1	gas	12	65	8
P34	S_DK_15	Intersection Fredericia	Fredericia Cluster	Denmark	1	gas	21	19	8

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Pipe #	From	To	Cluster	Country	Phase	State	Flow-rate [t/h]	Length [km]	Size [inches]
P35	S_DK_54	Intersection Fredericia	Fredericia Cluster	Denmark	1	gas	68	17	12
P36	S_DK_9	Intersection Fredericia	Fredericia Cluster	Denmark	2	gas	51	22	10
P37	Intersection Fredericia	Intersection Germany-Denmark	Fredericia Cluster	Denmark	1	dense	152	30	10
P38	S_SE_79	S_SE_29	Gothenburg Cluster	Sweden	1	gas	15	5	6
P39	S_SE_31	S_SE_89	Gothenburg Cluster	Sweden	1	gas	68	2	8
P40	S_SE_33	S_SE_34	Gothenburg Cluster	Sweden	1	gas	63	6.5	12
P41	S_SE_34	S_SE_73	Gothenburg Cluster	Sweden	1	gas	123	1.5	12

CO₂ will be shipped from the Gothenburg and Esbjerg clusters to offshore storage locations in Denmark. The respective ship cycle times are presented in Table 3-14.

Table 3-14 Cycle times from selected harbours to offshore storage sites

From	To	Distance [km]	Cycle time [h]
Gothenburg	Lisa	210	54
Gothenburg	Inez	330	65
Esbjerg	Inez	215	54
Esbjerg	Greensand	255	58

The selected scenario for transportation infrastructure is a concept out of many possible. The current selection is not equivalent to a thorough analysis and comparison between the different transportation solutions. Nonetheless, it takes inspiration from existing or planned projects and provides a pragmatic solution for implementing a CCUS network in the three countries analysed.

3.6 CO₂ use options

CCU is being increasingly recognised in recent legislation at EU level and is starting to be adopted also in national climate and energy transition plans as solution to reduce emissions, increase circularity in production systems and provide an alternative carbon feedstock for the production of fuels, chemicals and materials that will substitute fossil-derived conventional products. The following sections describe some indicative projects in the countries of interest

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even if they are not located inside the clusters. Indeed, the advantage of a CCU value chain is that it can be replicated in different locations, as long as there is a supply of CO₂ (industrial, biogenic, atmospheric) and a demand for CCU products; this is by default the case in the CCUS ZEN clusters that are located in areas of concentrated industrial activity where CO₂ can be an alternative feedstock to produce the products that are generated in these clusters, thereby contributing to the industrial symbiosis of the clusters.

Table 3-15 CCU Projects Overview

Country	City	Project / Technology	Amount of CO ₂ used	Product per t CO ₂
Germany	Hannover	Leilac 2: Oxyfuel combustion	Approx. 100 kt/year captured (possibly to be used or stored)	Unknown, depending on the use
Germany	Lägerdorf (50 km northwest of Hamburg)	Carbon2Business: Oxy-fuel Combustion / CO ₂ to Methanol / Methanol to Jet fuel	Approx. 1.2 Mt/year	Approx. 0.72 kg methanol
Denmark	Aalborg	ConsenCUS demo: alkali absorption/ catalytic conversion	Approx. 100 kg/h	Approx 1 kg formic acid
Denmark	Aabenraa (80 km south of Fredericia)	Kassø: Catalytic methanol production	Approx. 60 kt/a	Approx. 0.72 kg of methanol
Denmark	Copenhagen	Green fuels for Denmark: CO ₂ to methanol / methanol to jet fuel	Approx. 70 kt/a (phase 2a; 2027); 210 kt/a (phase 2b); 850 kt/a (phase 3)	Approx. 0.72 kg of methanol Approx. 0.3 kg of synthetic jet fuel
Sweden	Stenungsund (50 km north of Gothenburg)	AIR: Catalytic methanol production	Approx. 270 kt/year	Approx. 0.72 kg of methanol
Sweden	Örnsköldsvik/ Sundsvall/ Umea/ (northeast of Gothenburg)	Flagships ONE/TWO/THREE: Catalytic methanol conversion	Approx. 70/140/140 kt/a respectively	Approx. 0.72 kg of methanol
Sweden	Forsmark (northeast of Gothenburg)	HySkies: Synthetic fuel production	Approx. 270 kt/a	Approx. 0.3 kg of synthetic jet fuel

A brief description of some of these projects follows:

Carbon2Business & Westküste100 (Germany)

Carbon2Business is an Innovation Fund-supported project that implements CCU technology in a cement installation of Holcim in Lägerdorf (Holcim, 2024). The project aims to capture approx. 1.2 Mt of CO₂ per year from an innovative oxy-fuel combustion kiln and transform them into methanol for subsequent conversion into jet fuel to cover fuel demand in the Hamburg airport. This project is developed in the context of the WESTKÜSTE100 real-world laboratory that aims to generate essential economic, technological, and scientific knowledge by integrating carbon capture, renewable hydrogen production from water electrolysis and synthetic fuel generation. The goal is to establish cross-sector, closed value-creation chains in the region (Westküste100, 2024).

The electrolyser will be integrated into an existing refinery process to demonstrate the direct industrial use of hydrogen. A nearby cavern system will serve as interim storage for the generated hydrogen, making it available for industrial use. A hydrogen grid connecting the refinery, the cavern, and Heide Municipal Utilities (SWH) will be established, featuring innovative pipeline technology in the section between Raffinerie Heide and Heide Municipal Utilities. This project will explore the long-term integration of hydrogen into the existing gas infrastructure, contributing to heat supply decarbonization through green hydrogen admixture in a gas grid section.

Feasibility studies will investigate how the oxygen produced during electrolysis can be used in the “oxyfuel process” for cement works in Lägerdorf, with subsequent carbon dioxide separation and methanol production as part of the Carbon2Business project.

Green Fuels for Denmark (Denmark)

Green Fuels for Denmark is an IPCEI-supported project in the area of Copenhagen that couples renewable energy production, biogenic point-source CCU, and synthesis of e-fuels with district heating, wastewater treatment, and sustainable fuel use in hard-to-abate transport sectors following a full sector-coupling approach. Designed in three phases, the project aims at advancing the Power-to-X industry, delivering the green e-fuels that are needed to secure Europe’s regional energy independence and fight climate change (Orsted, 2024). The three phases are:

Phase 1: 10 MW electrolyser capacity, completed in 2025; **Phase 2a:** 100 MW, completed in 2027; **Phase 2b:** Upscaling to 300 MW accumulated capacity by 2028/2029; **Phase 3:** Realise 1,300 MW beyond 2030

In its first phase, the project will produce green hydrogen to fuel heavy-duty road trucks. In phase 2a, the consortium plans to produce enough e-methanol to power an ocean-going vessel or several ferries, and to start producing e-kerosene, a renewable synthetic jet-fuel, in volumes suitable to run the first, innovative tests. In phases 2b and 3, the project will significantly scale-up the production of both e-methanol and e-kerosene.

Project Air (Sweden)

Project Air is an industrial initiative aimed at achieving climate neutrality in the chemical industry and reducing carbon emissions throughout industrial value chains. Perstorp Group and Uniper will collaborate to produce sustainable methanol for chemical manufacturing using circular production methods, resulting in a significant annual reduction of 500,000 tons of carbon dioxide emissions, equivalent to the emissions from approximately 340,000 new cars

running on fossil fuels (Project Air, 2024). Perstorp will establish CCU plant in Stenungsund, Sweden. This facility will convert captured carbon dioxide emissions from Perstorp's operations, along with other residue streams, biogas, and renewable hydrogen, into methanol. Uniper will provide renewable hydrogen from a cutting-edge hydrogen electrolysis plant.

Project Air's primary goal is to replace all 200,000 tons of fossil methanol used annually by Perstorp in Europe as a raw material for chemical products. This will involve using carbon dioxide emissions captured from Perstorp's operations as a fundamental component in methanol production, effectively eliminating greenhouse gas emissions associated with operations.

Furthermore, various streams of residues containing carbon and hydrogen from production processes will be recycled, biomethane from biogas production plants will be converted into synthesis gas, and Uniper will generate renewable hydrogen using purified wastewater and renewable electricity, making it one of the world's largest hydrogen electrolysis units in the chemical industry, and the first to use purified wastewater in electrolysis on a global scale.

HySkies (Sweden)

The HySkies project will establish a large-scale synthetic sustainable aviation fuel (SAF) and renewable diesel production facility in Sweden, annually producing 82,000 t of SAF and 9,000 t of renewable diesel. It utilizes fossil-free hydrogen, biogenic CO₂ from waste-to-energy, and sustainable ethanol in a two-step gas fermentation and alcohol-to-jet (AtJ) process, achieving a 94% greenhouse gas emission reduction over the first decade of operation (Vattenfall, 2024).

HySkies demonstrates the scalability and integration of carbon capture, electrolysis, gas fermentation, and AtJ processes, resulting in cost-efficiency, high yields, and production flexibility.

CO₂ capture technology, electrolysis, and gas fermentation are established, with the 200 MW electrolyser being notably larger than existing plants. The AtJ technology, while less mature, is based on standard refinery operations.

The project is expected to contribute to EU climate neutrality objectives by avoiding 2.7 Mt of CO₂ equivalent emissions in its first ten years, equivalent to the CO₂ absorbed by about 10 Mln trees annually.

FlagshipONE – TWO – THREE (Sweden)

Located in Örnsköldsvik in Northern Sweden, FlagshipONE is Europe's largest green e-methanol facility. FlagshipONE is expected to enter into operation in 2025 and will produce around 50,000 t of e-methanol each year to help decarbonise the world's shipping industry, a sector responsible for 3% of global greenhouse gas emissions.

Ørsted started onsite construction of FlagshipONE in the spring of 2023 (Orsted, 2023). The project is located on the grounds of the biomass-fired combined heat and power plant Hörneborgsverket in r, operated by Övik Energi. Biogenic carbon dioxide emissions from the energy facility will be captured and combined with renewable hydrogen to form liquid carbon neutral fuel. In addition, FlagshipONE will use steam, process water, and cooling water from Hörneborgsverket. Excess heat from the e-methanol production process will be delivered back to Övik Energi and integrated in their district heating supply.

Liquid Wind's second facility (FlagshipTWO) is being designed in cooperation with the energy company Sundsvall Energi and will be located on the Korstaverket site in Sundsvall, close to

the Tunadal harbour. The facility will capture carbon dioxide from the Korsta plant, and the biogenic part of the captured carbon dioxide (approx. 140 kt/a) will be used to produce e-fuel for shipping as a substitute for fossil fuels (Liquid Wind, 2024). A third facility (FlagshipTHREE) of similar size to the one in Sundsvall is now planned together with the energy company Umeå Energi at the Dåva cogeneration plant in Umeå (Liquid Wind, 2024).

3.6.1 CCU value chain scenarios

Typically, CCU facilities are located directly next to or close to the source of CO₂ as their size can be flexible depending on the supply of CO₂ from the side of the emitter. Nevertheless, and depending on the transport scenario considered within CCUS ZEN within each cluster, it can be envisaged that (larger) CCU facilities can be deployed in the intermediary collection hubs that would gather CO₂ from more emitters. Based on the infrastructure options considered in section 3.6 we can assume that this role will be played by Bremen, Aalborg and Gothenburg for the clusters of Germany, Denmark and Sweden, respectively. In the following, we have assumed that (a minimum of) 30% of the captured CO₂ in a cluster is dedicated to CCU and 70% to CCS, to be aligned with the Impact Assessment of the EU 2040 climate targets communication (for 2040).

Scenario 1 (Table 3-16) would consider CCU facilities in the direct vicinity of the Phase 1 emitters (some of which are already planning such installations), while scenario 2 would consider CCU facilities in the vicinity of the collecting hub, thereby accommodating a larger volume of CO₂. In Scenario 1, the conditioning of the CO₂ stream from each individual emitter will match directly the requirements of the connected downstream utilisation. In scenario 2 it is expected that a conditioning step will be required between the centralised collection hub and the respective CCU facility.

Table 3-16 Two scenarios for CO₂ use options

Scenario 1						
Country	Cluster	Captured CO ₂ from Phase 1 emitters (<i>Biogenic fraction</i>) (Mt)	Captured CO ₂ from Phase 1 emitters for CCU (Mt)	Number of CCU installations close to Phase 1 emitters	Average capture capacity of CCU installation (kt)	Average product capacity of CCU installation (kt)
Germany	-	6.61 (4.98)	1.98	7	280	190 (for methanol) 85 (for synthetic jet fuel)
Denmark	-	4.16 (1.17)	1.25	8	156	109 (for methanol) 47 (for synthetic jet fuel)

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Sweden	-	2.95 (0.34)	0.89	5	178	125 (for methanol) 53 (for synthetic jet fuel)
Scenario 2						
Country	Cluster acting as collection hub	Captured CO ₂ from all emitters (<i>Biogenic fraction</i>) (Mt)	Captured CO ₂ from all emitters for CCU (Mt)	Number of CCU installations close to the collection hub	Average capture capacity of CCU installation (kt)	Average product capacity of CCU installation (kt)
Germany	Bremen	10.66 (5.59)	3.20	5	640	450 (for methanol) 192 (for synthetic jet fuel)
Denmark	Aalborg	5.53 (1.82)	1.66	5	332	232 (for methanol) 100 (for synthetic jet fuel)
Sweden	Gothenburg	3.95 (0.65)	1.19	5	238	167 (for methanol) 72 (for synthetic jet fuel)

In both scenarios, the capture and product capacity of the envisaged installations is comparable to the capacities of the ongoing and upcoming projects that have been described in section 3.5.1, which renders both scenarios plausible. Scenario 2 has in general considered a larger average capacity because it reflects a concept where CO₂ volumes have been centralised, hence the facilities may accommodate larger volumes. For both scenarios, it is relevant to compare the CO₂ amount dedicated to CCU to the biogenic CO₂ capacity estimated from Phase 1 emitters from Table 3-2, Table 3-3 and Table 3-4, even though this estimation entails some uncertainty. In Germany's case the CCU-dedicated is clearly inferior and in Denmark's and Sweden's case it is comparable considering the uncertainty of the estimation. This is an indication that CCU applications can be covered by the biogenic CO₂ available, in case ETS-related CO₂ is not counted as avoided as of 2041 in the calculation for the emission reduction of CCU fuels. The scenarios above considered CCU installations for the production of fuels and chemicals, but mineralisation is an equally relevant option for all clusters. It is nevertheless difficult to provide an estimation of the product capacity because it depends strongly on the input material in which the CO₂ will be mineralised. As an example, the project CO₂ncrEAT in Belgium considers mineralisation of approx. 20 kt/a of CO₂ into treated steel

slags to produce about 130 kt/a of masonry blocks. Based on above mentioned capture capacities, mineralisation is, therefore, also an option.

3.6.2 Selected option for WP4

Scenario 2 has in general considered a larger average capacity because it reflects a concept where CO₂ volumes have been centralised, hence the CCU facilities may accommodate larger volumes. Scenario 1, although more flexible on Phase 1, shows more risk, as the utilisation plants are highly dependent of their respective adjacent emitter. For these reasons, utilisation Scenario 2 was selected for analysis in WP4.

3.7 Risk and safety

In the EU, sites handling large quantities of hazardous substances are subject to the Seveso directive. It is important to note that while CO₂ is not currently considered a risk/hazardous substance according to Seveso II directive, it may be in the future. As such, it is common practice to take a proactive approach to mitigate potential risks and apply similar strategies and methods for CO₂ as we do for risk/hazardous facilities in accordance with the Seveso III Directive and the corresponding country-specific regulations (Haper, 2011).

The hazards of a CO₂ release increase significantly when the CO₂ is in its supercritical or liquid phase. Storing or transporting substantial inventories of CO₂ in these phases together in hubs may result in very large risk zones. This raises the possibility of CO₂ being categorized as a major accident hazard (MAH) and/or being subject to stricter country-specific regulations, especially when it comes to permitting for land use planning purposes.

The assessment of risks is therefore essential to decide which risks would be acceptable and what kind of analysis would be required to properly assessed and mitigate those risks. For this purpose, a set of acceptance criteria is required.

In land-use planning processes, risk is often quantified with the two measurements:

- Individual risk, location specific and risk per annum
- Societal risk

Location specific individual risk (LSIR) refers to the yearly risk of an accident-related fatality for a hypothetical person. It is typically used to assess risks for the public (3rd parties). This measurement assumes the person is positioned at a specific location 24h/day for 365 days/year. The purpose of the individual risk acceptance criterion is to effectively limit risks to individuals in populations residing near a source of risk.

Individual risk per annum (IRPA) is a second measurement for individual risk, primarily used for the workforce (1st parties). It refers to the yearly risk of an accident-related fatality for a specific or hypothetical person, such as a worker group, that is positioned at a specific location and thereby exposed to a source of risk for a defined period during the year.

Societal risk, also known as group risk, refers to the risk of loss of life caused by a given activity without referring to specific individuals. To establish a tolerance criterion for societal risk, and F-N (F=accident frequency; N=number of fatalities) curve is often presented, showing the cumulative number of fatalities.

The societal risk encompasses the entire population, including the public (3rd parties) exposed to a particular risk. Societal risk acceptance criteria are specifically designed to limit the risk for certain areas or for populations near a source of risk. This approach is useful for identifying potential risks and assessing their impact on society rather than focusing on specific

individuals. The FN curve helps to establish a threshold for acceptable risk, which can inform decision-making around activities that may pose a risk to society.

3.7.1 Country-specific requirements

Figure 3-26 Acceptance criteria for societal risk according to Environment Project 112 (Taylor et al, 1989)

Due to variations in regulations across countries, the acceptable risk requirements are contingent on the specific location. Consequently, the requirements to address the distinct safety and risk considerations applicable to each of the three countries involved in the project (Germany, Denmark, and Sweden) are described in the following Table 3-17.

The purple line indicates the minimum criteria. The grey zone indicates where the ALARA (As Low As Reasonably Achievable) principle should be used.

Table 3-17 Country specific regulations

Country	Regulatory Body	Main legislation & regulations	Risk acceptance criteria (RAC)
Sweden	Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency (MSB)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Environmental Code, Miljöbalk (1998:808) - Building act, Plan och bygglagen (2010:900) - The Act on Protection against Accidents, Lag (2003:778) om skydd mot olyckor - The Act on Flammable and Explosive Substances, Lag (2010:1011) om brandfarliga och explosiva varor 	<p>The LSIR is considered acceptable if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Upper limit where risks to public can be tolerated under certain conditions: 1×10^{-5} per year. - Below 1×10^{-7} risks to public can in general be accepted without further reduction. <p>There is no official RAC for Sweden, but DNV on behalf of the Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency (MSB) presented a suggestion for RAC which is unofficially adapted as the RAC for major accident facilities in Sweden (DNV, Värdering av risk, 1997).</p> <p>For societal risk, the following risk acceptance criteria have been proposed by DNV for persons from the public (3rd parties) (F = accident frequency and N = number of fatalities):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Upper limit where the risks under certain conditions are considered acceptable: $F = 10^{-4}$ per year for $N = 1$ with the slope on the F / N curve -1.

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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Upper limit where risks are considered acceptable: $F = 10^{-6}$ per year for $N = 1$ with the slope on the F / N curve -1.
Denmark	Miljøstyrelsen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Environmental assessment, Miljøvurderingsloven - Building act, Bygningsreglementet (BR18) - BEK nr. 1444 af 15/12/2010 (Bekendtgørelse om tekniske forskrifter for gasser) for storage of CO2 - Guidelines from DNV-RP-F104 for pipelines design 	<p>The LSIR is considered acceptable if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The company behind the risk source has full control of the area inside the 10^{-5} iso-risk curve (inden for grænsen till naboskel). - No vulnerable areas (følsom arealanvendelse) exist or are planned inside the 10^{-6} iso-risk curve. <p>A vulnerable area is defined as a residential area, office area, hotels, or a corresponding area where many persons are expected to be present (e.g., sports center, train stations and shopping malls).</p> <p>There is no official RAC for societal risk in Denmark but there have been recommendations from the study Environment Project 112 (Taylor et al, 1989) which are used as guidelines and are shown on Figure 3 below.</p>
Germany		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Federal Emission Control Act (BImSchG) - Environmental Impact Assessment Act (UVPG) - Circular Economy and Waste Act (KrW-/AbfG) - Greenhouse Gas Emissions Trading Act (TEHG) - Major Accident Hazard Ordinance (12-BImSchV) – Seveso III directive - Ordinance on Industrial Safety (BetSichV) - Guideline KAS 18 from the German Committee on Plant Safety (KAS) 	<p>Germany uses a purely qualitative method whereby frequencies are not assessed at all. The risk acceptance criteria are available in the form of distance requirements.</p> <p>CO₂ is neither explicitly named in the Major Accident Hazard Ordinance or KAS 18 guidelines, nor can it be assigned to one of the hazard categories listed there.</p> <p>Therefore, the storage or pipeline transport of carbon dioxide is not subject to the scope of the Major Accident Hazards Ordinance due to its material properties. However, chemicals that fall under the Hazardous Incident Ordinance, such as amines, may be used in CCS unit. Here, it must be determined whether the relevant thresholds listed in Annex 1 Major Incident Ordinance are met or exceeded.</p> <p>Very often, the main plants, especially gas or gasoline fuelled power stations, chemical plants, i.e., are classified major incident establishments in the Major Accident Hazards Ordinance. In this case, identified relevant operation chemicals must be considered to determine whether the establishment is classified under lower or upper tier. Additionally, potential hazards caused by the CCS unit must be identified and counter or mitigation measures must be taken.</p>

3.7.2 Recommendations

As we explore the advancements in Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage (CCUS) technologies, it becomes evident that this field presents unique challenges and opportunities for environmental protection and operational safety. The CCUS sector, by its nature, handles carbon dioxide (CO₂) on a scale vastly different from its usage in industries such as oil and gas or food processing. This difference is not just quantitative but also extends into the realms of regulatory frameworks and safety considerations, notably in the absence of specific guidelines like those provided by the Seveso Directive in Europe. The complexity of the CCUS value chain cannot be understated, stretching across multiple countries and encompassing

varied regulatory landscapes. Certain segments of the value chain, particularly CO₂ storage or export pipelines that traverse urban locales, harbour significant risks to the environment, infrastructure, and public health. These potential hazards underscore the importance of conducting comprehensive risk assessments tailored to the specific requirements of each country and locality involved in the CCUS process.

Addressing the risks intrinsic to the handling and storage of large volumes of CO₂ necessitates a proactive approach to risk management. Despite the familiarity with CO₂'s properties and risks, existing legislation may fall short of adequately addressing the challenges posed by CCUS operations. Early implementation of risk management strategies is essential, considering the diverse legislative environments that could introduce project risks and complicate compliance efforts.

In mitigating high-risk scenarios within CCUS operations, the emphasis on inherently safe design principles, adequate safety barriers, and the strategic placement of infrastructure becomes paramount. This includes maintaining safe distances from public areas and leveraging natural and physical barriers for secure CO₂ containment. Optimizing the layout and capacity of storage tanks, particularly by situating them in less populated areas, significantly reduces the risk of exposure to hazardous events.

For CO₂ transportation, particularly liquid CO₂ (LCO₂), recommendations advocate for underground pipelines to protect against external threats and maintain a safe distance from residential areas. Effective communication with regulators and updating safety data sheets to reflect the properties of LCO₂ are crucial steps toward establishing a robust regulatory framework.

Moreover, the European Union and global stakeholders are called upon to pursue harmonized regulatory approaches, ensuring clear, location-specific guidelines for hazard and risk assessments. Educating and training third-party personnel involved in CCUS activities is also vital, preparing them to manage the sector's complexities safely and efficiently.

In integrating these perspectives, the CCUS sector's development must be approached with caution and innovation. Drawing from related industries' best practices and pioneering new standards in safety and regulation, CCUS can fulfil its potential as a key component of global climate mitigation efforts, achieving environmental safety and sustainability through collaborative industry, regulatory, and community efforts.

3.8 CO₂ monitoring infrastructure

The monitoring programme, which shall be in effect before injection begins and until transfer of responsibility, shall be based on a baseline survey comprising all relevant pre-injection data pertaining to the storage complex itself supplemented by data covering the near-surface (e.g. groundwater) and surface conditions (e.g. onshore and offshore biota, natural CO₂ flux, natural CO₂ compositions, etc.).

According to the published Technology Description from DEA (2024) – Danish Energy Agency, some typical baseline components are suggested:

- Baseline survey onshore – typical components:
- 2D or 3D seismic survey
- At least one well with ample data from the reservoir, cap rock, and top hole
- Laboratory analysis of samples, especially cap rock integrity
- Storage complex numerical maps, models and predictions

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- Legacy wells (location, abandonment, leakage risk)
- Well integrity monitoring
- Groundwater survey: mapping and representative sampling of water
- Natural CO₂ flux in representative locations above the storage complex taking into account soil types, vegetation, seasonal variations, etc.

According to DEA (2024), the cost of establishing the onshore baseline is estimated at 20 MDKK (2.7 M€), and some 5 MDKK (0.7 M€) in annual follow-up cost. In addition, there is the cost of less frequent onshore seismic surveys (estimated at 90 MDKK (12 M€) (per survey) combined with the use of monitoring wells at spill points.

For offshore baseline monitoring DEA (2024) suggests some typical components:

- 3D seismic survey
- Storage complex model based on at least one well, or in the case of a depleted oil and gas field numerical models based on production data and operational experience, possibly supplemented by specific additional data on cap rock and reservoir susceptibility to CO₂
- Legacy wells; exploration, appraisal and production wells (location, abandonment, leakage risk)
- Well integrity monitoring
- Marine pelagic and benthonic biota survey
- Seabed survey of shallow geographical and geological features including possible natural flux of CO₂ or other gasses

According to DEA (2024), the cost of establishing the offshore baseline is estimated at around 10 MDKK (1.35 M€). To be repeated every 4–5 years combined with a 3D seismic survey (estimated at 70 MDKK (9.3 M€) per survey) and model updates.

The cost estimates for seismic surveys given above are only indicative as they will be very site dependent. The cost includes mobilisation and area depending on cost. As shown in the table the area is very variable and will therefore influence the site-specific cost.

3.8.1 Old Infrastructure Reusing

Table 3-18 Parameters relevant for infrastructure and monitoring assessment

Baltic-2 cluster, Site name	Location	Area of structure as used in the capacity estimation, km ²	Number of wells	Comments
Gassum	Onshore	233	1	Completed 1951, no commercial hydrocarbons, abandoned
Voldum	Onshore	560	1	Completed 1974, no commercial hydrocarbons, abandoned
Jammerbugt	Offshore	140	0	
Inez	Offshore	250	1	Completed 1977, no commercial hydrocarbons, abandoned

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Bifrost	Offshore West Harald field	16	5	Mature gas/condensate field. 2 wells producing gas, 3 wells abandoned (status 2012)
Greensand	Offshore Nini field	16	10	Depleted oil field. 6 producing wells and 4 wells with water injection (status 2009)
Lisa	Offshore	70	0	
Thorning	Onshore	210	0	

The storage sites of offshore depleted oil and gas fields have existing production infrastructure including 15 production wells. Bifrost has a production platform and an accommodation platform. Greensand has an unmanned production platform. It is the plan to re-use some of these installations for the injection of CO₂, probably undergoing modifications and adaptations to the new compounds and pressures in these operations.

For the Danish onshore sites where old wells are present, some are drilled during the 1950'es, and the plugging and abandonment procedures and thereby the status of the well integrity is highly uncertain. These wells are risk elements that have to be included in the risk register for these sites as they penetrate the sealing formations.

3.8.2 New infrastructure planned

The depleted offshore reservoirs are assumed to operate for 20 years, the other sites for 30 years.

For Bifrost and Greensand, the permeabilities are estimated as conservative numbers based on limited data.

For Bifrost and Greensand, the minimum Storage Capacities are based on published numbers for annual injection rates and assumption of a 20-year operation period. Detailed information on capacity prediction is not available.

Well injectivity is assumed linked to permeability. A 400 mD formation is assumed to take 0.5 Mtpa pr well as it is assumed in publication on Danish CCS (DEA, 2024).

The storage site area for the Gassum, Voldum and Thorning sites was calculated during the capacity evaluation, the rest is estimated from the published maps of structural contours.

The total annual CO₂ injection volume is linked to the number of wells and their injectivity. All estimates include 1 extra surplus well accounting for maintenance periods. For Greensand it is assumed for the first 5 years operation that 4 wells inject in total 1.5 Mtpa. The future development plans are not included in this analysis which has decided to use conservative numbers for these uncertain scenarios. For Bifrost, it is assumed for the first 5 years of operation that 4 wells inject 0.8 Mtpa. For the remaining sites, the well count is based on evaluating permeability and area.

Monitoring wells are only advised for onshore sites. Numbers are advised in publication on Danish CCS (DEA 2024).

The number of monitoring campaigns by operator can be calculated (based on the regulations table). It is calculated as following: baseline monitoring (1) + annually during storage (projects duration) + (3) three years annually after storage site closure + (4) every 5 years before transfer responsibility (minimum 20 years). Financial contribution to Competent authority for

30 years after the transfer of responsibility could be calculated as 6 monitoring campaigns (30 years - we propose every 5 years).

3.8.3 Monitoring plan design and implementation

Monitoring plan design and implementation consists of the process for selecting various monitoring techniques, locations, and frequencies of application. The monitoring plan should adopt a risk-based approach to its design. The risk assessment compiled should be used to identify the range of monitoring needs for risk management purposes. A wide range of potential techniques should be considered. Choices of technique, their base level data needs, locations, and frequency of application should be carefully considered.

For the potential Danish storage sites, the recent storage licensing round in the spring of 2024 – “Licenses for exploration and storage of CO₂, including environmental consultation rounds” issued a rich catalogue of application material with documents also describing the conditions for monitoring (DEA, 2024).

In this material, Appendix 3 contains a relevant chapter: “B1.4. Information about the area under application”

This chapter advises on an initial screening to assess and characterize the storage project and storage site. There is reference to the relevant directives, standards and guidelines such as the Danish CCS Executive Order and the EU CCS Directive with annexes, ISO standard 27914:2017 and DNV-RP-J203. The chapter lists some points as a short guide to what such an initial screening could include, although not exhaustive:

- Preliminary description of risk management for the project, divided into activities associated with the various phases.
- Initial screening of the storage site, storage complex and the hydraulic unit. I.e. initial characterisation and assessment of the potential storage site, storage complex and the surrounding area, to the extent possible, concerning technical and geological uncertainties and risks, containment, capacity and injectivity.
- A brief description of the preliminary plans for MMV (measurement, monitoring & verification).”

As seen in this Danish licensing announcement there are indications of the EU Directive and other formal documents as a basis for the description but not a very fixed scheme for the requested MMV plan, other than it should be risk assessment based.

3.9 Non-technical issues

This section introduces the key non-technical issues that shape the challenges and opportunities of pursuing CCUS in the countries that would be primarily concerned with the development of the Baltic-2 CCUS project: Germany, Denmark, and Sweden. Drawing on a broader examination of non-technical issues presented in a white paper (Honegger et al., 2024), it first outlines the overall situations in each country including their national strategies pertinent to CCUS, second it outlines the status and applicability of international regulations, followed, third, by an overview of the regulatory conditions, fourth, governmental support, and finally, fifth, an overview of challenges in public perception that may be supporting or holding back necessary policy developments.

3.9.1 Overall Situation and National Strategies in the Baltic case

3.9.1.1 Germany

National climate targets reported by Germany are a minimum 65% decrease in GHG emissions by 2030 compared to 1990, at least -88 % by 2040, and GHG neutrality by 2045 (NECP-Germany, 2024).

Germany does not presently have a pertinent strategy for CCUS but throughout 2023 and well into 2024 it has been developing a carbon management strategy, which is expected to provide greater clarity as to the intended role of carbon capture and storage as well as carbon capture and utilization including toward emissions reductions and removal of CO₂. As of the time of writing the Government has announced the key points of the strategy which include a declaration of willingness to remove regulatory hurdles to transporting and storing carbon dioxide and, the establishment of guidelines for CCU. Enablement of storage is limited to the high seas outside of marine protected areas, whereas storage on German land is up to the individual federal states. The carbon management strategy is also expected to limit the allowability of CCS and CCU activities for fossil sources – including ruling out entirely the application to coal power plants and precluding all government funding for all fossil fuels. Finally, the strategy is also going to steer government funding for CCS/CCU to emissions sources that are otherwise considered difficult or impossible to abate.

Germany's position is particularly as one of Europe's largest emitters and it aims to become climate neutral by 2045. CCS is thus considered necessary and a subsidy programme for the raw material industry to develop CCUS technologies is under development. Given the uncertain acceptance and legal permissibility of storage on German national territory, CO₂ export is key.

3.9.1.2 Sweden

In its long-term strategy, Sweden anticipates some contribution to its net-zero target from BECCS and CCS for the decarbonization of cement. Approximately 64% of CO₂ emissions are biogenic in Sweden (Rodrigues, et al., 2021) which opens the potential of large amounts of CO₂ removal through BECCS. Sweden is planning to reduce their GHG emissions for 85% by 2045 compared to 1990 (NECP-Sweden, 2024). 85% of Sweden's emissions are to be cut through emission reductions while the remaining 15% are envisaged to be addressed by additional measures including CCS. CCS is supported by Swedish policy measures such as investment and the regulatory framework in development. Sweden is in the process of investigating and defining specific potential storage sites.

3.9.1.3 Denmark

Denmark has conducted a first tendering process for offshore licenses for full-scale exploration and storage of CO₂ in specific areas on the Danish continental shelf and awarded three offshore exploration permits. Denmark is home to the most prominent storage site in the region with CO₂ injection being considered both onshore, nearshore and offshore. With high-level government support, GEUS and Energistyrelsen are advancing the potential of 12 to 22 billion t of CO₂ storage in Denmark. Internationally recognised for its progress toward a legal framework for CO₂ storage including the repurposing of depleted oil and gas fields for CO₂ storage, Denmark is a promising example to learn from in regard to advancing CCUS. The political outlook (for public policy support) is deemed favourable, which can be seen in the ongoing high-level financial, political rhetoric, and regulatory support (Honegger et al., 2024).

While Denmark has a regulatory framework for offshore storage, a corresponding framework for onshore storage is still under development. Denmark expects to select additional areas for storage sites before the next report and it expects to hold tenders for 1-8 additional onshore and nearshore saline aquifer storage sites in 2024 (GEUS, 2023).

3.9.2 International regulations as applicable to the Baltic case

The 1996 Protocol (London Protocol) to the 1972 Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matter (London Convention) represents the most advanced international regulatory instrument addressing the issue of CCS in sub-seabed geological formations. Initially, storage of CO₂ was prohibited under the Protocol as CO₂ was not included on the list of exceptions (Annex 1) to the general ban on dumping introduced by the Protocol. In 2006, the Contracting Parties adopted an amendment adding CO₂ to the list of exceptions, thereby creating a legal basis in international environmental law to regulate the storage of CO₂ in sub-seabed geological formations. In 2009, another amendment was proposed to overcome the export prohibition of Article 6 (which prohibits the export of wastes and other matter for dumping or incineration at sea). The amendment exempts CO₂ from the export prohibition by introducing a new paragraph 2 to this effect. This was done to facilitate cross-border CCS projects which may be needed to deploy CCS at scale. The second paragraph mandates an arrangement or agreement that, *inter alia*, allocates and confirms permitting responsibilities for the states involved in line with the provisions of the Protocol and other applicable international law. The Protocol requires that 2/3 of the Contracting Parties have accepted the amendment for it to enter into force. At the time of writing, 11 States have accepted the amendment, with Switzerland being the latest to accept the amendment on 3 January 2024. Australia and Germany have recently communicated their intention to accept the amendment.

In 2019, after 10 years of not reaching the required number of formal acceptances for entry into force, Norway and the Netherlands suggested an interim solution of provisional application. Provisional application has its basis in Article 25 of the 1969 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties and provides that the amendment can be provisionally taken into use. To do so, the Contracting Parties need to deposit a declaration of provisional application to the IMO and satisfy the Article 6.2 requirements. At the time of writing, seven Contracting Parties have deposited such declarations: Norway, Sweden, Denmark, the UK, Belgium, the Netherlands and the Republic of Korea. Italy expressed an intention to deposit a declaration of provisional application in its Draft NECP 2021–2030. This is needed before any export for offshore storage can take place. The London Protocol has no bearing on onshore storage.

Denmark and Sweden have deposited declarations of provisional application and only need to enter into an Article 6.2 agreement or arrangement to transport CO₂ across borders for offshore storage and notify the IMO. Germany will also need to deposit a declaration of provisional application before export can occur.

In addition to the international regime, several regional sea conventions have a bearing on offshore CCS operations. Particularly relevant for the Baltic Sea region are the 1992 Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area (Helsinki Convention) and the 1992 Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (OSPAR Convention).

The Helsinki Convention currently prohibits offshore storage of CO₂ in the Convention Area. This is due to Article 11 which prohibits the dumping of all wastes and other matter, except for dredged materials. Until the Convention is amended to address the ban, any offshore storage

would be prohibited. The OSPAR Convention, on the other hand, facilitates and regulates offshore storage. Sweden and Denmark are parties to both the OSPAR Convention and the Helsinki Convention. The implications are that the parts of their continental shelf that fall under the territorial scope of the Helsinki Convention cannot be used for storage. Denmark's northern and western continental shelf is open for storage as it extends into the territorial scope OSPAR Convention. The same applies for Sweden's southern/western continental shelf. For these countries, offshore storage can only occur in an area where the OSPAR regime applies, or onshore.

3.9.3 National regulations in the Baltic case countries

3.9.3.1 Germany

The Federal Government's 2022 evaluation report on the Carbon Dioxide Storage Act (KSpG), which transposed the CCS Directive, concluded that the current legal framework effectively hindered CCS, CCU, and the approval of CO₂ pipelines for CCU (Deutscher Bundestag, 2022).

In May 2024, the Federal Cabinet adopted key principles for a Carbon Management Strategy and a draft act to revise the KSpG. This revision acknowledges that emissions in certain fields are difficult or impossible to abate, necessitating the removal of current barriers blocking CCS/CCU in Germany (BMWK, 2024).

The revised KSpG will permit offshore storage, excluding marine protected areas. Onshore storage may be allowed if federal states choose to permit it and enact their legislation. To facilitate the construction of privately run CO₂ pipelines within a state regulatory framework, the KSpG will be updated based on the Federal Government's 2022 evaluation report. A uniform approval system for CO₂ pipelines will be established to clarify legal ambiguities (BMWK, 2024). Operational Power Plants Two combustion power plants, each with over 300MW capacity, became operational in 2020 and 2022, respectively. These plants have reserved areas for retrofitting CO₂ capture facilities (EU, 2001).

Exporting CO₂ for Storage For exporting CO₂ for storage in Denmark, Germany must deposit a declaration of provisional application with the IMO and enter into an arrangement or agreement with Denmark before the export can occur.

3.9.3.2 Sweden

The CCS Directive was transposed through Förordning (2014:21) om geologisk lagring av koldioxid (ordinance (2014:21) on the geological storage of CO₂), and several amendments to existing legislation. Sweden allows for storage offshore. Sweden has recently clarified its legal provisions regarding the implementation of the CCS Directive's post-closure requirements (EC, 2023).

3.9.3.3 Denmark

Denmark allows for both onshore and offshore storage of CO₂ in their national legislation due to several regulatory changes.

Since the third implementation period of the CCS Directive, Denmark has adopted legislation that "opens certain areas to continuous granting of permits for exploration and storage of carbon dioxide, designating the national permitting authority and enabling state participation in every storage permit" (EC, 2023). While there is a framework for offshore storage, the framework for onshore storage is currently under development. Denmark has established the

required processes for storage permit applicants to engage with the competent permitting authority and invite potential applicants to contact and engage for information and advice (EC, 2023).

Denmark has legislative measures in place to ensure that potential users can obtain fair and open access to transport networks and storage sites.

3.9.4 Governmental support in the Baltic case countries

3.9.4.1 Sweden

Sweden has a number of policies and measures, decided and planned, which aim to create the conditions for investments in CCS and thus interact with the achievement of the EU's overall climate objectives and contribute to emission reductions in the EU ETS. Since 2021, the Swedish Energy Agency has been mandated to be a national centre for carbon capture and storage (CCS), promoting the effective application of CCS in Sweden. In addition, in the memorandum of appropriations for 2023, the Government instructed the SGU to investigate suitable sites for permanent carbon storage in Sweden. Sweden is not expected to have a national storage capacity by 2030. Investment aid for both fossil CCS and bio-CCS is provided in the context of Industry Life (see section 3.5.3 for more details). The Industriklivet has so far supported some 80 projects. Sweden has decided to introduce State aid for bio-CCS through reverse auctions. Operators receive support for both investment and operation distributed through the so-called reverse auction where operators bid for how much CO₂ they can capture and store and at what cost. The Swedish Energy Agency is designated as an auctioneer and can distribute SEK 36 billion over the period 2026-2046 to the operators who win the reverse auctions (NECP-Sweden, 2024).

In the presented scenarios by 2030, more than 1.5 million tonnes of CO₂eq will be captured. The installations are located at the water and the CO₂ is expected to be transported by ship to Norway for storage. The estimated amount of biogenic CO₂ that could be captured by bio-CCS from 2030 onwards is 1.2-2.2 million tonnes (NECP-Sweden, 2024).

The Swedish Government and the Norwegian state-owned company Gassnova are co-funding a bilateral three-year demonstration project for CCS investigating the possibility of a full-scale CCS plant at the refinery's hydrogen installation with a potential full-scale plant being built in 2025.

3.9.4.2 Denmark

Denmark has demonstrated strong governmental support for CCUS through the establishment of a 16.6 billion Danish Krone "CCUS Fund." This fund is designed for simplicity and high effectiveness, covering the entire CCS value chain, including both fossil and biogenic CO₂. The first tendering round has been completed, and the Danish Energy Agency is currently evaluating two proposals.

Recognizing the role of CO₂ removal and its competitive challenges compared to fossil-derived CCS, 2.6 billion Danish Krone has been earmarked specifically for supporting negative emissions through BECCS. A tender process for allocating these funds is under development.

Furthermore, Executive Order No. 974, issued on June 22, 2022, supports the exploration of geological storage potentials, with the first permit already granted under this order. Additionally, the Danish Green Tax Reform has set aside an additional 17.2 billion Danish Krone for future CCS-related activities.

3.9.5 Public acceptance in the Baltic case countries

3.9.5.1 Germany

Germany has a uniquely difficult history with carbon capture as one of the first countries instituting heavily restrictive regulations in response to controversy and civil society organizations campaigning against the use of CCS. Public sentiment has been strongly negative in the past (associating it with storage of nuclear wastes) and the legal landscape consequently turned out very restrictive (amounting de facto to a moratorium of underground CO₂ storage). This legacy sentiment is still strongly present and only slowly and gradually have some civil society organizations taken a more positive position. This is not least thanks to some leading organizations such as the Clean Air Task Force, and Bellona Europe. The latter has also established a Berliner office in recent years to work in the challenging German public opinion landscape. Though the debate has reignited and there is a visible improvement in public support and regulatory conditions in Germany – exemplified with the development of the Kohlendioxid-Speicherungsgesetz (KSpG; translating to “CO₂-storage law”) and the publication of the cornerstones of the *Carbon Management Strategy*, public acceptance is still considered low (Honegger et al., 2024).

3.9.5.2 Sweden

Public acceptance of CCUS is overall considered *medium* in Sweden as most experience to date has only been made with carbon capture infrastructure, whereas the focus has been on capture from biomass processing plants including pulp and paper with storage abroad (in Norway) (Honegger et al, 2024). The advanced implementation stage of BECCS in Sweden is thus reflected in more generally positive attitudes as observed (Bellamy, 2019) though awareness varies significantly between municipalities (Haug and Stigson, 2016).

3.9.5.3 Denmark

The levels of public support for CCUS in Denmark are considered medium (Honegger et al., 2024). This is as there is on the one hand high trust in the government, which makes communication of CCUS plans and projects relatively easy and such information consequently has a positive effect on acceptance as municipalities, local politicians, and companies are jointly involved in outreach and communication. Yet at the same time, there are cultural differences between the northern and southern parts of the country, as well as a discrepancy in acceptance between the cities (high acceptance) and rural areas (low acceptance). Perceived risks include health issues due to fears of CO₂ leakage, accidents, and decreased property value. In the case of offshore CCS, there are also concerns about negative impacts on the ocean scenery and fisheries. Denmark is a good example of the benefits of involving local politicians in communications regarding CCUS and in proactive engagement with local communities to build trust.

3.10 Integration of technical and non-technical issues and conclusions in the Baltic case

The development of Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage technology is pivotal to achieving substantial reductions in carbon emissions for the three countries studied. However, the sector also faces challenges and uncertainties. A selection of the main characteristics and uncertainties of the Baltic-2 project is presented below.

Regulatory Considerations: Germany has prepared a draft act which will amend the KSpG to, inter alia, allow for offshore storage. Onshore storage will be permitted for research purposes where the federal states have allowed for such storage, having passed legislation permitting this. At the time when the value chains and locations were selected for this project, the framework in Germany presented a high risk with the de facto ban and export was seen as a suitable solution. Comparatively, Denmark has a robust and mature legal framework for storage, making it a suitable storage country for this value chain.

For Sweden, although offshore storage is allowed, the reported Helsinki Convention hinders it from being possible on a large part of its continental shelf, namely the eastern continental shelf which extends into the Helsinki Convention area. Storage is permissible on the continental shelf that extends into the OSPAR Convention regime. For Sweden, CO₂ export is the main solution for the captured carbon dioxide.

Transport Infrastructure Uncertainty: The need for large-scale transport infrastructure, including extensive pipeline networks, introduces cost and risk-related uncertainties. Transport routes may also be subject to non-technical aspects such as public acceptance and governmental support, which were not considered in the routing exercise. These factors can be impacted by the fear of consequences from failures such as leakages. Therefore, an appropriate risk and safety assessment and clear and effective communication may allow the public to understand risks.

Differing Advances in Capture, Storage, and Utilisation: The readiness level of capture solutions is noticeable, whereas the framework for carbon utilisation needs better integration. Additionally, the development of storage sites is mostly at an early readiness level, hindering the selection presented in this report and feeding uncertainty into the transport network. Denmark has licensed two offshore storage sites (Bifrost and Greensand CCS, considered in the Baltic-2 network) and launched a tender for onshore storage sites (from which Thorning and Gassum are also included). Nonetheless, these are still not at commercial readiness level.

CO₂ Volume Management: The significant CO₂ emissions of the German and Swedish economies, combined with Denmark's promising storage capacity, suggest a favourable balance for effective CCUS deployment, in the Baltic-2 network. The network can also account for expansion to other regions of Denmark, Sweden and Germany, and countries not analysed at this stage.

Danish Storage Site Accessibility: The practical use of Danish storage facilities is paramount. This involves ensuring that logistical, institutional, and contractual factors support the timely implementation of storage solutions, which is essential for the CCUS deployment timeline.

4. Mediterranean Region: Mediterranean-2 CCUS Project

4.1 Value Chain Description

Figure 4-1 Mediterranean-2 CCUS project. Location of Tarragona, Barcelona and Fos-Marseille clusters and storage site.

While the Mediterranean Sea region is defined in CCUS ZEN to cover Spain, France, Italy, Greece and Türkiye, the selected Mediterranean-2 CCUS project spans France and Spain.

The Mediterranean-2 project comprises of three clusters of emitters and one storage site offshore Spain, that is yet to be developed. The industrial clusters located in Spain are the Tarragona and the Barcelona clusters, and in France is the Fos-Marseille cluster. The geological storage site is located offshore Tarragona in the Ebro Basin (Figure 4-1). Various possibilities for CO₂ utilization (CCU) are also being considered based on CCU feasibility studies and projects in France and Spain.

Based on the promising CCUS value chains identified in Western Mediterranean (Gravaud et al., 2024), the Mediterranean-2 CCUS project is designed to keep consistency between the captured emissions volume in the promising clusters and the limited storage capacities available to date. However, as identified in WP1 work, the Lyon industrial cluster in France and emitters along the Rhone Valley could be connected to the CCUS project if additional storage capacity will be developed in the Ebro offshore area.

Figure 4-2 Block scheme of the Mediterranean CCUS Value Chain

To facilitate the collection of CO₂ from various sources within each cluster, a local gathering network is being planned before the CO₂ export. This network will transport the CO₂ in its gaseous phase via pipelines that are specifically designed for this purpose (Figure 4-2).

Once the CO₂ has been collected, two transportation scenarios (Reference Case and Alternative Case) are considered for transporting it from each cluster to the geological storage site.

Note: The scenario for the Mediterranean-2 Value Chain includes one value chain with the only difference between the Reference case and the Alternative case, being the technical options regarding the feasibility of the transport and storage chain. The number of emitters, assumed onshore pipelines, geological storage site location, injection wells, etc. are the same for the two technical alternatives. Due to the high level of uncertainty around the proposed value chain, the alternative case cannot be disqualified with the level of definition that the project has at this present state. Hence, both technical alternatives are described (but belonging to the same value chain) in this report and will be studied in Work Package 4 to allow a proper comparison based on economics.

Option 1 (Reference Case). An onshore gathering hub at Tarragona would collect the CO₂ from three clusters: CO₂ from local Tarragona emitters, CO₂ from Barcelona sent by an offshore dense phase pipeline and CO₂ from Fos-Marseille transported by ships. Fos-Marseille cluster included in the CO₂ value chain is more advanced in terms of development as the region was selected by E.U. as a Project of Common Interest (PCI) for CO₂ export terminal. From the onshore gathering hub at Tarragona, a single dense phase offshore pipeline will send the collected CO₂ to the subsea system including subsea injection wells around 58 km away (Figure 4-3).

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Figure 4-3 Transport scenario for Mediterranean-2. Option 1.

Figure 4-4 Block diagram for the Option 1 (Reference Case) of the Mediterranean-2 scenario.

Option 2 (Alternative Case): the offshore dense phase pipeline will only transport emissions from Tarragona cluster and will send the collected CO₂ from Tarragona to the subsea system including subsea injection wells around 58 km away. Captured CO₂ from the Barcelona cluster will be sent to the injection site by a dedicated offshore dense phase pipeline. Captured emissions from Fos-Marseille cluster will be shipped directly to the offshore storage site (Figure 4-6). Their injection will be via a Floating Storage and Injection Unit (FSIU) and the subsea system including subsea wells.

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Figure 4-5 Block diagram for the Option 2 (Alternative Case) of the Mediterranean-2

Figure 4-6 Transport scenario for Mediterranean-2. Option 2

4.2 Technology blocks along the chain

The Mediterranean chain includes the following technology blocks:

- Carbon Capture and Conditioning at Emitters Sites.
- CO₂ Gathering Network (onshore gas phase pipelines).
- Compression facilities to Gas phase for gathering network.
- Liquefaction Fos-Marseille
- LCO₂ carriers, Ship loading and unloading facilities (Jetty) at Fos-Marseille.

- Intermediate Buffer Storage in case of ship transportation.
- CO₂ Compression Booster station to dense phase for offshore pipeline export.
- Offshore dense phase pipeline to subsea injection system.
- Offshore injection facilities (e.g. FSIU – Floating Storage and Injection Unit).
- Subsea Injection System and Injection Wells for CO₂ injection.
- Necessary utilities.

4.3 CO₂ emission sources

The CO₂ emission sources are the industrial sites located in the Tarragona, Barcelona and Fos-Marseille clusters. To quantify the amount of CO₂ to be handled by the value chain, the total amount of emissions per cluster was estimated. In a second step, some assumptions were taken to better estimate the actual volumes that could be considered for a CCUS chain which aims to build a cross-border network for large CO₂ volume storage.

4.3.1. Total CO₂ emissions per cluster

Table 4-1 Industrial clusters for the Mediterranean-2 CCUS project (emitters > 100 Kt/y)

Country	Cluster	Total CO ₂ emissions (MT/y)	Number of emitters
Spain	Tarragona Cluster	4.51	5
	Barcelona Cluster	4.31	9
France	Fos-Marseille Cluster	15.00	18
Total		23.82	32

The CO₂ emission sources are the industrial sites located in the Tarragona, Barcelona and Fos-Marseille clusters. These clusters were described by Gravaud et al, 2024. For the present report, only industrial sites that emit above 100 kt/y of CO₂ are considered for the Mediterranean-2 CO₂ value chain, in consistency with the hypotheses taken for all the value chains studied in the CCUS ZEN project. Moreover, an update of the CO₂ emissions was performed based on 2022 data. The total CO₂ emissions out of each cluster are listed in Table 4-1 and detailed in the following subsections.

Emissions considered come from several sources from various industry sectors. Significant differences between clusters can be highlighted with Tarragona involving mainly Refineries and Chemicals plants, Barcelona having mainly power generation and cement plants and finally Fos-Marseille with a more diversified type of emitters such as power, refineries, chemical and iron & steel plants.

To achieve their decarbonization targets, emitters have different solutions to reduce their carbon emissions, for example, electrification, process efficiency, fuel switching or CCUS. Therefore, not all emissions listed above will be directed to the CCUS value chain. An exercise to estimate the share of CCUS and final amounts to be considered in the Mediterranean value chain definition is described below.

4.3.2 Total potential CO₂ captured per cluster

Volumes of CO₂ captured for each cluster are calculated in two steps:

- Quantification of CCUS contribution to each emitter carbon emissions reduction
- CO₂ capture technology efficiency to be applied for each emitter.

Share of carbon emissions reduction addressed by CCUS:

It is important to note that while CCUS is a promising technology for reducing carbon emissions, it may not be the only solution for all emitters. Some facilities may choose to decarbonize their operations through other means, such as electrification, fuel switching, process optimization, energy recovery, carbon offsetting etc. For this reason and the purpose of the CCUS ZEN project, the following assumptions (Table 4-2) were made regarding the share of carbon emissions potentially addressed by CCUS, according to the emission source facility type. These assumptions are based on inputs from the International Energy Agency report (Ref 1) and current understanding of each sector.

Table 4-2 Share of Emissions addressed by CCUS

Facility Type	Assumed share of emissions addressed by CCUS [%]
Chemicals	35
Iron & Steel	25
Refineries	50
Power	50
Cement/Lime	65
Energy from waste	80
Hydrogen	85

CO₂ Capture technology efficiency and operating time:

It is assumed that CO₂ will be captured at the plants using one the following capture technologies:

- Post-Combustion Carbon Capture
- Pre-Combustion Carbon Capture
- Oxyfuel Processes

As for the Baltic region, the Carbon Capture Recovery is considered 95%. The Carbon Capture Technology assumed at this stage of the project is a generic amine technology which has the most installed applications to date in the industry.

CO₂ dehydration, conditioning and treatment are considered to take place in the emitters site to meet the minimum of the specifications' requirements mentioned in section 4.4.

An assumption of 8000 hours of operation is made for all plants.

Based on the above assumptions, actual CO₂ volumes to be considered for the design of the chain are shown in Table 4-3.

Table 4-3 Quantities of CO₂ captured by cluster

Country	Cluster	Number of emitters	CO ₂ captured (Mt/y)	Captured biogenic CO ₂ (Mt/y)
Spain	Tarragona	5	1.98	0.0007
	Barcelona	9	2.25	0.23
France	Fos-Marseille	18	5.54	0.21
Total		32	9.77	0.44

In the Med-2 chain scenario, the size of the Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) value chain is determined by the geological storage capacity, which is approximately 200 Mt (equivalent to 10 Mt annually over 20 years). Given the current storage site and the minimal biogenic CO₂ emissions from the clusters, a decision was taken to design the CCS value chain for the total captured emissions and a total injection rate of 9.77 Mt per year. Indeed, the fact that there is high uncertainty regarding the utilization of CO₂ in the clusters (due to uncertainty regarding the availability of green hydrogen and renewable electricity, low amount of biogenic CO₂ to date), the decision to size the transport and storage infrastructures for the total capture emissions was deemed the most relevant at this stage of the project to ensure that emitters have a solution to manage their captured emission even if the CO₂ utilization plants are not ready. Still, a minimum share of CO₂ captured is considered for utilization. This minimum corresponds to the amount of biogenic CO₂ that is captured in each cluster. Indeed, some CCU projects are already on track in these regions, offering some potential for utilization (see section CO₂ use options below) and captured biogenic CO₂ will be used in priority.

However, based on the International Energy Report (IEA, 2020) and EU strategy (EC, 2024a) targeted amounts of CO₂ to be considered for CO₂ utilization could be up to 30% of captured CO₂. The project partners therefore agreed to consider a maximum of 30% of captured CO₂ for possible CO₂ utilization scenarios by 2040.

CO₂ volumes considered for utilization are a first estimate which shall be revised based on each emitter's strategy. This target will also depend on the ability of emitters to switch from fossil fuel to biogenic fuel to increase the share of biogenic CO₂ which is today very low compared to fossil CO₂.

Based on that scenario, the CCS value chain could have up to 30% extra capacity that could be filled with new emitters connecting to the Mediterranean-2 value chain or an increase to the amount of CO₂ captured by the emitters and directed to storage in the future.

Note: All the assumptions for the amount of CO₂ directed to CCS and CCU are preliminary and shall be confirmed during the next stages of the project, where emitters will have to reserve storage capacity and secure projects that utilize CO₂ in close proximity to the clusters. The value chain will be able to adapt to any changes in CO₂ volumes since the fundamentals will not be affected as long as the storage capacity of the reservoir is respected.

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The following Table 4-4 summarizes the CO₂ volumes considered for the Mediterranean-2 value chain.

Table 4-4 CO₂ Volumes for Mediterranean-2 chain design basis

Country	Cluster	CCS value chain (Mt/y)	CO ₂ for Utilization (Mt/y)
Spain	Tarragona	1.98	0.0007–0.59
	Barcelona	2.25	0.23–0.72
France	Fos-Marseille	5.54	0.21–1.76
Total		9.77	0.44–3.07

4.3.2.1 Tarragona cluster description

The list of selected emitters located in the Tarragona Cluster can be found in Table 4-5 below.

- Captured CO₂ emissions will be transported along a new-build onshore pipeline with tie-in points for each emitter.
- The pipeline is a gas-phase pipeline that operates at 3 MPa.
- The gas phase pipeline will connect to a central compression facility, located close to Tarragona port which will compress the CO₂ from 3 MPa to approximately 15 MPa to reach dense phase.
- CO₂ will be compressed at the compression/pumping facility and a dense phase offshore pipeline will be used to transport the CO₂ from Tarragona to the injection facility located offshore.
- Depending on the scenario, the compression/pumping facility will handle CO₂ volumes from Tarragona, Barcelona, and Fos-Marseille emissions sources.

Figure 4-7 Location of the emitters - Tarragona cluster

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Table 4-5 Tarragona CO₂ emitters volumes considered for the Value Chain

Emitter ID	Facility name	Industry sector	CO ₂ emissions 2022 (Mt/y)	CO ₂ captured (Mt/y)	Fossil CO ₂ captured (Mt/y)	Biogenic CO ₂ captured (Mt/y)
S_ES_4	Repsol Refineria Tarragona	Refineries	1.968	0.935	0.933	0.00095
S_ES_24	Repsol Quimica	Chemicals	0.851	0.283	0.277	0.0058
S_ES_28	hemical Iberica (Jow Nord)	Chemicals	0.985	0.327	0.327	0.0
S_ES_47	Tarragona Power	Power	0.403	0.191	0.191	0.0
S_ES_77	Hyco (La Pobra De Mafument)	Hydrogen	0.303	0.244	0.244	0.0
TOTAL for Tarragona cluster			4.510	1.981	1.974	0.007

4.3.2.2 Barcelona cluster description

Figure 4-8 Location of the emitters - Barcelona cluster

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The list of emitters located in the Barcelona Cluster (Figure 4-8) can be found in Table 4-6 below.

- Captured CO₂ emissions will be transported along newly built pipelines which will connect individual emissions sites to a central gathering facility for CO₂ export.
- The pipelines connecting to the export facility are gas phase pipelines that operate at 3 MPa.
- The individual emitters gas phase pipelines will be connected to a compression or facility for CO₂ export. This export facility will be situated near Barcelona port and will transfer the CO₂ through an offshore dense phase pipeline to Tarragona or directly to the geological storage location, depending on the option.

Barcelona compression facility is described in section 4.5.5

Table 4-6 Barcelona CO₂ emitters volumes considered for the Value Chain

Emitter ID	Facility name	Industry sector	CO ₂ emissions 2022 (Mt/y)	CO ₂ captured (Mt/y)	Fossil CO ₂ captured (Mt/y)	Biogenic CO ₂ captured (Mt/y)
E_ES_13	Central Termica De Cicle Combinat (Sant Adria De Besos - Grup 4)	Power	0.648	0.308	0.308	0.0
E_ES_70	Central Termica De Cicle Combinat (Sant Adria De Besos - Grup 3)	Power	0.585	0.278	0.278	0.0
E_ES_20	Cementos Molins Industrial (Sant Vicenc Dels Horts)	Cement/Lime	0.934	0.577	0.507	0.07
E_ES_55	Fabrica De Montcada (Lafargeholcim Espana Sau)	Cement/Lime	0.426	0.263	0.211	0.052
E_ES_80	Central Termica De Cicle Combinat (Sant Adria De Besos - Grup 5)	Power	0.787	0.374	0.374	0.0
E_ES_103	Planta De Valoritzacio Energetica De Sant Adria De Besos	Energy from waste	0.285	0.217	0.109	0.108
E_ES_130	Barcelona Cartonboard	Paper and pulp	0.137	0.110	0.110	0.0
E_ES_144	Compania Espanola De Laminacion (Celsa 1-4)	Iron & Steel	0.148	0.0352	0.0352	0.0

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E_ES_232	Central Termica De Cicle Combinat (Port De Barcelona)	Power	0.356	0.089	0.089	0.0
TOTAL for Barcelona cluster			4.306	2.251	2.022	0.229

4.3.2.3 Fos-Marseille cluster

The list of emitters located in the Fos-Marseille Cluster (Figure 4-9) can be found in Table 4-7 below.

There are already existing projects in the Fos-Marseille cluster that are further along in their development (e.g. SYRIUS program, Callisto PCI project) and will be responsible for gathering the CO₂ emissions from industrial sites and transferring them to an export liquefaction facility. As a result, the CCUS ZEN project will not duplicate these efforts and will instead leverage these facilities to streamline the process.

The CCUS ZEN project will not consider the detailed design of the capture of CO₂ emissions from industrial sites as part of its scope. Instead, it will solely focus on the export facility and the associated CO₂ buffer storage located in the Fos-Marseille area. This means that the project will not consider the detailed development of a gathering network to capture CO₂ emissions from industrial sites and liquefaction facility as this is expected to be covered by existing projects already in development. Assumptions will be made for example by considering an onshore pipeline gathering network of around 50 km to allow WP4 to carry out the full assessment of the value chain.

Figure 4-9 Location of the emitters – Fos-Marseille cluster

A total volume of 5.535 Mt/y of captured CO₂ has been estimated for Fos-Marseille and will be used to size the transportation infrastructures required for the CCS value chain.

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Table 4-7 Fos-Marseille CO₂ emitters volumes considered for the Value Chain

Emitter ID	Facility name	Industry sector	CO ₂ emissions 2022 (Mt/y)	CO ₂ captured (Mt/y)	Fossil CO ₂ captured (Mt/y)	Biogenic CO ₂ captured (Mt/y)
E_FR_2	Arcelormittal Mediterranee	Iron & Steel	6.447	1.531	1.531	0
E_FR_8	Naphtachimie	Chemicals (other)	1.431	0.476	0.476	0
E_FR_10	Petroineos Manufacturing France Sas	Refineries	1.117	0.531	0.531	0
E_FR_15	Basell Polyolefines France Sas (Berre)	Chemicals	0.444	0.148	0.148	0
E_FR_17	Centre Production Thermique Ponteau - CCG de Martigues	Power	1.446	0.687	0,687	0
E_FR_28	Esso Raffinage Sas	Refineries	0.677	0.322	0,322	0
E_FR_55	Engie Thermique France - Cycfos	Power	0.732	0.348	0,348	0
E_FR_62	Lafargeholcim Ciments	Cement	0.368	0.227	0.210	0.017
E_FR_63	Evere Sas	Energy from waste	0.42	0.319	0.129	0.190
E_FR_65	Centrale Thermique de COMBIGOLFE	Power	0.574	0.273	0,273	0
E_FR_95	Total Raffinage France	Refineries	0.199	0.095	0,095	0
E_FR_122	Cifc	Cement/Lime	0.189	0.117	0.117	0
E_FR_132	Air Liquide France Industrie (Alfi)	Hydrogen	0.134	0.089	0.089	0
E_FR_136	Lyondell Chimie France Sas (Fos)	Chemicals (other)	0.205	0.068	0.068	0
E_FR_143	Chaux De Provence Sacam	Cement/Lime	0.107	0.066	0.066	0
E_FR_145	Imerys Aluminates Sa	Cement/Lime	0.157	0.097	0.097	0

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E_FR_146	Kem One France	Chemicals (other)	0.155	0.052	0.052	0
E_FR_151	Lyondell Basell Services France Sas	Power	0.193	0.092	0.092	0
TOTAL for Fos-Marseille cluster			14.995	5.535	5.328	0.207

4.4 CO₂ Specification at Emitters

The CO₂ composition will vary depending on the source:

- Captured from combustion/processing of fossil fuels.
- Generated from industrial processes.
- Extracted from high CO₂ containing hydrocarbons streams.
- Produced from natural sources.

In the context of CCS, CO₂ may come from large-scale combustion of fossil fuels, typically gas, oil or coal fired power plants but also from industrial processes. The different techniques for capturing the CO₂ from combustion power plants are commonly characterized as pre-combustion, post-combustion or oxyfuel processes.

Further, CO₂ may be captured from a range of industrial processes, e.g., steel manufacturing, cement manufacturing refineries and chemical industries. These processes may generate different types and amounts of chemical components in the CO₂ flow, such as CH₄, H₂O, H₂S, SO_x, NO_x, N₂, O₂, glycol and others.

The presence of one or more types of impurities can have adverse effects on CO₂ transportation and usage. Impurities typically have impacts on the thermodynamic properties of a CO₂ stream. They can also affect corrosion reactions and material selection.

Therefore, specifications were developed to limit the quantity of contaminants in the CO₂ stream being transported. It is highlighted that safe maximum impurity limits shall be selected for the whole CO₂ transportation chain. Indeed, acceptable limits for pipeline transportation condition may be unacceptable for other parts of the chain, like injection or storage. For instance, it is important to avoid precipitation of solid products since it may cause problems at the injection point and in the reservoir.

Selecting the allowable CO₂ content will add some extra costs to the overall cost of the capture and transportation system. Indeed, it will affect the level of purification of the CO₂ required after capture as well as the suitability of carbon steel material for transportation.

For CCUS ZEN project, the specifications presented in below Table 4-8 outline the minimum CO₂ purity requirements that must be met at the emitters site, for transportation of CO₂ by pipeline and ship.

It is assumed that high-purity CO₂ will be collected from the emission sources and will be compressed to a maximum of 3 MPa for introduction to the pipeline gathering network. The specification is based on the latest available data from Northern Lights

Figure 4-10 Impurities Impact on CO₂ rich stream (Fluid Phase Diagram) (Stokes et al., 2024)

Note 1: When multiple sources of CO₂ emissions are connected to the same pipeline gathering network, there is a risk that the CO₂ stream may not meet the original design specifications of the pipeline. This is especially true in the CCUS ZEN project, where CO₂ will be collected from various emissions sources and locations, making it challenging to ensure universal quality. Moreover, it is important to note that some clusters may transport CO₂ by ship, which has stricter specifications than pipeline transportation. To address this issue, it is assumed that the CO₂ will be conditioned at the emitter's site to meet the stricter specification, ensuring that it meets the necessary specifications for injection into the pipelines, compression, liquefaction and shipping.

Table 4-8 Typical Specifications of CO₂ at Emitters Site (Northern Lights, 2024)

COMPONENT	UNIT	LIMIT FOR CO ₂ SHIPPING WITHIN REFERENCE CONDITIONS ¹
Carbon Dioxide (CO ₂)	mol-%	Balance (Minimum 99.81%)
Water (H ₂ O)	ppm-mol	<30
Oxygen (O ₂)	ppm-mol	<10
Sulphur Oxide (SO _x)	ppm-mol	<10
Nitrogen Oxides (NO _x)	ppm-mol	<1.5
Hydrogen Sulfide (H ₂ S)	ppm-mol	<9
Amine	ppm-mol	<10
Ammonia (NH ₃)	ppm-mol	<10
Formaldehyde (CH ₂ O)	ppm-mol	<20
Acetaldehyde (CH ₃ CHO)	ppm-mol	<20
Mercury (Hg)	ppm-mol	<0.0003

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Carbon Monoxide (CO)	ppm-mol	<100
Hydrogen (H ₂)	ppm-mol	<50
Cadmium (Cd), Thallium (Tl)	ppm-mol	Sum<0.03
Methane (CH ₄)	ppm-mol	<100
Nitrogen (N ₂)	ppm-mol	<50
Argon (Ar)	ppm-mol	<100
Methanol (CH ₃ OH)	ppm-mol	<30
Ethanol (C ₂ H ₅ OH)	ppm-mol	<1
Total Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC) ²	ppm-mol	<10
Mono-Ethylene Glycol (MEG)	ppm-mol	<0.005
Tri-Ethylene Glycol (TEG)	ppm-mol	Not allowed
BTEX ³	ppm-mol	<0.5
Ethylene (C ₂ H ₄)	ppm-mol	<0.5
Hydrogen Cyanide (HCN)	ppm-mol	<100
Aliphatic Hydrocarbons (C ₃ +) ⁴	ppm-mol	<1,100
Ethane (C ₂ H ₆)	ppm-mol	<75
Solids, particles, dust	Micro-meter (µm)	<1

- ¹Reference Conditions means, with respect to vapor above the liquified CO₂ in a storage tank, a pressure ranges from 1.3 MPa to 1.5 MPa and the corresponding temperature range of approximately from -26.5 degree Celsius to -30.5 degree Celsius, respectively. If the vapor above the liquified CO₂ is within Reference Conditions, both the liquified CO₂ and the CO₂ vapor in all pressure-connected storage tanks shall be deemed to be within Reference Conditions.
- ²Total Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC) in addition to the ones listed separately in this specification, i.e., Ethanol, Methanol, Formaldehyde, Acetaldehyde, and BTEX, and includes the following components: 1-propanol < 1 ppm-mol, 2-butanol <1 ppm-mol, 1,2,4-trimethylbenzene <5 ppm-mol, Methyl acetate <10 ppm-mol, Acetone <10 ppm-mol, Hexanal <10 ppm-mol, Diethyl ether <10 ppm-mol, and Acetonitrile <10 ppm-mol. Other VOCs are not allowed
- ³BTEX refers to the following chemical compounds: Benzene, Toluene, Ethylbenzene and Xylene.
- ⁴Total number of hydrocarbons not to exceed 1,100 ppm-mol. Individual limits for groups of HCs: C3 <1,100 ppm-mol, C4-C5 < 815 ppm-mol, C6-C7 < 75 ppm-mol, C8-C9 < 8 ppm-mol. C10+ not allowed.

4.5 CO₂ pipeline transportation

Transportation of CO₂ through pipelines is feasible in both gas and dense phase. Gas phase transportation is often carried at pressures around 3 MPa, to limit the possibility of CO₂ condensation due to low ambient temperatures. Gaseous CO₂ transportation is often required in densely populated areas, where the construction of high-pressure pipelines is not allowed. Normally, dense-phase transportation is preferred since, for a given pipeline internal diameter, a larger volume of CO₂ can be transferred. Given the ambient temperature constraints, to avoid any CO₂ vaporization in dense phase pipelines, the CO₂ is usually transported at pressure above 8 MPa. On the other hand, the maximum operating pressure is limited to around 15 MPa, value constrained by the costs originating from the pipeline thickness. Moreover, depending on the location of the pipeline, the pressure of the CO₂ may vary. Offshore pipelines typically allow higher pressures than onshore pipelines. For onshore pipelines, to overcome pressure losses, booster stations may be usually located approximately every 100 km. Although the conditioning required for pipeline transportation eventually depends on the “source” of the CO₂ and its conditions before entering the pipeline, compression is usually required to increase the pressure of the CO₂ from the pressure level at the outlet of the capture facility to the pressure required for pipeline transportation.

Defining design conditions and margins is key for pipelines design.

- **Design Pressure:** Industry codes and standards state that the MAOP (Maximum Allowable Operating Pressure) can be equal to or less than the design pressure and the MAIP (Maximum Allowable Incidental Pressure) cannot be greater than 10% of the MAOP. If the pressures are defined such that the MAIP exceeds the design pressure, then these excursions are limited to a discrete duration.
- **Design Temperature:** The maximum design temperature is typically set to 50°C. Above 50°C the yield strength of carbon steel line pipe is derated which results in an increase in wall thickness.

A comparison of typical CO₂ conditions for pipeline transportation can be found in Table 4-9.

Table 4-9 Comparison of CO₂ conditions for pipeline transport (DEA, 2024, page 127)

Condition	TEMPERATURE (°C)	Pressure (MPa)	Density (kg/m ³)
Liquid	-28–5	1.5–3	1100
Dense	5–25	8–11	800–1000
Gas	5–25	2.5–3.5	<1000
Supercritical	>31	>7.5	<600

A summary of the different CO₂ transportation solutions envisaged for each option is provided in Table 4-10 below. A focus on the selection of the various pipeline selection and sizing is provided in the following sections.

Table 4-10 Transportation solutions for each option

	Option 1 Reference Case	Option 2 Alternative Case
Barcelona Emitters Cluster Gathering network	Two Gas phase pipelines collecting CO ₂ from emitters	Two Gas phase pipelines collecting CO ₂ from emitters
Tarragona Emitters Cluster Gathering network	One Gas phase pipeline collecting CO ₂ from emitters	One Gas phase pipeline collecting CO ₂ from emitters
Fos-Marseille Emitters Cluster Gathering network	Onshore gas pipelines collecting CO ₂ from emitters	Onshore gas pipelines collecting CO ₂ from emitters
Barcelona cluster export	Offshore dense phase pipeline to Tarragona Export Hub	Barcelona CO ₂ will be transported directly to the subsea system at the storage site via offshore pipeline.
Fos-Marseille cluster export	Shipping up to Tarragona Export Hub	Shipping up to the FSU at the storage site.
Tarragona CO₂ Hub to Offshore Injection site	Dense phase pipeline to subsea injection system at the storage site. (CO ₂ volumes from all clusters)	Dense phase pipeline to subsea injection system at the storage site. (CO ₂ volumes only from Tarragona)

4.5.1 Gas Phase Pipeline Transportation description

The gas phase CO₂ is stable if pressure is kept below the critical pressure with operational safety margin. Often maximum operational pressure is set to 3–5 MPa, depending on the length of pipeline and end of pipeline conditions needed.

Due to the low density, this transport form requires relatively larger pipeline dimensions to transport the same amounts of CO₂ as the dense phase, and hence relatively high CAPEX in the pipeline construction and installation is expected. For that reason, this transport form is often used for short distances and relatively low throughput.

This solution is also favoured in populated areas as operating pressure is lower than dense phase pipeline, reducing safety risks.

- Captured CO₂ from the emitters will be transported in gas phase pipelines which will connect the emission sources to a CO₂ central compression or liquefaction facility in each cluster depending on the scenario.
- Transportation of CO₂ through the gas phase pipeline will be carried out at a pressure between 2–3 MPa.
- CO₂ will have been conditioned according to the minimum specifications described in section 4.4 at the emitter’s site.
- Gas phase pipelines will be designed using API 5L X80 Carbon Steel pipeline with a 300 lb flange rating with a maximum allowable pressure of 5 MPa.

4.5.2 Onshore Gas Phase Pipeline Gathering Networks

4.5.2.1 Tarragona cluster

The emissions from 5 emitters are collected via a single gas phase pipeline. The minimum temperature in the Tarragona area (5.1°C) is used as a worst-case scenario. Pressure downstream the CO₂ Capture Unit and Purification (Dehydration) Unit is taken as 0.3 MPa. The flow rate is calculated assuming 8000 hours of operation per year. Pipe size and inlet pressure calculations are performed using Schlumberger's PipeSim® software. The pressure at the gathering facility located in Tarragona is taken as 2.1 MPa. GERG 2008 compositional model is used for the determination of phase changes, a pure CO₂ stream is assumed to flow inside the pipes though. The smallest inner pipe diameter that keeps the pressure low enough is chosen to prevent the condensation of CO₂ during the flow. In Tarragona, a single trunk line is used to transport the CO₂ to the gathering facility.

Figure 4-11 Left - Tarragona gas phase pipelines

Figure 4-12 Right - Pipeline Segment Code ES_24_28

Closeup views of the pipeline segments are shown in Figure 4-11, Figure 4-12, Figure 4-13, Figure 4-14 and Figure 4-15.

Figure 4-13 Left- Pipeline Segment Codes ES_28_04 and

Figure 4-14 Right- Pipeline Segment Code ES_77_47 ES_04_77

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Figure 4-15 Pipeline Segment Code ES_47_GF

A total of 15,684 m of pipe is used to transport 1.981 MT/y CO₂ with a maximum CO₂ flow rate of 247.68 t/hr. The gas velocity throughout the pipeline is calculated in between 4.41 m/s and 11.90 m/s.

Table 4-11 Tarragona gas phase pipeline length and elevation change information

Pipeline	FROM	TO	Elevation Gain/Loss	Pipeline Length
Segment Code	(Emitters ID)	(Emitters ID)	(m)	(m)
ES_24_28	S_ES_24	S_ES_28	13.4/-21.0	2,148
ES_28_04	S_ES_28	S_ES_04	2.86/-4.24	591
ES_04_77	S_ES_4	S_ES_77	0.65/-2.54	294
ES_77_47	S_ES_77	S_ES_47	93.4/-130	10,865
ES_47_GF	S_ES_47	Gathering Facility	6.4/-24	1,786
Total Pipeline Length	-	-	-	15,684

Maximum inlet pressure in the pipeline is estimated as 3.05 MPa at the Facility S_ES_24. Pipeline sizes increase as the additional CO₂ added to the pipeline at each facility along the line (Table 4-12).

Table 4-12 Tarragona gas phase pipeline pressure and pipe size information

Pipeline	CO ₂ Emissions Transported	Pressure at Emitters Site		Nominal Diameter	Size (ID)	Size (OD)	Pipe Wall Thickness
		(t/hr)	(MPa)				
Segment Code	Mt/y	(t/hr)	(MPa)	(mm)	(in)	(in)	(mm)
ES_24_28	0.283	35.37	3.05	200	7.625	8.625	12.7
ES_28_04	0.610	76.31	2.93	250	9.564	10.75	15.0622
ES_04_77	1.545	193.16	2.88	300	11.376	12.75	17.4498

Deliverable 3.1. CCUS value chains for two regions

ES_77_47	1.790	223.75	2.83	450	16.126	18.00	23.7998
ES_47_GF	1.981	247.68	2.24	450	16.126	18.00	23.7998
Total CO ₂ from Tarragona	1.981	247.68	-		-	-	-

At each facility CO₂ is captured in a CO₂ Capture Unit, followed by a Purification (Dehydration) Unit and compressed using a two-stage compressor.

Figure 4-16 Compressor network schematic that is used to compress CO₂ comes from Capture and Purification Unit

A preliminary sizing exercise has been performed to assess the compression and cooling needs on the gathering and compression facility located in Tarragona. This is a high-level design and a detailed process design has not been carried out at this stage of the project. The design will need to be verified with compressor vendors.

The inlet pressure to the compressor is 0.3 MPa. First-stage compressors increase the pressure to 1.4 MPa so that the gas temperature is kept below 150°C. The first heat exchanger reduces the gas temperature to 40°C. A second stage of compression then increases the gas pressure to the required inlet pipe pressure to transport CO₂ towards the gathering facility. Another heat exchanger decreases the gas temperature to 30°C. A schematic of the compressor system is shown in Figure 4-16 Compressor network schematic that is used to compress CO₂ comes from Capture and Purification Unit.

The power consumption and cooling duty at each facility is calculated using PipeSim® as well. An adiabatic efficiency of 75% was used for the compressor duty calculation (

Table 4-13, Table 4-14).

Table 4-13 Compression and Cooling Duty for the Stage 1 of the compressors in Tarragona Cluster

STAGE 1	P _{in}	Compression Duty	P _{out}	Temp.	Cooling Duty	T _{out}
Emitter ID	(MPa)	(MW)	(MPa)	(°C)	(MW)	(°C)
S_ES_24	0.3	1.222	1.4	145.5	0.999	40
S_ES_28	0.3	1.415	1.4	145.5	1.157	40
S_ES_4	0.3	4.039	1.4	145.5	3.301	40

Deliverable 3.1. CCUS value chains for two regions

S_ES_77	0.3	1.057	1.4	145.5	0.864	40
S_ES_47	0.3	0.827	1.4	145.5	0.676	40

Table 4-14 Compression and Cooling Duty for the Stage 2 of the compressors in Tarragona Cluster

STAGE 2	P _{in}	Compression Duty	P _{out}	Temp.	Cooling Duty	T _{out}
Emitter ID	(MPa)	(MW)	(MPa)	(°C)	(MW)	(°C)
S_ES_24	1.4	0.608	3.05	106.7	0.803	30
S_ES_28	1.4	0.667	2.93	103.3	0.882	30
S_ES_4	1.4	1.876	2.88	102.4	2.479	30
S_ES_77	1.4	0.472	2.83	100.1	0.626	30
S_ES_47	1.4	0.241	2.24	79.7	0.335	30

4.5.2.2 Barcelona Cluster

The emissions from 9 emitters are collected in gas phase via two routes. Only one of the emitters is located on the Eastern part (S_ES_55), and CO₂ from 8 emitters are collected with a pipeline in the Western part. Two lines connect in the Gathering and Compression Facility where CO₂ is compressed to a dense phase for both options. In Option 1, an offshore pipeline transports CO₂ to the Tarragona Gathering Facility, whereas in Option 2, the dense phase CO₂ is transported via an offshore pipeline directly to the storage site and the subsea injection system. The minimum temperature in the Barcelona area (5.5 °C) is used as a worst-case scenario for gas-phase transportation. Pressure downstream the CO₂ Capture Unit and Purification (Dehydration) Unit that are used by the emitters is taken as 0.3 MPa. The flow rate is calculated assuming 8000 hours of operation per year. Pipe size and inlet pressure calculations are performed using Schlumberger's PipeSim® software. The pressure at the gathering and compression facility located in Barcelona is taken as 2.1 MPa. GERG 2008 and E300 compositional models are used for the determination of phase changes, a pure CO₂ stream is assumed to flow inside the pipes. The smallest inner pipe diameter that keeps the pressure low enough is chosen to prevent the condensation of CO₂ during the flow.

Deliverable 3.1. CCUS value chains for two regions

Figure 4-17 Left - Barcelona gas phase pipelines.

Figure 4-18 Right - Pipeline Segment Code ES_55_00 (Table 4-15).

A total of 49,076 m of pipe is used to transport 2.25 Mt/y CO₂. The length of the Eastern part is 8,550 m, while the length of the Western part is 40,526 m. The eastern part transports a total of 0.263 Mt/y of gaseous CO₂ with a maximum rate of 32.85 t/hr. On the other hand, Western part transports a total of 1.987 Mt/y with a maximum flow rate of 248.39 t/hr. The gas velocity throughout the pipelines is calculated in between 4.99 m/s and 6.60 m/s in the Eastern part and between 2.45 m/s and 11.21 m/s in the Western part.

Figure 4-19 Left - Pipeline Segment Code ES_130_144

Figure 4-20 Right - Pipeline Segment Code ES_144_20

Figure 4-21 Left - Pipeline Segment Code ES_20_232

Figure 4-22 Right - Pipeline Segment Code ES_232_103

Deliverable 3.1. CCUS value chains for two regions

Figure 4-23 Pipeline Segment Codes ES_103_70, ES_70_13, ES_13_80 and ES_80_00

Table 4-15 Barcelona Eastern part gas phase pipeline length and elevation change information

Pipeline	FROM	TO	Elevation Gain/Loss	Pipeline Length
Segment Code	(Emitters ID)	(Emitters ID)	(m)	(m)
ES_55_00	S_ES_55	Gathering Facility	96.3/-147	8550
Pipeline Length	-	-	-	8550

Table 4-16 Barcelona Western part gas phase pipeline length and elevation change information

Pipeline	FROM	TO	Elevation Gain/Loss	Pipeline Length
Segment Code	(Emitters ID)	(Emitters ID)	(m)	(m)
ES_130_144	S_ES_130	S_ES_144	30/-52.7	3218
ES_144_20	S_ES_144	S_ES_20	41.5/-52.7	5309
ES_20_232	S_ES_20	S_ES_232	131/-152	18330
ES_232_103	S_ES_232	S_ES_103	144/-141	12597
ES_103_70	S_ES_103	S_ES_70	1.76/0.0	58
ES_70_13	S_ES_70	S_ES_13	0.25/0.0	77
ES_13_80	S_ES_13	S_ES_80	1.25/-1.85	92
ES_80_GCF	S_ES_80	Gathering Facility	6.53/-7.72	845
Pipeline Length	-	-	-	40526

Deliverable 3.1. CCUS value chains for two regions

Maximum inlet pressure in the pipeline is estimated as 2.96 MPa at the Facility S_ES_130 and 2.63 MPa at the Facility S_ES_55. Smaller diameter pipes are used in the top hill sections and pipeline diameter increases with an increase in the transported CO₂ amount.

Table 4-17 Barcelona Eastern part gas phase pipeline pressure and pipe size information

Pipeline	CO ₂ Emissions Transported		Pressure at Emitters Site	Nominal Diameter	Size (ID)	Size (OD)	Pipe Wall Thickness
	(Mt/y)	(t/hr)					
Segment Code	(Mt/y)	(t/hr)	(MPa)	(mm)	(in)	(in)	(mm)
ES_55_GCF	0.263	32.85	2.63	200	7.625	8.625	12.7
Total CO ₂ from Barcelona East	0.263	32.85	-	-	-	-	-

Table 4-18 Barcelona Western part gas phase pipeline pressure and pipe size information

Pipeline	CO ₂ Emissions Transported		Pressure at Emitters Site	Nominal Diameter	Size (ID)	Size (OD)	Pipe Wall Thickness
	(MT/y)	(t/hr)					
Segment Code	(MT/y)	(t/hr)	(MPa)	(mm)	(in)	(in)	(mm)
ES_130_144	0.110	13.78	2.96	150	5.761	6.625	10.9728
ES_144_20	0.145	18.18	2.85	200	7.625	8.625	12.7
ES_20_232	0.722	90.25	2.79	400	14.314	16.00	21.4122
ES_232_103	0.811	101.38	2.50	400	14.314	16.00	21.4122
ES_103_70	1.028	128.51	2.19	400	14.314	16.00	21.4122
ES_70_13	1.306	163.26	2.19	400	14.314	16.00	21.4122
ES_13_80	1.614	201.76	2.18	450	16.126	18.00	23.7998
ES_80_GCF	1.987	248.39	2.17	450	16.126	18.00	23.7998
Total CO ₂ from Barcelona West	1.987	248.39	-	-	-	-	-

At each facility CO₂ is captured in a CO₂ Capture Unit, followed by a Purification (Dehydration) Unit and compressed using a two-stage compressor.

A preliminary sizing exercise has been performed to assess the compression and cooling needs on the gathering and compression facility located in Barcelona. This is a high-level

Deliverable 3.1. CCUS value chains for two regions

design and a detailed process design has not been carried out at this stage of the project. The design will need to be verified with compressor vendors.

The inlet pressure to the compressor is 0.3 MPa. First-stage compressors increase the pressure to approx. 1.4 MPa. To keep the gas discharge temperature below 150°C. The first heat exchanger reduces the gas temperature to 40°C. A second stage of compression then increases the gas pressure to the required inlet pipe pressure to transport CO₂ towards the gathering facility. Another heat exchanger decreases the gas temperature to 30°C. A schematic of the compressor system is shown in [Figure 2-7](#).

The power consumption and cooling duty at each facility are calculated using PipeSim® as well. An adiabatic efficiency of 75% was used for the compressor duty calculation ([Table 4-19](#) & [Table 4-20](#)).

Table 4-19 Compression and Cooling Duty for Stage 1 of the compressors in Barcelona Cluster

STAGE 1	P _{in}	Compression Duty	P _{out}	Temp.	Cooling Duty	T _{out}
Emitter ID	(MPa)	(MW)	(MPa)	(°C)	(MW)	(°C)
S_ES_55	0.3	0.765	0.89	102	0.524	40
S_ES_80	0.3	0.980	0.81	93	0.630	40
S_ES_13	0.3	0.810	0.81	93	0.521	40
S_ES_70	0.3	0.732	0.81	93	0.471	40
S_ES_103	0.3	0.573	0.81	93	0.369	40
S_ES_130	0.3	0.341	0.94	107	0.241	40
S_ES_144	0.3	0.106	0.93	106	0.075	40
S_ES_20	0.3	1.730	0.92	105	1.204	40
S_ES_232	0.3	0.253	0.87	99	0.170	40

Table 4-20 Compression and Cooling Duty for Stage 2 of the compressors in Barcelona Cluster

STAGE 2	P _{in}	Compression Duty	P _{out}	Temp.	Cooling Duty	T _{out}
Emitter ID	(MPa)	(MW)	(MPa)	(°C)	(MW)	(°C)
S_ES_55	0.89	0.836	2.64	139	1.026	30
S_ES_80	0.81	1.080	2.17	131	1.311	30
S_ES_13	0.81	0.893	2.18	131	1.083	30
S_ES_70	0.81	0.805	2.19	131	0.979	30

Deliverable 3.1. CCUS value chains for two regions

S_ES_103	0.81	0.628	2.19	131	0.763	30
S_ES_130	0.94	0.370	2.96	144	0.241	30
S_ES_144	0.93	0.116	2.85	143	0.143	30
S_ES_20	0.92	1.893	2.79	142	2.333	30
S_ES_232	0.87	0.275	2.50	137	0.337	30

4.5.3 Dense Phase Pipeline Transportation description

For dense phase CO₂ transportation, the requirement is that pressure is kept above the critical pressure (i.e. 7.38 MPa), and the temperature shall be kept below the critical temperature (i.e. 31 °C). The pressure can be increased above 15 MPa depending on the end user specifications and pressure drop in the pipeline, but for practical reasons, the pipeline inlet pressure is often chosen to be between 8–15 MPa, depending on pressure drop and pipeline length. The operation temperature is chosen to be in the 10–25 °C range.

- A dense phase pipeline can be onshore or offshore depending on the scenario.
- An offshore dense phase pipeline will be used to transport the captured CO₂ from the Tarragona Hub and compression facility to the offshore injection point for the reference case.
- Transportation of CO₂ through the dense phase pipeline will be carried out at a pressure of approximately 15 MPa.
- Dense phase pipelines will be designed using API 5L X80 Carbon Steel pipeline with 1500 lb flange rating (designed to 25.5 MPa upper working pressure) with a maximum working pressure of 20 MPa.

4.5.4 Offshore Dense Phase Pipelines

An offshore dense phase pipeline is foreseen to send CO₂ from Barcelona to Tarragona and from the Tarragona hub to the offshore storage site. The volumes to be transported will be different depending on the case.

Transport from Barcelona to Tarragona – Option 1 (Reference Case).

4.5.4.1 Selection of the dense phase pipeline option

Different alternatives exist to transport the captured CO₂ from Barcelona cluster to Tarragona CO₂ Hub: shipping, onshore or offshore gas phase transport, onshore or offshore dense phase transport.

Pipeline transportation is favoured over shipping for the transportation of captured CO₂ from the Barcelona cluster to the Tarragona CO₂ Hub. This is because pipeline costs are dominated by CAPEX, which means that higher flow rates allow the CAPEX to be spread over higher CO₂ volume, resulting in significantly lower unit costs for high flow rates. On the other hand, shipping costs are dominated by OPEX and are less sensitive to flow rates. Pipeline costs are also highly sensitive to distance, as CAPEX costs are proportional to distance. In contrast, shipping costs are far less sensitive to distance, with fuel costs being a small component of the overall costs. While shipping may be cheaper than pipeline transport for high distances and low flow rates, the breakeven distance of shipping increases as the flow rate increases. Therefore, for a higher flow rate, pipeline transport unit costs decrease, making it a more cost-effective option for transporting captured CO₂.

Figure 4-24 The offshore pipeline between Barcelona and Tarragona

Approximately 2.25 Mt/y for the full value chain of CO₂ (CCS and CCU) are expected to be transferred from Barcelona to Tarragona. The distance between Barcelona and Tarragona is approximately 106 km (Figure 4-24).

To facilitate a selection between shipping and pipeline for the transportation of captured CO₂ from Barcelona to Tarragona a public report was used (Element Energy, 2018).

To showcase the impact of the flow rate on the comparison of pipeline and shipping costs, Figure 4-25 shows the unit costs of both transport options for flow rates from 0.1 Mt/y to 10 Mt/y, in the case of a transport distance of 100 km (left graph) and 400 km (right graph).

For the case of 2.25 Mt/y and a distance of approximately 100 km pipeline unit cost per ton of CO₂ is less than the one for shipping, hence pipeline transportation is favored.

Transporting captured CO₂ from Barcelona to Tarragona can be achieved through either an onshore or offshore pipeline. While an onshore pipeline may be a bit cheaper option in terms of capital expenditure (CAPEX), it is not a preferred option due to social and environmental issues, hence an offshore shallow water pipeline is chosen as the most practical and sustainable option for transporting CO₂ from Barcelona to Tarragona. The construction of an onshore pipeline would require land acquisition, which can result in the displacement of communities and destruction of natural habitats. This can lead to legal and environmental issues, which can delay the project and increase costs. These factors can have a negative impact on the local community and the environment. Furthermore, due to the relatively shallow water (approx. 100 m) in this area, an offshore pipeline could be easier to construct and install.

To further develop and solidify the concept of transporting CO₂ through an offshore pipeline, a decision has been made regarding the state of the CO₂ that will be transferred. The chosen method is an offshore dense phase pipeline that will serve both cases. For the reference case, the dense phase pipeline will merge with the Tarragona pipeline upstream of the compression station and for the alternative case, the dense phase pipeline will be routed directly to the offshore storage location and the subsea injection system. The pipeline will operate at

pressure of approximately 11–12 MPa, which means that it will be thinner and easier to transport and install in the seabed. This will result in lower costs and reduced complexity during installation. Additionally, the dense phase transportation will provide flexibility in managing fluctuations in demand, allowing large volumes of CO₂ to be stored in the pipeline during periods of low demand minimizing the need of CO₂ buffer storage at Barcelona cluster. Moreover, since both CO₂ export cases from Barcelona include dense phase transportation, decarbonization of Barcelona industrial cluster is further derisked.

Figure 4-25 Breakeven flow rates of pipeline transport for two different transport distances (Element Energy, 2018).

Overall, this concept offers a cost-effective, efficient, and flexible solution for transporting CO₂ through an offshore pipeline. Additionally, it will help to reduce the complexity of the Tarragona compression facility, which will have lower compression demand.

4.5.4.2 Sizing of the dense phase pipeline

Consequently, in the reference case, all the CO₂ that is collected at Barcelona Cluster will be sent to Tarragona by an offshore dense phase pipeline of around 106 km. The flow rate to be transported is 2.25 Mt/y.

Arrival pressure of Barcelona CO₂ Emissions to Tarragona Gathering Facility is approximately 11.1 MPa. The pipe length is determined as 106 km for the pipeline from Barcelona to Tarragona and the maximum water depth reaches 80 m. The pressure at the Barcelona Gathering and Compression Facility is calculated using PipeSim®. Using the 8000 operational hours assumption, 281.3 t/hr of CO₂ is compressed. The compressor has two stages. The first stage increases the pressure from 2.1 MPa to 5.2 MPa. The compression duty of this phase is approximately 5.35 MW. The temperature is cooled down to 40°C with a cooling duty of 7.4 MW. The second stage increases the pressure to 12.5 MPa. The compression duty of the second stage is 4.6 MW. A cooling duty of 20 MW is required to decrease the temperature to 30°C.

Figure 4-26 Dense phase offshore pipeline (red lines) concept from Barcelona to Tarragona. Blue contour lines with numbers are water depth (in meters). The source of the map: <https://map.openseamap.org/>

The pipeline's internal diameter of 12.5 in with a wall thickness of 19.05 mm is required. The outer diameter of the pipe is 14.00 inch, and the nominal diameter is 350 mm.

4.5.4.3 Transport to storage site – Option 1 (Reference Case)

In the reference case, all the CO₂ is collected at Tarragona Hub and sent to the injection site by an offshore pipeline. The flowrate to be transported is 9.767 Mt/y.

Figure 4-27 Dense phase offshore pipeline concept from Barcelona to Tarragona

The length of the sub-sea pipeline from Tarragona to Castellon is 48.1 Km which starts from the central compression facility in Tarragona and ends at the Castellon storage site. The elevation gain and loss are 10 m and 122 m, respectively. The subsea injection site is 105 m below sea level. This sub-sea pipeline will transport the CO₂ emissions captured in Tarragona, Barcelona and Fos-Marseille clusters, which makes a mass flow rate of 1,220.9 t/hr. The pipeline internal diameter that transports the dense phase CO₂, and the inlet pressure at the Tarragona Gathering and Compression facility is calculated using PipeSim® software

assuming a compressor discharge temperature of 30°C. The pressure at the wellhead is calculated as 7.92 MPa as explained in the coming sections. On top of the wellhead pressure, a 0.5 MPa of loss is added that would occur in the choke valve, therefore the pressure upstream of the choke valve should be 8.42 MPa.

The inner pipeline diameter is estimated as 17.938 in with a wall thickness of 26.1874 mm. The outer diameter of the pipe is 20 inches, and the nominal diameter is 500 mm. The inlet pressure of the pipeline in Tarragona should be 11.1 MPa. The velocity of the stream in the pipeline reaches to 2.7 m/s. The compressor for Tarragona emissions has two stages. The first stage increases the pressure from 2.1 MPa to 4.83 MPa. The compression duty of this phase is approximately 4.3 MW. The temperature is cooled down to 40°C with a cooling duty of 5.7 MW. The second stage increases the pressure to 11.1 MPa. Compression duty of the second stage is 3.9 MW. The temperature rises to 122°C. The cooling duty of the second heat exchanger is 17.4 MW. The pumping duty for the LCO₂ emissions from Marseille cluster is approx. 2.2 MW to raise the pressure from MP storage conditions (1.5 MPa) to 11.1MPa and the heating duty is approximately 26 MW. Barcelona emissions are expected to tie in the Tarragona gathering facility, but no further compression is foreseen as the CO₂ will be compressed in Barcelona compression facility.

4.5.4.4 Transport to storage site – Option 2 (Alternative Case)

The Alternative case considers two dedicated dense-phase pipelines: one from Tarragona, one from Barcelona, sending dense-phase CO₂ to the storage site.

Tarragona Offshore dense phase pipeline

In the alternative case, captured CO₂ from Tarragona emitters will be sent to the injection site by an offshore dense phase pipeline. The flow rate to be transported is therefore lower than the base case and accounts for 1,981 Mt/y. The mass flow rate assuming 8000 hours per year operational time becomes 247.6 t/hr. The discharge temperature of the compressor is taken as 30°C. The pressure at the wellhead is calculated as 7.92 MPa as explained in the coming sections. On top of the wellhead pressure, a 0.5 MPa of loss is added that would occur in the choke valve, therefore the pressure upstream of the choke valve should be 8.42 MPa.

The pipeline internal diameter of 9.564 in with a wall thickness of 15.0622 mm is required. The outer diameter of the pipe is 10.75 inch, and the nominal diameter is 250 mm. Larger pipe diameters increase the cost of the pipeline as well as a risk of gas phase occurrence due to the reduced pressure need 12 in the inlet side. The required inlet pressure is estimated as 11.35 MPa at Tarragona. The liquid velocity reaches 1.86 m/s.

The compressor has two stages. The first stage increases the pressure from 2.1 MPa to 4.83 MPa. The compression duty of this phase is approximately 4.3 MW. The temperature is cooled down to 40°C with a cooling duty of 5.7 MW. The second phase increases the pressure to 11.35 MPa. The compression duty of the second stage is 4 MW. The temperature rises to 124°C. The cooling duty of the second heat exchanger is 17.60 MW.

Barcelona Offshore dense phase pipeline

In the alternative case, captured CO₂ from Barcelona emitters will be sent to the injection site by an offshore dense phase pipeline of around 130 km.

The flow rate to be transported is only the emissions from the Barcelona cluster which accounts for 2.25 Mt/y. The mass flow rate assuming 8000 hours per year of operational time becomes 281.3 t/hr. The temperature of the CO₂ coming out of the compressor is taken as

30°C. The pressure at the wellhead is calculated as 7.92 MPa as explained in the coming sections. On top of the wellhead pressure, a 0.5 MPa of loss is added that would occur in the choke valve, therefore the pressure upstream of the choke valve should be 8.42 MPa.

The pipeline internal diameter of 12.5 in with a wall thickness of 19.05 mm is required. The outer diameter of the pipe is 14.00 inch, and the nominal diameter is 350 mm. The required inlet pressure is estimated as 12.98 MPa in Barcelona. The liquid velocity reaches 1.26 m/s.

The compressor has two stages. The first stage increases the pressure from 2.1 MPa to 5.22 MPa. The compression duty of this phase is approximately 5.36 MW. The temperature is cooled down to 40°C with a cooling duty of 7.4 MW. The second stage increases the pressure to 12.98 MPa. Compression duty if this stage is approximately 4.8 MW. The temperature rises to 130°C. The cooling duty of the second heat exchanger is 20.3 MW.

4.5.5 Tarragona CO₂ Hub and Compression Terminal

A CO₂ gathering and compression hub will be in Tarragona.

The CO₂ Pipeline Terminal is expected to have the following functionality depending on the nature of the import method:

- Ship unloading facilities (including jetty and berths).
- Heating and/or pumping to achieve the selected CO₂ storage conditions.
- CO₂ buffer storage.
- Vapor management (requirements to be determined).
- Plant utilities and control.
- Compression/pumping.
- Heating/cooling.
- Metering.
- Pigging facilities.
- Land valve station

4.5.5.1 Tarragona CO₂ Hub and Compression Terminals – Reference Case

For the reference case, Tarragona CO₂ Hub will handle the emissions sources from the three Clusters and then commingle them into one offshore dense phase pipeline for storage to the offshore location.

- CO₂ emissions from Tarragona arrive in the gathering facility via a gas phase pipeline at 2 MPa.
- CO₂ emissions from Barcelona arrive in the gathering facility via a dense phase pipeline at 11.1 MPa and are connected to the emissions from Tarragona downstream of the Tarragona compression system.
- CO₂ emissions from the Fos-Marseille area arrive in the gathering facility via LCO₂ carrier at MP conditions (15 bar and -33°C) and are stored in the temporary buffer storage located in the Tarragona Gathering Facility. After passing through the storage the CO₂ is pumped to 11.1 MPa and heated up to approximately 30°C to commingle with the rest of the CO₂ from the other cluster, into the offshore dense phase pipeline to the offshore injection location.

The following table summarizes the concept and the flowrates scenario at Tarragona CO₂ Hub for the reference case (Table 4-21):

Table 4-21 Base Case Flowrate Scenario

BASE CASE	FROM Emitters TO Tarragona	FROM Emitters TO Barcelona	FROM Barcelona TO Tarragona	FROM Fos Marseille TO Tarragona	FROM Tarragona TO Offshore Storage
Quantity (Mt/y):	1.981	2.25	2.25	5.535	9.767
Flow rate (t/hr)	247.7	281.3	281.3	691.9	1220.9
Condition	Gas Phase Pipeline	Gas phase Pipeline	Dense phase Pipeline	LCO ₂	Dense Phase

4.5.5.2 Tarragona CO₂ Hub and Compression Terminal – Alternative Case

For the alternative case, the Tarragona gathering facility will handle only the emissions sources from the Tarragona Cluster since the Barcelona cluster will be transported directly to the storage site via an offshore pipeline and Fos Marseille cluster will transport the CO₂ to the Floating Storage and Injection Unit by ship. Emissions from Tarragona and Barcelona will be compressed and transported separately for storage to the offshore location. The Table 4-22 summarizes the concept and the flow rates scenario for the alternative case.

Table 4-22 Alternative Case Flowrate Scenario

ALTERNATIVE CASE	From emitters to Tarragona	From Tarragona to Wellhead	From Emitters to Barcelona	From Barcelona to Wellhead	From Fos Marseille to FSIU	From FSIU to Wellhead via Riser
Quantity (Mt/y):	1.981	1.981	2.250	2.250	5.535	5.535
Flow rate (t/hr)	247.7	247.7	281.3	281.3	691.9	691.9
Condition	Gas Phase Pipeline	Dense Phase Pipeline	Gas phase Pipeline	Dense Phase Pipeline	LCO ₂	Dense Phase Riser

4.6 CO₂ transportation by ship

CO₂ transportation by ship is considered for CO₂ coming from the Fos-Marseille cluster in the Mediterranean-2 value chain, either to the Tarragona gathering hub (reference case) or FSIU (alternative case).

4.6.1 Ship Operating Conditions

For transport via shipping, CO₂ must be chilled to reduce its vapour pressure to a low enough value to enable an economic design for the LCO₂ tankers. Low vapour pressure translates to thinner-walled (lighter) storage tanks.

- Most studies in the literature consider modest pressure levels (<20 bar) as this will ensure high CO₂ density without requiring too high-pressure tanks. Current Liquefied CO₂ (LCO₂) ship designs are being developed for the carriage of CO₂ at the following conditions:

- Low-pressure conditions: Around a few bars above the triple point (0.52 MPa, -56°C) approx. 0.7–0.9 MPa and approx. -50°C. These conditions will result in the highest CO₂ density 1150 kg/m³ and lowest thickness of pressure tanks. The low temperature will however require more comprehensive (expensive) insulation and the use of low-temperature steel types.
 - Medium pressure conditions: 1.5–2 MPa and -25 to -30°C (The most common conditions for transport of liquid CO₂ today). This density of CO₂ around 1070 kg/m³.
 - High-pressure conditions: 4.5–7.2 MPa and ambient temperatures are also envisaged by some shipping entities. However, this is less developed than MP and LP conditions

The ship design will be different for the different transport conditions. The selection of CO₂ transport conditions will also affect the export terminal design and the CO₂ liquefaction plant to some extent.

4.6.2 Selection of Ship Operating Conditions

The current LCO₂ carriers are operating in the MP condition which ensures the tank operating range is away from the CO₂ phase diagram triple point allowing sufficient margin to manage a pressure loss scenario reducing the risk of liquid to solid state change of cargo. Also allowing for the differing compositions of CO₂ which will be shipped.

In addition, the MP carriage of LCO₂ is a technically more mature method already deployed in the food and beverage industry, coupled with the extensive valuable operating knowledge gained in the Liquid Petroleum Gas (LPG) shipping industry.

The alternative option for LCO₂ carriage is to adopt the low-pressure (LP) range. This option could allow to reduce the weight and cost of the storage tanks onboard the ship. However, carriage at lower pressure requires superior material due to the lower temperatures as compared to MP carriage. The LP concept has not been deployed and is a novel concept, however, all industry work going forward from Shipyards, Classification societies and design houses is focused on LP carriage condition for LCO₂ transportation by Ships. Work is required to develop the concept, including maturing the design and instrumentation of all the additional equipment required to manage the risk of moving nearer to the CO₂ phase triple point.

MP Shipping operating conditions are therefore selected for the project. This could be revised in a later stage when the LP transport will be more developed.

4.6.3 Liquid CO₂ carrier sizing data

LCO₂ carrier sizing will take into account the following data Table 4-23.

Typical shipping size will be between 10,000 to 35,000 m³. A preliminary logistic study will be conducted as part of WP4 technical definition to confirm the ship capacity, number of ships required as well as buffer storage needed at each terminal facility.

4.6.4 CO₂ Liquefaction

A simplified block flow diagram of a CO₂ Liquefaction facility is presented in Figure 4-28. Note that the configuration will be essentially the same for MP or LP operation, however, lower refrigerant operating pressures and temperatures are required for the LP version. This building block presents a CO₂ Liquefaction facility consisting of the main components such as shell and tube heat exchangers, refrigerant compressor(s) and vessels. CO₂ is fed to a chiller where it cooled to liquid conditions using a boiling propane refrigerant. Propane vapour from the chiller is firstly compressed and then condensed with the heat of condensation rejected to a suitable cooling medium. The cooling medium can be cooling water if easily available or a closed-loop cooling medium that uses air coolers or chillers. The pressurized liquified propane is returned to the chiller, where it is flashed to low pressure generating the low temperature

refrigerant required for the process. The liquefied CO₂ exits the chiller and is rundown to storage. Depending on the distance to the storage tanks, rundown pumps may be required.

Table 4-23 LCO₂ carrier sizing data LCO₂ carrier sizing data

PARAMETER	UNITS	BASE CASE	ALTERNATIVE CASE
Shipping route Description	-	Fos-Marseille to Tarragona	Fos-Marseille to FSU
Distance	km	470	460
Travelling speed	knots	10–14	10–14
Time at port: Offloading Loading	hour	17–20 18–20	17–20 18-20

Figure 4-28 CO₂ Liquefaction block flow diagram

4.6.5 CO₂ Buffer Storage and Port Facilities

In general, CO₂ is emitted by continuous industrial processes that can operate 24 hours/day, 365 days/yr. Shipping, however, is not a continuous process and allowance must be made for the following:

- Entry to port (possibly tide dependent)
- Docking and tying up at the jetty/quay
- Hook up to loading facilities
- Loading / unloading time
- Unhooking from loading facilities
- Completion of formalities (paperwork)
- Un-docking and leaving harbour (possibly tide dependent).

All this means is that LCO₂ needs to be stored whilst awaiting loading onto a ship. This is the basic requirement for the Buffer Storage and Port Facilities. LCO₂ is exported in 'parcels' of a given size dependent on a ship's capacity which dictates the minimum storage capacity required. Some 'ullage' is also added to the storage volume as a safety factor.

Enough storage capacity must be provided to allow for the CO₂ received during time between ships. The basic components are:

- Storage Tanks, generally bullets or spheres
- Loading Pumps (Export terminals)
- Jetty facilities (loading arms)
- Vapor handling systems (boil-off and vapor displaced during loading / unloading operations).

In general, storage tanks will operate at the same conditions as the ship's tanks, meaning that MP storage tanks are required for MP ships and LP tanks for LP ships. For these building blocks, storage bullets have been assumed. For the Mediterrean-2 value chain, a volume of approximately 1700 m³ is assumed for each bullet for the case of MP ships that are used in the concept.

4.7 Offshore Injection Facilities

Offshore injection facilities are required to inject the CO₂ into the geological reservoir. Very little information is available regarding the reservoir location and behaviour, wells' future location, etc (Ref. section 4.9). Several assumptions have therefore been taken and will need to be confirmed as the project progresses:

- Water depth around 100–150m.
- Project considered 1.09 Mt/y per injection well, in total 10 wells (9 wells + 1 extra surplus well for maintenance periods).
- Project considered 1 monitoring well.
- Assume vertical drilling to limit costs.
- Limited information regarding the reservoir specificities and pressure management strategy, hence, assume no need for brine management.
- Project significant expansion: not planned.

4.7.1 Option 1 (Reference Case)

Figure 4-29 Offshore injection facilities generic illustrations (wet tree platform, dry tree platform, full subsea development), (Source of pictures – Genesis website).

Several offshore injection facilities can be foreseen and have been compared based on a general pros/cons assessment while taking into account all uncertainties associated with the development.

Dry tree platforms such as steel jackets are usually relevant for limited water depth (up to 120-150m) and when injection wells' locations are well-known and in a limited perimeter. For deeper water, other platforms are possible (Tensioned leg platform, Spar, semi-sub) but become more costly. The advantage of fixed platforms lies in the feasibility of installing process equipment on the topside (e.g. brine handling or offshore compression if future expansion storage sites are further away). However, this equipment is not foreseen at this stage.

If a platform was to be selected, an unmanned installation would be recommended to limit safety risks associated with the transportation of dense phase CO₂ at high pressure and to minimize OPEX.

Wet tree platforms are also feasible but are generally more costly than dry tree platforms due to subsea production systems including umbilicals, drill centres, flowlines and manifolds as well as increased OPEX with workovers requiring drilling rigs. In our case, this solution is not recommended as it does not bring sufficient cost or flexibility benefits.

A full subsea development can be a more flexible solution compared to the fixed platforms and can be adapted to the uncertainties of the reservoir and well locations. It is also well suited for phased drilling if required. It minimizes safety risks and visual impacts which could influence public acceptance. Drawbacks are linked to the cost of maintenance which will require subsea intervention and workover rigs. All processing will have to be performed onshore but additional processing equipment is not foreseen at this stage of the project.

Based on the above general assessment and considering the very early phase of the project, associated assumptions and uncertainties, a full subsea system will be considered in the concept development. This could be reviewed at a later phase of the project when more reliable data will be available.

4.7.2 Option 2 (Alternative Case)

The Alternative case considers the CO₂ injection from the FSIU and from the offshore dense pipeline for the CO₂ coming from Tarragona and Barcelona.

The injection from the FSIU will be done through a riser and flowlines to be installed on the seabed up to the injection wells and manifolds.

As a subsea injection system will already exist for the FSIU and based on the recommendations from the previous section, a subsea injection system will also be considered for the injection of the CO₂ from the Offshore dense phase pipeline from Tarragona and Barcelona.

4.8 CO₂ storage site

The storage site considered for Mediterranean-2 CCUS value chain is an offshore storage site near Tarragona in the Ebro basin (Spain). This site is studied in the ongoing H2020 PilotSTRATEGY project (Fleury et al., 2023a; Fleury et al., 2023b). The targeted reservoir is in the upper Miocene Castellón Sandstones, which runs from approximately 1600m to 1900m overlain by the Ebro shales. Analysis of neighbour wells data predicted promising properties for reservoir and sealing. An application for a research permit for CO₂ storage in this area has been requested to the Spanish authorities by Repsol Exploration, S.A. in November 2023. Location of the permit area is shown on Figure 4-30.

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Figure 4-30 Location of the area concerned by the TARRACO₂ research permit.

First estimations of the storage potential in the area indicate a capacity over 200 Mt based on communication received by the project partner Repsol Exploration for the injection site. The reservoir's parameters are summarized in Table 4-24. Continuous injection of CO₂ in the reservoir is assumed with 20 years of storage and injection lifetime.

Figure 4-31 Structural map of the Castellon storage site (Gravaud et al, 2023)

Table 4-24 Reservoir parameters for Castellon storage site

Storage site parameters	Units	
Country		Spain
Site name		Castellon
Onshore/offshore		Offshore
Reservoir Lithology		Upper Miocene Castellon Sandstone
Cap rocks		Ebro Shales
Top depth	m	1600
Thickness	m	300-600
Reservoir pressure @1600m	MPa	16
Reservoir temperature @1600m	°C	74
Porosity	%	14-20
Permeability	mD	10-500
Average Storage Capacity	Mt	>200

4.9 CO₂ storage infrastructure

4.9.1 Injection Wells

In the present study, we consider a storage capacity of 200 Mt of CO₂ (Table 4-24) and a duration of injection operations of 20 years. The calculation of number of wells required for the injection of captured CO₂ mainly depends on the amount of CO₂ to be injected, well tubing sizes, and reservoir injectivity. As the tubing size in the wellbore decreases, the wellhead pressure increases which results in a higher compression capacity. Well size should be designed considering the available CO₂ amount. The injectivity of the well is a function of fluid properties such as viscosity, but mainly reservoir properties such as reservoir thickness and rock permeability. The size of the reservoir has an effect, but assuming a steady state system where injected CO₂ displaces the same amount of water out of the aquifer, its effect becomes almost negligible. The radial inflow equation for a steady state flow condition in terms of average reservoir pressure can be written as follows:

$$(\bar{P} - P_w) = \frac{q\mu}{2\pi kh} \left(\ln \frac{r_e}{r_w} - \frac{1}{2} \right)$$

Where \bar{P} and P_w are average reservoir pressure and bottom hole flowing well pressure in atm, q is the reservoir flow rate in cm³/s, μ is the viscosity in cP, k is permeability in Darcy, h is reservoir thickness in cm, r_e and r_w are the reservoir drainage radius and wellbore radius, respectively. The injectivity can be calculated with the following equation:

$$\frac{q}{(\bar{P} - P_w)} = \frac{2\pi kh}{\mu} \frac{1}{\left(\ln \frac{r_e}{r_w} - \frac{1}{2}\right)}$$

The reservoir drainage radius assuming a circular reservoir and given the storage capacity of 2.8 Mt/km² (Repsol presentation, Madrid 2023), can be estimated as 4768.3 m for 200 Mt of storage capacity. The wellbore radius is taken as 7 inches (0.1778 m) which is a common size for injection wells. The viscosity and density of CO₂ is estimated as 0.0386 cP, and 513.94 kg/m³ by GERG-2008 equation of state at 16 MPa and 74 °C.

Using the highest permeability and thickness values known as a range for the reservoir (0.5 Darcy permeability and 600 m thickness), the injectivity of the well is calculated as 0.735653 Mt/year/MPa. Including Tarragona, Barcelona and Fos-Marseille emissions, total CO₂ to be injected makes 9.7669 Mt/y. Considering 9 vertical wells, each well needs to inject 1.085 Mt/y. Based on the calculated injectivity, required drawdown pressure ($\bar{P} - P_w$) can be calculated as -1.475 MPa. Knowing the average reservoir pressure, 16 MPa, the bottom hole pressure can be calculated as 17.475 MPa.

Using the average case permeability and thickness values (0.1 Darcy and 300 m), the drawdown pressure increases ten times and becomes 14.7 MPa. In return the bottom hole pressure requirement reaches 30.7 MPa, which could be not possible as it might exceed the reservoir fracturing pressure and design pressures for the compressor, tubing and pipeline.

4.9.2 Existing Infrastructure available

Many existing wells are registered in the Ebro offshore storage area, and 13 are in the perimeter of the TARRACO2 permit (Figure 4-32). However, none of them could be considered for repurposing for CO₂ injection, nor crosses the targeted structure. The majority is plugged and abandoned. Drilling new wells should be considered.

4.9.3 New Infrastructure needed

The continuous CO₂ injection will be performed through new wells with an assumption that there is no need for brine production wells. Uncertainties associated with pressure management in the reservoir will be highlighted in the risk identification activity in WP4.

Due to the lack of public data about the Castellon storage site, the location of the injection point can only be estimated. It has been placed in the middle of the area concerned by the TARRACO2 research permit (Figure 4-32).

Considering injecting at the reservoir base, the well depth should be 2000m (MD).

Table 4-25 Coordinates of injection point

Coordinates (WGS 84)	Latitude	Longitude
Injection point	40.6664	1.1999

Based on data from the surrounding wells, the water depth at the injection point is about 95 - 120 metres. In Google Earth, it is given as 105 m.

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Figure 4-32 Location of existing wells in the area of the TARRACO2 permit. The purple point indicates the planned injection point.

4.9.4 Drilling technics

Figure 4-33. Example of deep high-pressure tubing sizing (Bellarby, 2009)

A vertical well schematic is given in Figure 4-33. The well is drilled with a large bit and progressively the bit size is reduced. According to the final depth, the formation pressure and amount of injection requirements the size of the final casing is decided. For the offshore injection wells, 7 inches or 7 5/8 inches are common.

The wellhead pressure is calculated using the Schlumberger PipeSim® software. A schematic of the wellbore is given in Figure 4-34. The casing dimensions are ignored as the design of the wellbore requires confidential reservoir data and it does not affect the wellhead pressure calculations if the assumed tubing size fits inside the wellbore. The tubing size is taken as 3.476 inches inner diameter (ID) with a wall thickness of 6.6548 mm. The final casing inner diameter is taken as 5.92 inches.

Figure 4-34 Well schematic. (Source: The figure is drawn using Schlumberger PipeSim® Software)

The reservoir thickness is given as 300 m to 600 m, and the top of the formation is at 1600 m. Therefore, drilling the well up to 1900 m, and installing packers to 1600 m would allow us to perforate the casing in the formation and setting the tubing to 1800 m. Given the injectivity 0.735653 Mt/y/MPa as calculated before, the pressure requirement at the wellhead is calculated as 7.92 MPa. The bottom hole pressure is calculated as 17.4 MPa in line with the analytical calculations done previously (Figure 4-35).

Figure 4-35 Well Pressure / Temperature Profile. (Source: The figure is drawn by Schlumberger PipeSim® Software)

4.10 CO₂ storage monitoring

The Ebro offshore storage site will require implementation of a monitoring plan to track the smooth and safe running of operations. This is not the objective of the project to provide a detailed plan, as it is an early phase study. However, we provide the main guidelines related to legal requirements.

4.10.1 Operation monitoring

Injection wells should be equipped to measure standard parameters and allow continuous monitoring of well head, annulus, and downhole pressure; well head and reservoir temperature; well integrity (see section 2.5.4). A fall-off test could be planned once a year.

Monitoring must also include measurements of volumetric flow and chemical composition of injected CO₂.

To monitor CO₂ plume behaviour during injection operations, seismic campaigns should be performed. A baseline acquisition is required before the operations start, so that future

acquisitions will be able to detect the perturbation induced by the CO₂ injection. Then, regular acquisitions must take place, during the 20 years of injection, to monitor the CO₂ plume spread in the reservoir. Feedback from Sleipner storage site is a 3D seismic every 2 years, on average. In the Northern Lights program, planned intervals between seismic repeats are longer, 2-4-7-10 years. In our project, we recommend considering a 3-years interval between repeats during injection operations (conservative hypothesis). Moreover, additional campaigns could be necessary in case of deviation from the expected pattern. After injection stops, during a post-closure period that lasts minimum 20 years, interval between seismic repeats can be extended to 5 years. The area of the permit amounts to 759 km². However, the surface covered by the monitoring campaign should be smaller. At this early stage, it is not possible to estimate precisely the extent of the CO₂ plume. Thus, we make the hypothesis that the monitored zone will represent half of the permit area, i.e. 380 km². The 4D seismic monitoring campaign shall cover the extent of the impacted area in the reservoir; at this early stage, as it is not possible to estimate the exact extent to be covered, we estimate that it represents roughly half the permit area (759 km²), i.e. 380 km².

Figure 4-36 Position of the seismological stations near the concession (in brown), map coordinates in WGS84 reference. EPOB is manned by the National Geographic Institute of Spain IGN, the others by the Catalunya Cartographical and Geological institute ICGC. Red contours are bathymetric depth contours. Sources: FDSN (Federation of Digital Seismograph Networks) station database (FDSN, 2024), European Marine Observation and Data Network database for bathymetry and coastline (EMODnet, 2024). Seismological stations: COBS - offshore station (ICGC), EPOB - station in Vimbodi (IGN), CBUD - station in Illa de Buda (ICGC), REUS - station in Reus (ICGC), VNIG- station in Villanova (ICGC).

Seismological monitoring is likely to be mandated by the regulatory authorities after the 2013 offshore earthquake at CASTOR site. Fortunately, the area in the vicinity of the projected reservoir is already equipped with several stations manned by ICGC (Institut Cartogràfic i Geològic de Catalunya) and IGN (Instituto Geográfico Nacional), including an offshore real-time station (COBS) right at the eastern limit of the concession (Figure 4-36).

At the time of this report, COBS station doesn't appear in the publicly available data stream from ICGC servers, depending on its status (working or out of order) and the availability of data it may be necessary to install another offshore real-time seismic station; on the coast, additional stations should be installed but the number can be limited to 2 or 3 additional

stations in order to get a correct coverage. Such a network should get seismic events with a magnitude $M_w > 2$ (estimation based of existing regional networks). Additionally, even if the site is offshore, a monitoring well is recommended as the reservoir is an aquifer and not a well-known structure as it would be for a depleted reservoir.

4.10.2 Environmental monitoring

Before starting injection, a baseline for the marine environment monitoring must be performed, including marine pelagic and benthonic biota survey, and seabed survey of shallow (<100 m) geographical and geological features including possible natural flux of CO₂ or other gasses. Additional surveys should take place where the storage complex may interact with locations where endangered species reside, identified by the baseline survey (for instance, near the injection wells or above possible CO₂ leak paths).

As they can be a leakage pathway, all legacy wells, exploration, appraisal and production wells should be identified and evaluated (location, abandonment, leakage risk). In the TARRACO2 permit area, a dozen of wells from the 70's and 80's are identified and listed in the Table 4-26 (source: Hidrocarburos – InfolGME <https://info.igme.es/infogeof/>). Gas detecting sensors should be planned at the seabed close to the location of these wells to monitor potential leakage.

Table 4-26 Legacy wells in the TARRACO2 area.

WELL	COMPANY	DRILLING YEAR	COORDINATES (WGS 84)			TOTAL DEPTH (m)	EXPLORATION OBJECTIVE	STATUS
			X	Y	Z			
SALMONETE-1A	SHELL	1985	1.1640319074465992	40.70449320239942	-101	3849	Hydrocarbons	P&A
SALMONETE-1	SHELL	1983	1.1641874577849762	40.704293250732974	-101.5	3982	Hydrocarbons	
PULPO-1	SHELL	1980	1.2635051473447447	40.72374417825125	-125	3579	Hydrocarbons	
CASTELLON-B-13	SHELL	1988	1.1827414599504777	40.558650988852094		3250	Hydrocarbons	P&A
CASTELLON-B-12	SHELL	1985	1.2281207683587922	40.60954683132127	-133	2871	Hydrocarbons	
CASTELLON-B-10	SHELL	1984	1.2952537795383705	40.671268117229886	-120	2980	Hydrocarbons	
CASTELLON-B-09	SHELL	1982	1.184327283077721	40.62232192491694		3290	Hydrocarbons	
CASTELLON-B-08	SHELL	1982	1.2937482200043746	40.6714319260426		2900	Hydrocarbons	
CASTELLON-B-07	SHELL	1981	1.1814273301072262	40.5928406949422		2200	Hydrocarbons	P&A
CASTELLON-B-06	SHELL	1979	1.2740167921413104	40.67344020030504	-117.3	2922	Hydrocarbons	P&A
CASTELLON-B-05	SHELL	1976	1.3076654301155486	40.67715718015978	-117.3	3768	Hydrocarbons	P&A

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CASTELLON-B-04	SHELL	1974	1.2521911525996643	40.62262780233124	-112	2776	Hydrocarbons	
CASTELLON-B-01	SHELL	1968	1.1824940780393263	40.580904256925976	-97.8	2833.8	Hydrocarbons	

4.11 CO₂ use options

4.11.1 Project Overview

Like the Baltic-2 case, the following sections describe some indicative projects in the countries of interest even if they are not located inside the clusters. Indeed, the advantage of a CCU value chain is that it can be replicated in different locations, as long as there is a supply of CO₂ (industrial, biogenic, atmospheric) and a demand for CCU products.

Table 4-27 Indicative on-going and upcoming CCU projects in the Mediterranean territory

Country	City	Project / Technology	Amount of CO ₂ used	Product per t CO ₂
France	Marseille	Hynovera : Catalytic conversion methanol and SAF	Approx. 123 kt/a	Approx. 0.3 kg synthetic jet fuel
France	Marseille	Jupiter1000 demo : Thermal and chemical conversion into methane	Approx. 45kg/h	Approx. 0.36 kg methane (25m ³ /h)
France	Le Teil (north of Marseille)	eM-Rhône Catalytic methanol production	Approx. 190 kt/a	Approx 0.72 kg methanol
Spain	Galicia (northwest of Tarragona)	GREEN MEIGA Catalytic methanol production	Approx. 140 kt/a	Approx 0.72 kg methanol
Spain	A Coruna (northwest of Tarragona)	Triskelion Catalytic methanol production	Approx. 56 kt/a	Approx 0.72 kg methanol
Spain	Biscay (northwest of Tarragona)	AggrecaO2 Mineralisation	Approx. 2.2 kt/a	-
Spain	Alicante (south of Tarragona)	CEMEX/ETFuels Catalytic methanol production	Approx. 450 kt/a	Approx 0.72 kg methanol

eM-Rhône (France)

EM-Rhône is an Innovation Fund supported project that combines renewable hydrogen production from water electrolysis and temporary storage, full scale carbon capture from a cement installation using cryogenic technology and methanol synthesis. The goal of the project is to produce approx. 140 kt/a of renewable methanol with a potential for duplication of the concept in a separate location in France (CO2Value Europe, 2024).

Jupiter 1000 (France)

The Jupiter 1000 project pioneers the conversion of surplus renewable power into green hydrogen and synthetic gas (syngas) for storage. This industrial demonstrator features a 1 MWe-rated electrolysis system and a methanation process with carbon capture. It leverages two electrolyzers with distinct technologies, exclusively powered by 100% renewable energy sources. The setup incorporates an innovative methanation technology, while carbon dioxide capture occurs at an adjacent industrial facility. Methane is produced at 25m³/h. The success demonstrated by this initiative will inform the development of technical and economic standards for full-scale installations of this kind, with the ultimate goal of launching Power to Gas activities in France. By 2050, this Power to Gas system has the potential to generate over 15 TWh of gas annually (Jupiter1000, 2024).

Hynovera (France)

Hynovera aims to produce hydrogen, E-Kerosene, E-Diesel, and E-Methanol in southern France as a green and circular economy solution to the planned closure of the Meyreuil/Gardanne coal-fired power plant. It leverages its strategic location in the Aix-Marseille metropolitan area with access to transportation infrastructure. The project addresses local renewable fuel demand and will be rolled out in two phases, focusing on E-Kerosene production at an industrial scale compatible with aviation sector decarbonization. These products are derived from biogenic CO₂ and renewable hydrogen from water electrolysis powered by local green electricity through a long-term PPA. Capacity is planned to be 130MW electrolysis and 123 kt/y CO₂. Production would reach 32.000 t/year for e-SAF, and 700 t/year for e-Diesel. Key partnerships have been established with major entities like Marseille airport, Airbus Helicopters, and Corsica Ferries (Hynovera, 2024).

CEMEX/ETFuels (Spain)

CEMEX has entered into an agreement with ETFuels, a green fuels producer, to convert CO₂ emissions from CEMEX's Alicante cement plant in Spain into green fuels. This groundbreaking carbon utilization project signifies significant progress in testing and scaling technologies aimed at expediting decarbonization in cement production. Under this partnership, ETFuels will combine up to 450,000 metric tons of captured CO₂ annually with green hydrogen to create more sustainable fuels, particularly green methanol (e-methanol) (CEMEX, 2024).

Green MEIGA (Spain)

An Innovation Fund supported project, GREEN MEIGA will produce approx. 100 kt/a of synthetic methanol. The project integrates hydrogen production through hybrid PEM, SOEC and co-SOEC systems, synthesis of methanol and development of capture systems integrating enzyme-based and direct air capture. GREEN MEIGA will also develop a strategic plan to replicate the concept in additional sites (CO2Value Europe, 2024).

AggregaCO2 (Spain)

A further Innovation Fund supported project on the non-energetic CCU application of captured CO₂. AggregaCO₂ focuses on the Air Pollution Control (APC) residues from Waste-to-Energy installations and combines them with captured CO₂ to generate aggregates that permanently bind CO₂. Approximately 2.2 kt/a of CO₂ will be chemically bound to approx. 22 kt/a of APC through an Accelerated Carbonation Technology (ACT) to yield approx. 56 kt/a of aggregates that can substitute conventional aggregates and at the same time avoid the burden of treating APCs (CO₂Value Europe, 2024).

4.11.2 CCU value chain scenarios

Similar to the Baltic-2 case, we can identify three scenarios for the development of CCU value chains. One where the CCU facilities are located next or close to the emitter (Scenario 1; explored only for the cases of Tarragona and Barcelona since for the Marseille cluster, the emitter analysis is out of scope), one where they are located in the vicinity of the gathering station within each cluster (Scenario 2; first step of centralisation; likely smaller number but larger CCU facilities compared to scenario 1) and one where they are located in the vicinity of the Tarragona hub that gathers all streams (Scenario 3; second step of centralization).

Table 4-28 Scenarios of CCU capacity deployment in the Med-2 cluster

Scenario 1						
Country	Cluster	Captured CO ₂ from emitters (Mt/y)	Captured CO ₂ from emitters for CCU (Mt/y)	Number of CCU installations close to emitters	Average capture capacity of CCU installation (kt/y)	Average product capacity of CCU installation (kt/y)
Spain	Tarragona	1.97	0.59	max. 5	120 (Range: 60-280)	84 (for methanol) 36 (for synthetic jet fuel)
Spain	Barcelona	2.25	0.68	max. 8	85 (Range: 35-150)	61 (for methanol) 26 (for synthetic jet fuel)
France	Marseille	5.55	1.67	max. 18	93	70 (for methanol) 28 (for synthetic jet fuel)

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Scenario 2						
Country	Gathering station	Captured CO ₂ from emitters (Mt /y)	Captured CO ₂ from emitters for CCU (Mt /y)	Number of CCU installations per cluster	Average capture capacity of CCU installation (kt /y)	Average product capacity of CCU installation (kt /y)
Spain	Tarragona	1.97	0.59	3	200 <i>Assuming CO₂ capacity comparable to the Green MEIGA project</i>	144(for methanol) 72(for synthetic jet fuel)
Spain	Barcelona	2.25	0.68	4	170 <i>Assuming CO₂ capacity comparable to the Green MEIGA project</i>	123 (for methanol) 61 (for synthetic jet fuel)
France	Marseille	5.55	1.67	5	238 <i>Assuming CO₂ capacity comparable to the eM-Rhône</i>	171 (for methanol) 86 (for synthetic jet fuel)
Scenario 3						
	Collection Hub	Captured CO ₂ from all clusters (Mt /y)	Captured CO ₂ from all clusters for CCU (Mt /y)	Number of CCU installations close to collection hub	Average capture capacity of CCU installation (kt /y)	Average product capacity of CCU installation (kt /y)
Spain	Tarragona	9.77	2.93	8	366 <i>Assuming CO₂ capacity comparable to the CEMEX/ETFuels project</i>	256 (for methanol) 109 (for synthetic jet fuel)

As in the Baltic-2 case, mineralisation can't be illustrated in term of product capacities the same way as CCU fuels and chemicals as the limiting factor is not the CO₂ capture capacity

rather than the availability of the industrial residual fractions that are used to bind CO₂. As seen by the AggregaCO₂ project, the CO₂ needs can easily be covered by the available captured amounts in all scenarios, so mineralisation is a very valid options for all the clusters.

The capture and product capacity of the envisaged installations in the above table is comparable to the capacities of the ongoing and upcoming projects that have been described above, which renders all scenarios plausible. Scenarios 2 and 3 have in general considered a larger average capacity because they reflect concepts where CO₂ volumes have been centralized, hence the facilities may accommodate larger volumes. However, Scenario 3 is only applicable to the Reference case and shows more risks as the utilisation plants will be depending on the full CCS transportation value chain and associated cost.

Scenario 2 will therefore be considered for the WP4 further analysis.

4.12 Summary of Technical Parameters

Values below are based on a project duration of 20 years ([Table 4-29](#)).

Table 4-29 Mediterranean-2 Value Chain Technical Parameters Summary

Technical Parameters	Units	Mediterranean- 2 CO ₂ Value Chain	
Countries involved	-	Spain & France	
Project Duration	years	20	
-	-	Reference case	Alternative case
Number of emission clusters	count	3	3
Total number of emission sources	count	32	32
Total CO ₂ emissions	Mt	476.4	476.4
Annually captured CO ₂ emissions	Mt/y	9.77	9.77
Annually stored CO ₂ emissions ¹	Mt/y	6.7 – 9.33	6.7- 9.33
Annually used CO ₂ emissions ¹	Mt/y	0.44 - 3.07	0.44 - 3.07
Total CO ₂ emissions captured	Mt	195.4	195.4
Total CO ₂ emissions stored ¹	Mt	134 - 186.6	134 - 186.6
Total CO ₂ emissions used ¹	Mt	8.8 - 61.4	8.8 – 61.4
Total onshore pipeline distance	km	115	115
Total offshore pipeline distance	km	163	190

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Total pipeline distance	km	278	305
Maximum shipping distance	km	470	460
Total shipping distance	km	470	460
Number of Ports used	count	2	2
Number of offshore storage sites	count	1	1
Number of onshore storage sites	count	0	0
Total storage capacity	Mt	200	200
Average project duration	Year	20	20
Number of planned injection wells - total	count	10	10
Number of planned monitoring wells - total	count	1	1
Number of reused wells	count	0	0
Number of reused offshore platforms	count	0	0

Note 1: having a very precise split of total stored or used amounts of captured CO₂ was deemed very difficult to state as many uncertainties lie around the development of the CO₂ use plants. A range is therefore proposed to illustrate the possible quantities.

4.13 Non technical issues

This section introduces the key non-technical issues that shape the challenges and opportunities of pursuing CCUS in the countries that would be primarily concerned with the development of the Mediterranean-2 CCUS value chain: France and Spain. Drawing on a broader examination of non-technical issues presented in a white paper (Honegger et al., 2024), it first outlines the overall situations in each country including their national strategies pertinent to CCUS, second it outlines the status and applicability of international regulations, followed, third, by an overview of the regulatory conditions, fourth, governmental support, and finally, fifth, an overview of challenges in public perception that may be supporting or holding back necessary policy developments.

4.13.1 Overall Situation and National strategies

4.13.1.1 France

France has unveiled in June 2023 its CCUS strategy, aiming for carbon neutrality by 2050. It foresees an annual volume of 4-8.5 million tonnes of CO₂ stored by 2030 and between 30 and 50 Mt CO₂ per year in 2050 for all sectors (including biogenic CO₂). It prioritizes industrial areas including Dunkerque, Le Havre, Fos-sur-Mer, Lacq/Sud-Ouest, Loire-Estuaire, and

Grand Est. To advance project development and accelerate CCUS uptake, the French government plans to initiate a Contracts for Difference scheme through a tender process. The strategy's objectives also include establishing a CO₂ transport framework and conducting pilot tests at geological storage locations during 2024-2025. Marseille is one of the largest cities and boasts a key trading seaport as well as an industrial cluster in Fos-sur-Mer with plans to ship CO₂ to an offshore storage site in Italy (Ravenna, Callisto PCI). Many industrial sites are in proximity and around the Etang de Berre. Lyon is another big city in the region with its chemistry industry. In these regions, there is a strong willingness for industry decarbonisation and proactive stakeholders with potential plans on hydrogen. There have been discussions on hydrogen infrastructure development from Spain to Marseille.

On December 13, 2023, the Ministry of the Economy, Finance and Industrial and Digital Sovereignty presented the ecological transition contracts signed by the main French industrial companies with the highest CO₂ emissions. Among these contracts, Heidelberg Materials committed for emissions reduction at its Cements Calcia French sites, comprising the Beaucaire plant. Objectives are reduction of 19-43% by 2030, and of 91-96% by 2050.

According to final NECP reported by France in June 2024 (NECP-France, 2024), the SNBC 3 project scenario plans to capture 6.6 Mt in 2030. This volume includes 3.3 Mt captured in the primary metals sector (of which 0.5 Mt biogenic), 2.2 Mt in the chemical sector (of which 0.5 Mt biogenic) and 1.2 Mt (including 0.2 Mt biogenic) in the non-metallic minerals sector (in particular cement and lime). The total 1.2 Mt of biogenic CO₂ and 5.4 Mt of fossil CO₂ will be captured in 2030, and 10 % of this volume will be used for the production of e-fuels.

4.13.1.2 Spain

Though Spain has long indicated interest in developing CCUS toward its climate efforts and in 2010 introduced regulation this has remained a largely theoretical possibility. While Spain's National Strategy for a Low-Emission Economy by 2050 foresees a significant role for CCS – including for the decarbonization of fossil powerplants – to reach the objective of an 80% reduction in emissions relative to 1990 levels it fails to outline a path to its implementation.

4.13.2 International regulations as applicable to the Mediterranean case countries

The proposed offshore storage site in Spain triggers the application of the 1995 Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Region of the Mediterranean (Barcelona Convention) and the London Protocol. The Barcelona Convention has seven protocols, including two Dumping Protocols. The original Dumping Protocol was adopted at the same time as the Convention itself in 1976. The 1976 Protocol follows the “black- and grey-list approach” for regulating dumping activities. The blacklist (Annex I) lists the wastes and other matter that cannot be dumped, and the grey list (Annex II) lists the wastes and other matter that may be considered for dumping having first acquired a special permit. All other wastes and other matter may be dumped with a general permit. Our assessment is that countries may store CO₂ with either a general or special permit issued in line with Annex III requirements.

Following global developments, the 1976 Dumping Protocol was amended in 1995. The 1995 Protocol is more like the London Protocol and departs from its predecessor's “black- and grey-list” approach in favour of the new “reverse-list” approach. Article 4 introduces a general ban on dumping and provides a limited list of exceptions to the ban. CO₂ is not included on the list of exceptions and would therefore be prohibited to store as storage falls within the definition of dumping. That said, the 1995 Protocol has not entered into force. This implies that the 1976

Protocol still applies under which storage may be permitted. If, however, the 1995 Protocol enters into force unamended, storage would be prohibited.

A Draft Framework for Risk Assessment and Management of Storage of CO₂ Streams in Geological Formations in the Mediterranean Basin was prepared in 2013 (UNEP(DEPI)/MED WG.387/Inf.14, 29 July 2013, Draft Framework for Risk Assessment and Management of Storage of CO₂ Streams in Geological Formations). The Framework provides generic guidance to the Contracting Parties to the Barcelona Convention and provides that storage should not be permitted by a Contracting Party without authorisation or regulation by their competent authorities. Any authorisation or regulation shall be in accordance with the abovementioned Framework, as updated from time to time.

Moreover, both France and Spain are Contracting Parties to the London Protocol. However, neither of the two States have accepted the 2009 amendment nor deposited a declaration of provisional application at the time of writing. However, France has recently (March 2024) concluded a Memorandum of Understanding with Denmark. As such, work is likely ongoing to enable the cross-border mechanism to export CO₂. Export for offshore storage cannot take place before Spain and France have concluded an arrangement or agreement in satisfaction of Article 6.2. It is not a requirement that the Contracting Parties accept the 2009 amendment to provisionally apply it, although preferable.

4.13.3 National regulations in the Mediterranean case countries

4.13.3.1 France

The French Environmental Code and the Mining Code together regulate the storage of CO₂, transposing the CCS Directive. The Mining Code has been revised in 2022, in the Law Energie Climat and a change was made to, inter alia, the granting of exploration permits. Previously, exploration permits were granted for five years, but could be renewed twice. Now, exploration permits can be issued once but for a period of 15 years. An additional period of two years, called development phase, is also available before “requesting a storage permit in order to focus on public acceptance” (EC, 2023). Storage of CO₂ is currently permitted onshore and offshore without specific limitations.

4.13.3.2 Spain

The CCS Directive was transposed by Law 40/2010 of 29th December of geological storage of carbon dioxide. For storage of <100 000 tonnes total, the Mining Law will apply. In the latest CCS implementation report, Spain confirms that “there is no limitation to select areas if the geological formation chosen as a storage site -under the proposed conditions of use- has no significant risk of leakage and no significant risk to the environment or human health” (EC, 2023). Generally, for onshore storage and exploration, the regional governments will be responsible. For offshore and exploitation, however, the national government will be responsible (Canteli, 2024).

4.13.4 Governmental support in the Mediterranean-2 scenario countries

4.13.4.1 France

Presently France does not have earmarked specific funding to CCUS projects despite several French companies being beneficiaries of EU funding. The French government has, however, outlined its approach to support Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage (CCUS) as part of its broader strategy to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and enhance industrial

sustainability. On June 23, 2023, French Prime Minister Elizabeth Borne presented the nation's CCUS strategy at a National Industry Council meeting. This strategy aims to capture 4 to 8.5 million tons of CO₂ annually by 2030, scaling up to 20 million tons by 2050. A consultation period was initiated, running until September 29, 2023, to gather feedback from manufacturers and stakeholders, ensuring the strategy's alignment with industry needs.

The government is considering a support scheme through contracts for difference (CCFD), to be awarded via a call for tenders. This scheme aims to back decarbonization projects identified through a comprehensive 50-site exercise. In early 2024 France's Industry Ministry has issued a call for interest in carbon capture and storage (CCS) at various sites to help decarbonize sectors like cement, steel, and aluminium production. Companies had until June 2024 to express interest, with initial storage potentially starting by 2027.

At national level, the development of CCUS technologies is supported under the 'France 2030' investment plan through the strategy for decarbonising industry with an overall budget of EUR 4.5 billion. Under the innovation component, the development of new technologies for capturing CO₂ is eligible for the calls for projects "DEMIBaC" and "IBAC PME" led by ADEME. A new support scheme to support large industrial decarbonisation projects, such as the installation of CO₂ capture units for geological storage, was announced in June 2023 and launched at the end of 2024 (NECP-France, 2024).

A public consultation on the draft tender specifications, accompanied by a call for expressions of interest, was published in June 2024, prior to the publication of the call for tenders.

France does not yet have a CO₂ geological storage capacity. Studies to assess these capacities were launched in early 2024. In addition, the 'France 2030' investment plan could devote EUR 25 to EUR 30 million to accompany the carrying out of studies or works to improve knowledge of the French basement capacities in terms of the storage of CO₂ (seismic campaigns or injection tests) (NECP-France, 2024).

4.13.4.2 Spain

Presently Spain does not have earmarked specific funding to CCUS projects, and the Spanish government has not outlined clear steps toward potential governmental funding support to CCUS activities. Though Spain's draft update national integrated energy and climate plan (NECP) for 2021–2030 (NECP-Spain, 2023) recognizes CCUS as a significant area of research, it does not outline specific policies to promote the technology during this period. However, the long-term strategy up to 2050 (Spanish Government (2020) identifies CCUS technologies as essential for decarbonizing industrial sectors that are difficult to electrify, such as cement, iron and steel, and the petrochemical industry.

Concerning CO₂ storage regulation, Spanish Law 40/2010 of December 29th on the geological storage of carbon dioxide was directly transposed from the EU Directive 2009/31/CE. This law establishes the legal framework for the safe and effective geological storage of CO₂, aligning Spain's regulations with European Union standards.

4.13.5 Public acceptance in the Mediterranean case countries

4.13.5.1 France

Few studies focus on the public perception of CCUS in France. One notable source is the 2011 Eurobarometer survey (EC, 2011), which revealed that over three-quarters of respondents were unaware of CCS technology. Of those surveyed, 34% believed CCS could effectively combat climate change, while 45% felt they would not benefit from its

implementation. Concerns about the technology included potential risks like water pollution. Additionally, nearly three-quarters of respondents expressed safety concerns about nearby CO₂ storage facilities, citing potential environmental, health impacts, and leaks. Similar conclusions were drawn regarding the near-inexistent public awareness of the technology by Ha-Duong et al. (2009). Most interviewees also in recent years were completely unaware of the technology (Oltra et al., 2022). Public acceptance of CCUS is currently considered low in France due to very low levels of technology awareness and limited trust in government (Honegger et al., 2023).

4.13.5.2 Spain

Initial research on public and social acceptance of CCS technologies in Spain was carried out between 2005 and 2010 as part of the Spanish PSE-CO₂ project. Early findings by Solá et al. (2007) revealed very low levels of public awareness about CCS technologies during the early stages of their development. As Spain began its first two CO₂ storage projects between 2010 and 2012, further studies on public acceptance were conducted. One notable study by Oltra and Sala (2012) focused on the Compostilla project, utilizing an online survey of residents in the affected region. This survey indicated a generally positive attitude towards CCS, with around 60% of respondents supporting the project and less than 20% opposing it.

More recent data from a representative sample of the Spanish population, as analyzed by Sala et al., (2017) showed a low level of familiarity with CCS technologies but a high level of interest. Initially, attitudes towards CCS were positive, and after respondents were provided with more information, their evaluations of the technology ranged from neutral to positive. The survey classified respondents into supporters (38%), neutrals (34%), and opponents (28%) of CCS, indicating a nuanced public perception that evolves with increased awareness and information.

In summary, public acceptance of CCUS is considered medium in Spain (Oltra et al., 2022; Honegger et al., 2024).

4.14 Integration of technical and non-technical issues and conclusions in the Mediterranean case

The Mediterranean Sea region shows a strong need of CCUS value chains with many emitters looking to capture and handle their emitted CO₂. The development of such a complete value chain will need to combine technical and non-technical challenges to make it a success. A more detailed analysis and project risk assessment will be developed as part of WP4 and will review all technical and non-technical aspects.

Regulatory Considerations

There is a limited readiness of regulatory frameworks and public acceptance which may require a longer time-horizon to operation. However, recent announcement in France show that governments are starting to develop a framework and objectives for the country.

Differing Advances in Capture, Storage, and Utilisation: The readiness level of capture solutions is noticeable, whereas the framework for carbon utilisation needs better integration. Additionally, the storage site development proposed is at a very early readiness level, hindering the selection presented in this report and feeding uncertainty into the transport network determined.

CO₂ Volume Management: The significant CO₂ emissions of the Spanish and France economies suggest a favourable balance for effective CCUS deployment. Highly concentrated emissions clusters in France and Spain are indicative of high potential economies of scale; however more complex permitting processes may cause delays and cost-increases.

Uncertainties in Transportation Infrastructures

The technical definition of the value chain demonstrates the need for large-scale transport infrastructure, including extensive pipeline networks (onshore and offshore), introducing cost and risk-related uncertainties. Transport routes may also be subject to non-technical aspects such as public acceptance and governmental support, which were not considered in the routing exercise. These factors can be impacted by the fear of consequences from failures such as leakages. Therefore, an appropriate risk and safety assessment and a clear and effective communication of it may allow for the public understanding of risks.

5 Short Projects Summary and Conclusions

The technical modelling of the two CCUS value chains, Baltic-2 and Mediterranean-2, selected from the two CCUS ZEN project regions, was performed in parallel with nontechnical parameters. The challenges, uncertainties and advantages were determined in all sections of the value chains and are described in this section.

5.1 Baltic-2 Scenario

The Baltic-2 CCUS project includes nine clusters of 33 emitters divided in two development phases from three countries (Denmark, Sweden and Germany) with an annual CO₂ emissions volume of 22.7 Mt and respective captured CO₂ volume of 20.1 Mt, from which up to 6.1 Mt will be directed for utilisation (CCU). Two CO₂ utilisation options (near emitters or near intermediate hubs) were considered, potentially converting the CO₂ into methanol or synthetic jet fuel. The storage locations include eight onshore, nearshore and offshore sites, in Denmark. The project is planned for 30 years of CO₂ storage in six DSA (deep saline aquifers), and for 20 years of CO₂ storage in two DOGFs. All CO₂ captured in the Bremen cluster will be utilised in a CCU sub-value chain. Emissions captured in the Gothenburg cluster which are not utilised, are sent to offshore geological storage sites in Denmark (Inez and Lisa). From Esbjerg, a ship with CO₂ from the remaining German industrial clusters and the Fredericia and Esbjerg clusters is sent to Greensand and Inez. All CO₂ that cannot be shipped from these clusters or that is captured from the remaining clusters is sent to a pipeline network. Using pipeline network, the CO₂ not used in a CCU installation in Aalborg is distributed to the geological storage sites Bifrost, Jammerbugt, Gassum, Voldum and Thorning.

The pipelines sized with nominal diameters between 6 to 30 inches and a total network length of approximately 1720 km.

Selected existing O&G production infrastructure offshore is planned to be retrofit, including some of the existing two production platforms and 15 production wells (5 in Bifrost and 10 in Greensand) for the injection of CO₂. Monitoring Programmes are planned according to requirements of DEA (DEA, 2024).

For the Baltic-2 scenario, regulatory readiness is different, for each of the three countries. The most developed part of the value chain is at the capture side, while CO₂ use, transport and storage require further accelerated development.

5.2 Mediterranean-2 Scenario

The Mediterranean-2 CCUS scenario is a transboundary project from France to Spain. It includes three clusters with 32 CO₂ emitters from two countries and one storage site offshore Spain in DSA. The included industrial clusters are the Tarragona and the Barcelona clusters in Spain, and the Fos-Marseille cluster in France, annually producing 23.82 Mt CO₂. The geological storage site is DSA located offshore Tarragona in the Ebro Basin. The captured 9.77 Mt CO₂ will be collected in the three clusters hubs, partly used depending on the viability of the CO₂ use options (biogenic emissions are around 0.44 Mt) and the remaining CO₂ will be transported and stored in Castellón site.

In the reference case, an onshore gathering hub at Tarragona port will collect the CO₂ from the three clusters: CO₂ from local Tarragona emitters, CO₂ from Barcelona cluster sent by an offshore dense phase pipeline and CO₂ from Fos-Marseille cluster transported by ships. From the onshore gathering hub at Tarragona, a single dense phase offshore pipeline will send the collected CO₂ to the subsea system including subsea injection wells around 60 km away (Figure 4-3).

In the alternative case, the offshore dense phase pipeline will only transport emissions from Tarragona cluster to the subsea system including subsea injection wells around 60 km away. Captured CO₂ from Barcelona cluster will be sent to the injection site by a dedicated offshore dense phase pipeline. Captured emissions from Fos-Marseille cluster will be shipped directly to the offshore storage site (Figure 4-6). Their injection will be via a Floating Storage and Injection Unit (FSIU) and the same subsea system s.

The limited readiness of regulatory frameworks and public acceptance in Spain and France may require a longer project implementation time. However, recent incentives in France show that governments are starting to develop a framework, financial support and objectives for the country.

The readiness of the different parts of the value chain is at different stage, being the less developed at the transportation infrastructure side in Spain and more developed in Fos-Marseille cluster. REPSOL EXPLORACIÓN, S.A. company has applied for the Exploration permit for CO₂ storage of Castellón site, which can be given soon and will give possibility for piloting and demonstration of CO₂ storage offshore Spain. Both countries have ongoing CO₂ utilization development and pilot projects. Ultimately the CO₂ utilization feasibility will be dependent on the availability of green energy or hydrogen available at an appropriate price level as well as the availability of non-biogenic CO₂ for e-fuels production

5.3 Technical Comparison of planned value chains

Both Baltic-2 and Mediterranean-2 CCUS scenarios are multinational and cross-border value chains, each including three and two countries, respectively. They include high volume CO₂ emission sources, producing annually approximately 23 Mt CO₂, in the Baltic-2 project and 24 Mt CO₂, in the Mediterranean-2 (see Table 5-1). In the Baltic-2 scenario about 50% of all emissions are from Germany, while in Med-2 about 63% of emissions are from France. There are regulatory obstacles for CO₂ storage in Germany and geological obstacles in France, leading to both countries higher interest in integrating transboundary CO₂ storage projects.

One of the most significant differences between the two projects is the availability of storage sites and storage capacity. Baltic-2 includes 8 storage sites onshore and offshore with total capacity about 1 Gt CO₂, while Med-2 includes only one storage site with estimated capacity of 200 Mt. Two offshore DOGF in Denmark – Greensand and Bifrost are currently piloting and demonstrating the first offshore cross-border CO₂ storage in the world, along with the first CO₂

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ship transport to Esbjerg from an external country, injected and stored in the depleted Nini West oil field, in the North Sea, during the Spring of 2023 (Greensand, 2024). Oppositely, Castellón Storage site in Spain is less ready, as in November 2023, the company REPSOL EXPLORACIÓN, S.A. applied for an exploration permit for CO₂ storage, called TARRACO2 and still waiting for the decision of the Spanish authorities. However, the onshore storage sites in Denmark are owned by landlords and public acceptance could be an issue for the onshore sites, while no such issues are expected for the offshore storage site in Spain.

Based on available storage capacity and captured CO₂ volumes, the Baltic-2 is planned mainly for 30 years, while Med-2 for 20 years. Overall, the Baltic-2 will store a larger total volume of CO₂, including a higher share bio-CO₂. It should be noted that Baltic-2 emitters already plan to produce a significant share of bio-CO₂ (30-40%) compared to small share in Med-2 (less than 5%). This difference resulted in different methodologies applied in the bio-CO₂ volumes estimation for both projects. The Baltic-2 scenario considered that some of the emitters in the Power sector will likely retrofit to biofuels (as communicated by the some of the respective plants), while in Med-2 only presently produced bio-emissions were applied.

Table 5-1 Summary of technical parameters of Baltic-2 and Mediterranean-2 value chains

Technical Parameters	Units	Baltic-2 CCUS Value Chain	Mediterranean-2 CCUS Value Chain, two cases
Countries involved		Denmark, Sweden & Germany	France & Spain
Project Duration	years	30	20
Number of emission clusters	number	9	3
Total number of emission sources	number	33	32
Total annual CO ₂ emissions	Mt/y	22.7	23.8
Annually total captured CO ₂ emissions	Mt/y	20.1	9.77
Annually captured bio-CO ₂ emissions (included in total CO ₂)	Mt/y	8.05	0.44
Annually stored CO ₂ emissions ¹	Mt/y	14.0	6.7 – 9.33
Annually used CO ₂ emissions ¹	Mt/y	6.1	0.44 - 3.07
Total CO ₂ emissions captured	Mt	603	195.4
Total CO ₂ emissions stored ¹	Mt	420	134 - 186.6
Total CO ₂ emissions used ¹	Mt	183	8.8 - 61.4
Total onshore pipeline distance	km	1464	115

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Technical Parameters	Units	Baltic-2 CCUS Value Chain	Mediterranean-2 CCUS Value Chain, two cases
Total offshore pipeline distance	km	256	163-190
Total pipeline distance	km	1720	278-305
Maximum shipping distance	km	210 - 330	460 - 470
Total shipping distance	km	1010	460 - 470
Number of Ports used	count	2	2
Number of offshore storage sites	count	5	1
Number of onshore storage sites	count	3	0
Total storage capacity	Mt	928	200
Number of planned injection wells - total	count	41	10
Number of planned monitoring wells - total	count	10	1
Number of reused wells	count	Max.18	0
Number of reused offshore platforms	count	Max. 3	0

In the Baltic-2, emitters that are most likely planning to invest in CCUS were selected at the emitter selection stage. In the Mediterranean, the emitters were not filtered at the emitter selection stage, but during the capture capacity calculation according to the methodology explained by in part 4.

Considering 8 storage sites in Baltic-2 versus one site in Med-2, the planned technical parameters of Baltic-2 include significantly higher availability for the infrastructure including total pipeline and shipping distance, 41 injection wells versus 10, and 10 monitoring wells versus 1 in Med-2. At the same time, Baltic-2 plans to retrofit existing platforms and wells in two offshore DOGFs in Denmark. However, for the injection of about two times more CO₂ in Denmark, it is planned to use 4 times more injection wells and ten times more monitoring wells than in Spain, for overall CCUS project to construct 5-6 times more pipelines, and total shipping distance will be more than two times higher in Baltic-2 than in Med-2 project. The shorter total pipelines distance in Med-2 is explained by location of the emitter's clusters in Med-2 close to the ports. All this gives possibility to assume the higher transport and storage costs per ton CO₂ in Baltic-2 than in Med-2, while this could be proved only in WP4.

Concerning impact against climate change, the Baltic-2 is planning to store and use up to 3 times more CO₂ emissions than Mediterranean-2 project during the full project duration.

5.4 Conclusions

- Both Baltic-2 and Mediterranean-2 projects are cross-border projects including CO₂ emission sources from three and two countries, respectively, with storage in one country each.
- CO₂ flow rates to be captured, transported and stored are limited in Med-2 project by the recently reported storage capacity of one Castellon site offshore Spain, while there are no such limitations in Baltic-2, using 8 storage sites onshore and offshore North Sea with total mean capacity above 1 Gt CO₂.
- The onshore storage sites in Denmark are owned by landlords, that potentially can cause public acceptance issues, while such risk is much less for the offshore sites in Denmark and Spain.
- Countries participating in the value chains have now many industrial emitters producing fossil and some bio-CO₂. The largest emissions volumes are produced in Germany and France, which have regulatory or geological limitations for CO₂ storage in their countries.
- Regulatory bases are more ready in Denmark, than in Spain. Denmark already awarded permits for CO₂ storage demonstration, with first injections made already for offshore fields in Denmark, with cross-border transported CO₂. In Spain, the exploration permit application from November 2023 for CO₂ storage is waiting now the decision from the legal authority to be ready in November 2024.
- The infrastructure for CO₂ transport is not yet developed in both projects, however the CO₂ terminals are already planned in Fos-Marseille within the Callisto PCI and Bifrost and Norne PCIs in Denmark. Additionally, infrastructure projects in the regions are in the research and development phases.
- Considering planned infrastructure, the Mediterranean-2 project can be less heavy and will make less impact to the environment planning less injection and monitoring wells, and pipelines per one ton of CO₂ injected compared to Baltic-2, explained by close location of emission clusters to ports and only one storage site included. However, the Baltic-2 can get higher revenues from the higher total bio-CO₂ used (in total 3-20 times higher than in Med-2).
- The countries involved in the projects have different levels of regulatory readiness, planned climate strategies and national financial support to CCUS projects.
- There is a large uncertainty in both projects in all parts of the value chain, including CO₂ capture, use, transport and storage and transportation options due to the early stage of the development.
- Regulations for CO₂ and bio-CO₂ utilisation and storage certification are not yet ready, therefore not all emitters and countries are reporting produced bio-CO₂.
- Reusing of wells and infrastructure is only possible for hydrocarbon fields, for which the corresponding capacity is close to depletion. Such option is available in two DOGF in Denmark. In Spain, all hydrocarbon infrastructure is too old, abandoned and cannot be reused.

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